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Climate Change and the Challenge Of Global Security & Sustainable Development: The Schism Between The United States And China In Focus

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ABSTRACT

The planet has undergone repeated distortion through human-related activities. The renewed activities of science and technological advancements of an industrialized craze world has left our environment under regular pollution and all forms of degradation. The resultant climate change has been major threats to life (man, animal and plants) and our environment. This phenomenon has attracted global attention since the 1980s. Thus, this paper is an addition to the discourse on climate change. This paper adopts the secondary source of data collection. Works of several scholars on climate change were presented and analyzed. The main polluters of global environment; the US and China were also spotlighted. The paper concludes by calling for more commitment of the industrialized world to adhere to the climate change protocols to ensure that the target of 1.5°C global temperature by 2050 is achievable and rid the world of the negative consequences of global warming. Some recommendations including a prompt migration by industrialized states from fossil fuels usage to renewable energy were made. This paper is of tremendous value to scholars who are interested in finding solution to the challenge of global warming and its adverse consequences.

Keywords: *Fossil Fuel, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS), COP26, Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Global Security and Climate Change.*

INTRODUCTION

Mankind has been engrossed with several challenges in its effort to make a living and overcome the vagaries posed by his environment. On several occasions, these challenges become so overwhelming that they constitute all life albatross.

Climate change refers to a long term warming of the planet thus causing an increase in global temperature, usually caused by human activities through the release of greenhouse gases such as;

- deforestation and land use changes through degradation.

- burning fossil fuels (such as coal, gas and oil and its by products); and
- impacts of agriculture and livestock production on the environment (Maathai, 2003).

Climate change received significant global attention between the late 1980s and 1990s, with several key events and milestones, contributing to its growing recognition as a pressing international challenge. Some key dates in global attention and a consequent response to climate change started when James Hansen testified as to its damaging effects before the US Senate, stating that climate change has begun and was becoming a global challenge. This was followed by the establishment of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) by the United Nations in 1990 whose report provided a comprehensive assessment of climate change science and impacts (Bond, 2012). The United Nations (UN) continue to drive the process of giving climate change the global attention it deserves. In 1972, the UN convened a conference on environment and development (Rio Earth Summit) leading to the establishment of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

In 1997, the UN convened the Kyoto Protocol produced an International Agreement to reduce greenhouse gas emissions was adopted, marking a significant step towards global cooperation on climate change (Basssey, 2012). The Paris Agreement of 2015 under the 15th Conference of Parties (COP 15), signed by almost 200 countries set a global goal to limit warming to well below 2°C and pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C.

The UN, under its International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), keeps promoting the adoption of renewable energy. In the same manner, several summits to address global climate change action plans have been in the works of the UN (Okereke, 2017). The Paris Agreement, climate change of 2015 has remained a central global issue with continued international negotiations, increased public awareness and the growing calls for global actions to contain its impact. Again, in 2015, the United Nations set up a Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of 17 goals and gave 2030 as the target date to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure peace and prosperity for all (Sofriate, 2018).

Finally, the United Nations packaged climate summit held in Glasgow 2021 under COP26 has one of its main agreements to achieve carbon-cutting targets by end of 2022, and dozens of member states have promised to phase out petrol and diesel-powered cars by 2025. But the two biggest pollutants, the US and China displayed much trepidation on compliance to most of the terms of the Glasgow Agreement (Maathai, 2003). It is remarkable that the social phenomenon of climate change, which associates all human efforts in the attempt to conquer his environment and become industrialized is becoming counterproductive. As mankind determines to advance in science and technology, the planet and our environment have always been at the receiving end (Monbiot, 2016).

OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

The overall objective of the paper is to interrogate different segments of climate change to deliver a world of a mitigated climate change. To achieve this course the followings are set as pathways:

- 1 To show how climate change contributes to global catastrophe.
- 2 To identify the main contributors to climate change.

3 To identify the issues leading to the schism between the united states and china on the climate change mitigation episode.

4 To show the challenges climate change poses to global security and sustainable development

5 To show global initiatives to address climate change; and

6 To recommended some solutions to climate change outcome.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In other to make above stated objectives convenient for proper interrogation, the following research questions were generated:

1 How does climate change lead to global catastrophe?

2 Who are the main contributors to climate change?

3 What led to the schism between the united states and china on the climate change mitigation episode?

4 What are the main challenges challenges climate change pose to global security and sustainable development?

5 What are the global initiatives to address climate change challenges?

6 How do we overcome the ravaging challenges of climate change?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change as an ongoing global challenge has attracted centrality of discourse by various environmental and development scholars around the globe. The works of some notable scholars to be reviewed are given thematic discussion in this session.

Kolbert (2020) dwelt on the far reaching impacts of climate change. To him, the impacts of climate change is overwhelming in various aspects of our life and the environment. Some of the significant impacts are summarized as follows;

A, Rising sea level leading to coastal flooding, sea erosion and salt water intrusion into fresh water. This negative impact has severely devastated our riverine communities in Nigeria. Most of our communities in Escravos River and other coastline grapple with this challenge year in year out.

B, The prevalence of extreme hot weather that increased frequency and intensity of heat wave, drought, storms and wildfire, are now common occurrences in various parts of the globe.

C, The Prevalence Of Scarcity Of Portable Water, caused by changes In Precipitation Pattern, Which Cause Droughts And Water Shortages.

D, Loss of biodiversity; caused by rising temperature, ocean acidification and habitat disruption and threatens the ecosystem.

Today, in most parts of Africa, the heat wave is excessively high, rising beyond 25°C in most cases. This is beyond a threshold of 1.5°C the Glasgow summit of 2021 recommended. The high heat level, occasioned by climate change, is inimical to convenient human life.

E, Food Insecurity is of a great challenge. Climate change impact on agriculture, marine life and livestock lead to crop failures, reduced yields and change of growing season of certain crops (kolbert,2020).

Dwelling more on adverse effects of climate change, wallace-wells (2019) identified the following as focal points;

A, Economic consequences wrought by climate change severely damage infrastructure, increased costs of health care emergency responses and loss of productivity.

B, Warmer temperature is injurious to human life. It increased the spread of diseases, heat stress and other health issues.

C, Climate change leads to social and cultural impacts. Problems of displacement, migration and loss of cultural heritage are occasioned by rising sea levels, extreme weather and devastating environments.

D, Increased ocean acidification that present in decreased ph levels harm marine life - especially coral reefs, shellfish and other calcium carbonate - based organisms.

E, Climate change leads to irreversible changes to critical ecosystems such as melting artic ice, coral bleaching or amazon rainforest die-offs.

Understanding these impacts is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate and adapt to climate change.

Advocating for a zero -sum approach to the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, Frankhauser, S. & Mbow, c. (eds) (2017) defined greenhouse as a structure made of transparent materials such as glass or plastic, in which plants are grown. The term greenhouse can also refer to the natural process by which certain gases in the atmosphere, e.g. carbon dioxide, methane, trap heat, keeping the planet warm. They then gave a rundown of greenhouse gases to include;

- Carbon Dioxide (CO₂)
- Methane (CH₄)
- Nitrous Oxide (N₂O)
- Fluorinated Gases (F-gases)
- Ozone (O₃)
- Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs).

Further, the continuous release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, primarily through human activities like burning fossil fuels, deforestation and agriculture have been recorded to have adverse effects on the environment and should be stopped (Fankhauser, S. & Mbow, C; 2017)

On the impact of Climate Change in global security, (Klein, 2014) refers the phenomenon to the measure and strategy implemented to ensure the safety and protection world's population, environment and interests from threats. These threats include:

1 TRADITIONAL SECURITY THREATS.

- Interstate Conflicts and Wars.
- Nuclear Proliferation
- Terrorism.

2 NON-TRADITIONAL SECURITY THREATS.

- Cyber Security Threats
- Climate Change and Environmental Degradation
- Pandemic and Global Health Crisis
- Migration and Refugee Crisis.

3 EMERGING SECURITY THREATS.

- Artificial Intelligence and Autonomous Weapons.
- Space Security and Satellite Technology
- Biotechnology and Biosecurity.

To Klein, these threats confronting mankind are being compounded by the ravaging climate change adversities (Klein, 2014).

In focusing on the global initiatives to mitigate climate change, (Alim, F. & Dube, O. P., 2018) recounted several global initiatives aimed at addressing the effects of climate change. They include;

1 The Treaty, founded on United Nations Framework Convention On Climate Change (UNFCCC) that aims to stabilize Greenhouse Gas concentrations in the atmosphere.

2 The Paris Agreement on climate change setting a global goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C; and

3 The Enactment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) initiative that sets 17 goals and timelines for achieving global development index. Goal 13, provides for climate control action, a strategy to overcome the negative effects of climate change.

urther on the challenges posed by climate change to global security, (Kolbert, 2020) identified the followings as the most prominent:

- Resource scarcity arising from competition for water, food and energy, which lead to conflicts.
- Mass migration and displacement due to rising sea levels, droughts, harsh weather and environmental pollution. Attendant social and political instability are also of common place.

- the challenge of global governance is also evident in climate change.

s a management of the Green Belt Movement advancing the course of environmental conversations. (Meathai, 2003). To Kolbert (2020), climate change requires international cooperation and collective action, which although can be challenging to achieve. To him, the challenge of social and political instability, particularly among vulnerable states, can be a major outcome of climate change. Most states devastated by harsh environmental conditions have shown signs of restiveness, and became potential source of political agitations and call for regime changes. This has been common occurrences in the Latin America states. Finally, Kolbert (2020) holds that addressing climate change is crucial to mitigating the effects of these global security challenges and ensure a more stable and secured future. (Meathai, 2003)

On strategies for mitigating climate change in Africa through living adaptations, Mbow, C., Fakir, S. and Zhu Z. (2019) called for the development of climate resilient infrastructure and urban planning that will ensure climate conditions compliance.

- They urged citizens to erect residential homes in areas that are not prone to harsh and unfriendly environmental conditions, such as floods and erosion.
- They urged citizens not only to strive towards ecosystem restoration, but to embark on sustainable agriculture and water management efforts to preserve both the environment and ensure water availability.
- they urged citizens to support researches aimed at mitigating negative impact of climate change.
- they urged citizens to use public transportation, cycling or walking to their destinations.
- they urged citizens to cultivate and eat plant-based diet and avoid food wastage.
- they urged citizens to support renewable energy projects and promote climate friendly policies.
- finally, to educate ourselves and others about climate change (Mbow, C., Fakir, S., and Zhu, Z., 2019).

On the schism and complex energy relationship between the United States and China, Wallace-Wells (2019) identified both states as not only global superpowers, but the two highest polluters of global atmosphere. On Greenhouse Gas emissions in the past and present, he identified China as the current world's biggest emitter of carbon dioxide, producing 12.7 billion metric tons of emissions annually. This figure dwarfs that of the United States (US) emissions currently he puts at 5.9 billion metric tons annually. He further holds that since 1850, China has emitted 284 billion tons of carbon dioxide. But the us, which industrialized far earlier, has emitted almost 509 billion, almost twice of china figure. Cumulatively therefore, the US emitted more carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. To him, there has been much schism between the major emitters in the climate change negotiations. Ordinarily, the country with higher historic emissions have a higher burden of contributing more to promote climate change mitigation, but this claim is being repudiated by the us. Instead, it's insistence has been on the one emitting more at the moment that ought to contribute more to the climate change mitigation efforts. (Wallace-Wells, 2019)

On the knotty issue of emission cuts, Mondiot (2016) opined that both the US and China have not demonstrated enough cooperation. Under President Obama's Administration, the US agreed

to cut emissions by at least 26% below 2005 level by the year 2025. While under the Biden administration, us has promised to stop new emissions by 2050. China under Xi Jinping on the other hand, promised in the Paris Agreement to first reach it's peak emissions by 2030 and pledged to increase the share of her non-fossil fuel energy like wind, solar and nuclear to 25%. China promised to become carbon neutral by 2060. On the fossil fuels - gas, oil and coal; Wallace-Wells recorded that the US consumes 20% of the world's oil, while china consumes about 14%. The us is also a top oil exporter. China, on the other hand imports most of it's oil.

The shift from coal to natural gas, a cheaper resource, has helped to lower greenhouse gas emissions. Natural gas now accounts for about 30% of energy use in the US. For China, most of her natural gas, accounting for 9% of it's energy mix, is imported. There has been a 40% decline in coal-fired power generation in the US over the last decade. China on the other hand, burns more coal than the rest of the world combined (US Energy Information Association, 2023). If both major polluters agree to speed up plans to cut greenhouse gas emissions, running same time lines, it would be consequential for the world's efforts to stay within safe limits of global warming.

Further contributing to the schism between the United States and China, Okereke (2023) identified china as the highest manufacturer of solar panels, wind turbines and electric vehicle batteries than any other nation. In 2022, china invested \$546 billion into clean energy; while the United States invested \$141 billion on the same project. (Okereke, 2023). To him, China's Renewable Energy capacity surpassed 1,000 Gigawatts in 2021, four times what it had decade earlier. Wind and Solar now exceeds 300 gigawatts each and predict the country will add up to 150 gigawatts soon. Hydropower, on the other hand, accounts for 16% of China's power generation and nuclear energy provides 5%. One in four cars sold in China in 2023 was an electric vehicle. For the US; wind, solar, hydroelectric power and other forms of renewable power accounts for 21% of the energy mix in 2021. In the us, one in every 17 new cars sold in 2023 was electric. The US under Biden administration has pledged to invest \$370 billion over 10 years into wind, solar, green hydrogen, nuclear energy and other non-fossil fuel power (us energy information association, 2024).

The EU Emission database for global atmospheric research report, 2023 identified the top five emitters of carbon dioxide as follows:

- 1 China emitted 11,535 billion metric tons annually.
- 2 US emitted 5, 107 billion metric tons annually.
- 3 EU emitted 3, 304 billion metric tons annually.
- 4 India emitted 2, 597 billion metric tons annually.
- 5 Russia emitted 1, 792 billion metric tons annually.

Source: EU Emission database for Global Atmospheric Research Report, 2023.

DATA ANALYSIS

From data generated from the Literature reviewed, the following are responses to the questions formulated from the research objectives:

HOW DOES CLIMATE CHANGE LEADS TO GLOBAL CATASTROPHE?

This study has revealed that increase of industrialization is a major reason high emissions of greenhouse gases which is injurious to man, animals and the environment. Climate change contributes to global warming of rising temperature, ocean acidification, disruption of the ecosystem, negative impact on agriculture- marine life and reduced crop yields.

Warmer temperature also leads to rising sea levels, sea erosion, wildfire, water scarcity, human health challenges, degradation of our environment leading to displacement and migration to safer grounds with attendant humanitarian crises associate climate change.

2 WHO ARE THE MAIN CONTRIBUTORS TO CLIMATE CHANGE?

This study has also revealed that the us and china are the two major contributors to global warming through the emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere.

This study shows china's greenhouse gas emissions amount to 12.7 billion metric tons annually, while the United States total emissions is put at 5.9 billion metric tons annually. In cumulative terms, from 1850 till date, the us is shown to surpassed china with 509 billion tons of carbon dioxide emissions, while china's cumulative emissions amount to 284 billion tons.

ther major greenhouse gas emitters are as follows; eu with 3.304 billion metric tons annually, India with 2.597 billion metric tons annually and Russia with 1.792 billion metric tons annually.

3 WHAT LED TO THE SCHISM BETWEEN THE UNITED STATES AND CHINA ON THE CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION EPISODE?

The complex rivalry and disagreement between the two superpowers and major gas emitters over reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and deliver a safer world has remained nagging. At several fora to address climate change mentioned in this paper ends in lack of consensus between the two powers on when to end the greenhouse gas emission. The tension arose over China's insistence that the US with higher cumulative volume of greenhouse gas emission should make more commitment of first in time to shift from gas emissions to usage of renewable energy of clean technology of solar, wind and nuclear than china. Both of them refused to accept a common date to to stop gas emissions. While the United States accepted 2050 as it's new date to end gas flaring, china projects 2060 as the year to become carbon neutral. This schism is not good enough for a world in haste to transit from gas flaring to renewable energy not only to protect our ecosystem but to greatly limit the huge negative impacts of climate change already mentioned in this paper.

4 WHAT ARE THE MAIN CHALLENGES CLIMATE CHANGE POSE TO GLOBAL SECURITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT?

his paper has shown the great nexus between climate change and global security. A secured world is one that it's citizens, marine life and environment are protected from various threats. This paper has identified climate change as a major threat confronting humanity. Greenhouse gase emissions have been identified as the major cause of food insecurity, water scarcity, mass migration and displacement, humanitarian crises, health challenges and global governance challenges.

Global sustainable development efforts have been shown in this paper to be heavily compromised by climate change. It is largely for this reason climate action was made a focal

point in the 17 sustainable development goals (sdgs), as goal no. 13. The un under the sdgs initiative projects 2030 as the target date to deliver a world free from gas emissions.

WHAT ARE THE GLOBAL INITIATIVES TO ADDRESS CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION?

This paper has been charitable to efforts of the UN and several agencies at every fora created to put the issue of climate change in the front burner of global attention. The creations of various frameworks, conventions, Kyoto protocol of 1997, Paris agreement of 2015, COP26 climate summit in Glasgow from October 31 to November 12, 2021 and the sustainable development goals SDGs initiative of 2015; are all geared to confront the challenge of climate change. It is expected that when the right commitment is shown by all stakeholders, the challenges humanity is facing under climate change if not totally eliminated, will be radically reduced.

6 HOW DO WE OVERCOME THE CHALLENGE OF CLIMATE CHANGE EPISODE RAVAGING THE WORLD?

This paper has shown that little hope remain for the world if efforts are not redoubled by all critical stakeholders to urgently migrate from greenhouse gas emissions to the full implementation of renewable energy projects. The devastating consequences of climate change must be mitigated through the rugged adoption of sourcing renewable energy from wind, solar and hydro electricity, away from greenhouse gas emissions.

CONCLUSION

This paper has presented climate change as the world's greatest enemy. The worst disasters the globe faces are derivable from the adverse effects of climate change. For this reason, the world, particularly the industrialized, need to close ranks, bury their differences and deliver the world from the imminent catastrophe that keeps knocking on our doors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

his paper provides the following as some of its key recommendations;

1 the world should as a matter of urgency, implement various climate change mitigation agreements and protocols to put an end to greenhouse gas emissions. It is a major destroyer of our ecosystem, the promoter of food crises, health hazard and wrought devastation to our environment.

2 We recommend the intensification of the adoption of renewable energy sources that will be environment and health friendly.

3 The UN should be more Thereby ensuring compliance to climate change protocols quicken the pace of renewable sources of energy in the area of compliance, assistance with funds to states that demonstrate the commitment to abolishing gas flares and in the sponsorship of more researches in that regard.

4 Climate Change should be made a compulsory course in every tertiary institution to make the students aware of the vagaries inherent in climate change and to be imbibed with the need to

develop technology to fast track the migration from gas flaring as a source of energy to renewable sources.

5 world citizens should be educated on how to be conscious of the hazard of climate change, and device ways to live right. Citizens should be advised not to live in erosion prone areas, be proactive and always in the consciousness of environmentally friendly standards. Finally, all citizens should refrain from carrying out actions that will compromise the environment.

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Agriculture, Food Security and Export Diversification In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the interconnectedness between agriculture, food security, and export diversification in Nigeria, highlighting the challenges and opportunities within these sectors. Nigeria's vast agricultural potential and diverse resources pose significant obstacles to sustainable development. The research examines existing policies, identifies key challenges, and proposes strategic interventions to enhance agricultural productivity, bolster food security, and diversify exports. Agriculture is a cornerstone of the economy, supporting millions of smallholder farmers. However, issues such as outdated practices, inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and climate change vulnerability need more robust implementation and support. Food security is another pressing concern, with a significant portion of the population facing hunger and malnutrition. The study advocates for enhanced climate resilience, improved social safety nets, and strengthened healthcare and nutrition education. Export diversification is crucial for reducing Nigeria's economic dependence on oil, and policy reforms are needed to simplify export procedures, enhance market access, and improve quality standards.

Keywords: Agriculture, Food Security, Export Diversification, Sustainable Development, Climate-Smart Agriculture, Climate Change.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, a country with vast agricultural potential, has historically relied heavily on its agricultural sector for economic growth and development. Before the discovery of oil, agriculture was the backbone of the Nigerian economy, contributing significantly to GDP, employment, and foreign exchange earnings. However, over the past few decades, the country's over-reliance on oil exports has led to the neglect of agriculture, creating challenges in food security and economic diversification (Okonkwo, Ogwuru, Ihugba, Echeta, & Manasseh, 2022).

In the pre-colonial era, Nigerian agriculture was characterized by diverse farming systems and a wide variety of crops and livestock, tailored to the country's varied ecological zones. Colonial policies introduced cash crops such as cocoa, palm oil, and groundnuts, which were exported to generate revenue for the colonial administration (Okonkwo, 2015). Post-independence, various agricultural policies and programs were introduced to boost productivity and self-sufficiency, but many were hampered by poor implementation and lack of continuity.

Today, Nigeria's agricultural sector remains a crucial part of the economy, employing about 70% of the labor force. The country produces a wide range of crops, including staples like cassava, yam, maize, and rice, as well as cash crops like cocoa, rubber, and palm oil. However, the sector faces numerous challenges, including outdated farming techniques, inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance and modern inputs, and frequent farmer-herder conflicts. These issues have resulted in low productivity and hindered the sector's ability to ensure food security and contribute significantly to export earnings (Owolabi, Ashaolu, & Twumasi-Ankrah, 2016).

The primary objective of this study, aims to analyze the relationship between Nigeria's agriculture, food security, and export diversification, identifying challenges and opportunities, analyzing existing policies, and identifying critical challenges that hinder agricultural productivity, food security, and export diversification.

AGRICULTURE IN NIGERIA

Agriculture in Nigeria is a vital part of the country's economy, contributing significantly to GDP and employment. The sector includes crop production, livestock farming, fisheries, and forestry. Nigeria has a rich agricultural history, with traditional farming methods and tools being employed throughout its history. The country has introduced cash crops like cocoa, palm oil, and groundnuts for export, and developed plantation agriculture and research institutes to support crop production. Post-Independence, policies focused on increasing agricultural production through large-scale farming and state-controlled enterprises (Amuda, 2023).

Major agricultural products include cassava, yam, maize, rice, cocoa, palm oil, rubber, livestock, and aquaculture. Nigeria has a rich potential in fisheries and aquaculture, with efforts being made to boost fish production to meet local demand and reduce imports. However, the agricultural sector faces challenges such as infrastructure deficiencies, limited access to finance, outdated farming techniques, climate change, conflicts and insecurity, and policy and implementation gaps (Chiaka Zhen, Hu, Xiao, Muhirwa, & Lang, 2022).

Government initiatives and programs include The Green Alternative, Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP), and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). Technological advancements include precision agriculture, biotechnology, post-harvest technologies, and digital agriculture. By overcoming existing challenges, Nigeria can enhance its agricultural productivity, ensure food security, and achieve export diversification (Sasu, 2023). The ongoing efforts to modernize agriculture, coupled with increasing private sector participation and international support, will be crucial in realizing the full potential of Nigeria's agricultural sector.

Overview of Nigeria's agricultural sector

Nigeria's agricultural sector is a vital part of the country's economy, with significant historical and current aspects. It has been the main economic activity since pre-colonial and colonial times, with cash crops like cocoa, palm oil, and groundnuts being introduced during colonial times. Post-independence, various policies and programs have been implemented to increase agricultural productivity, such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) and the Green Revolution. Major agricultural products include staple crops like cassava, which is the world's largest

producer, and livestock and poultry, which are rich in marine and freshwater resources (Yusuf & Francis, 2019).

Challenges facing the agricultural sector include infrastructure deficiencies, limited access to finance, outdated farming techniques, climate change, conflicts and insecurity, and policy and implementation gaps (Azih, 2008). Government initiatives include The Green Alternative, Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP), and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), which aim to improve productivity, market access, and value addition in agriculture. Technological advancements include precision agriculture, biotechnology, post-harvest technologies, and digital agriculture (Ogen, 2007).

Nigeria's agricultural sector holds significant potential for driving economic growth, ensuring food security, and achieving export diversification. Strategic investments, robust policies, and the adoption of modern technologies are critical to overcoming existing challenges. Increased private sector participation and international support will also play a key role in transforming the sector. By addressing infrastructural deficits, improving access to finance, and fostering innovative practices, Nigeria can unlock the full potential of its agricultural sector, ensuring a prosperous and sustainable future.

Challenges faced by Nigerian farmers

Nigerian farmers face numerous challenges that hinder their productivity, profitability, and contribution to the nation's food security and economic development. These challenges span various aspects, including infrastructure, finance, technology, climate, security, and policy. Infrastructure deficiencies include poor transportation networks, inadequate storage facilities, and insufficient processing facilities (Eme, Onyishi, & Uche, 2014). Limited access to finance is another issue, with smallholder farmers often struggling to secure loans due to lack of collateral and high interest rates. Inadequate insurance coverage also limits farmers' ability to invest in modern farming techniques and inputs (Albert, Aadaeze, & Obike, 2022).

Traditional farming methods are often used, leading to low yields and productivity. Limited extension services provide training and support to farmers, but they are often underfunded and understaffed. Climate change and environmental issues, such as unpredictable weather patterns and land degradation, also disrupt farming activities. Security challenges include farmer-herder conflicts, insurgency, and banditry (Okonkwo, 2018).

Policy and implementation gaps include inconsistent policies, weak implementation, market volatility, and a monopoly of middlemen. Farmers are exposed to price fluctuations due to inconsistent demand and supply dynamics, and their limited bargaining power leads to reduced income and profit margins. Health and education issues, such as poor health services in rural areas, malnutrition, and diseases, also affect farmers' productivity and ability to work (Olufemi, 2024).

To address these challenges, Nigeria can invest in improving infrastructure, enhance access to finance, promote modern farming techniques, mitigate climate impact, ensure security, formulate consistent and effective policies, and establish transparent and fair market systems (Okojie, 2022). By addressing these multifaceted challenges, Nigeria can enhance its agricultural productivity, ensure food security, and improve the livelihoods of millions of farmers.

FOOD SECURITY IN NIGERIA

Food security in Nigeria is a critical issue affecting millions of people across the country. It involves ensuring that all people have access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food at all times. The current state of food security in Nigeria is classified as having a serious hunger problem, with a significant portion of the population suffering from food insecurity (Garba, 2023).

Food security is defined by four key components: availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability. Nigeria faces significant food security challenges, with high levels of hunger and malnutrition. Regional variations exist, with the northern regions being particularly vulnerable due to conflict and climatic challenges. The southern regions, while relatively better off, still experience pockets of food insecurity due to economic disparities and infrastructure deficits (Ogunniyi, Omotoso, Salman, Omotayo, Olagunju, & Aremu, 2021).

Factors affecting food security include climate change and environmental factors, such as irregular rainfall, droughts, and flooding, land degradation, conflict and insecurity, and insurgency and banditry. Economic factors include poverty, inflation, unemployment, agricultural productivity, poor healthcare, and lack of education. Government and policy interventions include national policies like The Green Alternative, Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP), programs and initiatives like Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP), Home-Grown School Feeding Program, and National Social Investment Program (NSIP). Technological and innovative approaches include Climate-Smart Agriculture and Digital Agriculture, which enhance resilience to climate change and provide farmers with market information, extension services, and financial inclusion (Aworh, 2015).

International organizations like the World Food Programme (WFP) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) offer technical assistance, policy advice, and capacity building. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) work on the ground to provide food aid, support agricultural development, and improve nutrition and health services (Strang et al., 2020).

Government initiatives to improve food security

The Nigerian government has implemented several initiatives to improve food security, focusing on enhancing agricultural productivity, improving access to food, and ensuring nutritional adequacy for its population. Key initiatives include the Green Alternative (Agriculture Promotion Policy), National Agricultural Technology and Innovation Plan (NATIP), Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP), Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), Home-Grown School Feeding Program (HGSP), National Social Investment Program (NSIP), National Food Security Program (NFSP), Green Imperative, Livelihood Improvement Family Enterprise (LIFE) Program, and National Agricultural Resilience Framework (NARF) (Davies, 2009).

The Green Alternative (APP) aims to promote sustainable agricultural development and enhance food security through improved productivity, market access, and value addition. It includes support for smallholder farmers, infrastructure development, value addition, and private sector engagement. The ABP provides financial support to smallholder farmers, while the ATA focuses on improving productivity, market access, and value addition (Gavrilova, 2020).

The Home-Grown School Feeding Program (HGSP) improves child nutrition and school attendance by providing free meals sourced from local farmers. The NSIP supports vulnerable populations through social safety nets, cash transfers, school feeding programs, and job creation initiatives. The NFSP ensures a stable and sustainable food supply by boosting domestic food production and reducing dependency on imports. The Green Imperative focuses on modernizing Nigeria's agricultural sector through bilateral cooperation with Brazil, focusing on mechanization and technology transfer (Strang, Che, & Vajjhala, 2020).

Lastly, the LIFE Program aims to improve rural livelihoods by promoting agribusiness and creating income-generating opportunities. The NARF aims to enhance the resilience of Nigeria's agricultural sector to climate change and other shocks. By continuing to implement and refine these initiatives, Nigeria aims to achieve a more secure and sustainable food system that meets the needs of its growing population (Davies, 2009).

EXPORT DIVERSIFICATION IN NIGERIA

Export diversification is crucial for Nigeria's economic stability and growth, as it helps stabilize revenue streams, reduce risks, create jobs, and foster sustainable development. Key sectors for diversification include agriculture, manufacturing, and services, which can help reduce vulnerability to oil price fluctuations, create jobs, and increase foreign exchange earnings (Okonkwo, Kalu, & Nwosu, 2018). The country is one of the world's largest producers of cocoa, with significant potential for export growth. The country also has a high demand for cashew nuts, sesame seeds, palm oil, textiles and garments, automobile assembly, pharmaceuticals, solid minerals, information and communication technology (ICT), entertainment, and tourism (Albert et al., 2022).

However, Nigeria faces challenges in infrastructure deficiencies, regulatory and policy issues, access to finance, skill gaps and technology, market access, and quality. Strategies for export diversification include infrastructure development, policy and regulatory reforms, access to finance, capacity building and skill development, market access and trade promotion, improving quality and standards, technology adoption and innovation, and public-private partnerships (PPPs) (Okonkwo et al., 2018). Government initiatives and programs include the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP), the Nigerian Industrial Revolution Plan (NIRP), the Zero Oil Plan, Export Expansion Grant (EEG), and the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC). These plans focus on diversifying the economy through agriculture, manufacturing, and services, aiming to increase the contribution of manufacturing to GDP and enhance industrial exports (Davies, 2009).

The Zero Oil Plan is an ambitious strategy to increase non-oil exports and reduce dependency on oil revenue. The Export Expansion Grant (EEG) provides incentives to exporters to boost non-oil exports, while the EEG provides incentives to boost non-oil exports. The Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) supports exporters through training, market information, and trade facilitation services (Umeji, 2019). Export diversification is essential for Nigeria's economic resilience and growth. By leveraging its diverse resources and implementing strategic initiatives, Nigeria can reduce its reliance on oil exports, enhance its global trade presence, and ensure sustainable development. The government, in collaboration with the private sector and international partners, must continue to address existing challenges and support sectors with high export potential to achieve a diversified and robust export economy (Dike & Njoku, 2019).

Agriculture, Food Security, and Export Diversification Nexus in Nigeria

The interrelation of agriculture, food security, and export diversification in Nigeria is a complicated and diverse matter. Agriculture is essential for food security as it ensures food availability, generates cash for food purchases, and produces nutritionally dense crops (Ayinde et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the industry encounters other obstacles, such as insufficient infrastructure, restricted access to contemporary agricultural methods, and the effects of climate change (Naheed, & Rukhsana, 2024).

Food security in Nigeria is determined by agricultural productivity, which directly impacts food supply and affordability. High agricultural productivity can lead to decreased food prices, making food more accessible to the poor (Ayinde et al., 2020). Conversely, low production can worsen food insecurity, especially in rural areas where agriculture is the major livelihood (Naheed, & Rukhsana, 2024).

Export diversification is another key issue. By diversifying exports, Nigeria can lessen its dependent on a single product, such as oil, and stabilize its economy (Aluko, 2020). Agricultural exports can play an important part in this diversification, creating new revenue

streams and improving economic stability³. However, doing this entails overcoming constraints such as insufficient infrastructure, limited market access, and trade policies that may not favor agricultural exports (Aluko, 2020).

Boosting agricultural production, guaranteeing food security, and diversifying exports are interrelated goals that require coordinated policies and strategic actions. Addressing the difficulties in these areas can contribute to sustainable development and economic resilience in Nigeria.

Case studies and success

Case studies and success stories provide practical insights into strategic interventions in agriculture, food security, and export diversification. These examples are based on Nigeria and other relevant contexts, highlighting effective practices, key achievements, and lessons learned. In Kebbi State, Nigeria, the state implemented the Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP) to boost rice production and achieve self-sufficiency in rice. This initiative provided smallholder farmers with access to finance, high-quality seeds, fertilizers, and modern farming techniques, leading to increased production and improved livelihoods for thousands of smallholder farmers. The state moved closer to achieving self-sufficiency in rice, reducing dependency on imports (Kara, 2019).

Olam Nigeria, a leading agribusiness company, established an integrated rice farm and mill in Nasarawa State to contribute to Nigeria's rice self-sufficiency goals. The integrated farm produced significantly higher yields compared to traditional farms, created thousands of jobs for local communities, and invested in local infrastructure, including schools and healthcare facilities (Guardian, 2023).

The Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) has been instrumental in promoting non-oil exports and supporting export diversification efforts. The council launched various programs to support exporters, including the Zero Oil Plan, which focuses on developing non-oil sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services. Key achievements include export growth, market access, capacity building, strategic planning, support services, and market promotion (NEPC, 2023).

Lagos State launched the Agricultural Youth Empowerment Scheme (AGRIC-YES) to attract young people to agriculture and reduce youth unemployment. The program provided training in modern agricultural practices, access to land, inputs, and financial support, aiming to make agriculture appealing and profitable for young Nigerians (The Nation, 2020).

Key achievements include youth participation, increased production, entrepreneurial skills, comprehensive support, and sustainability. Innovative programs that make agriculture attractive to youth can address unemployment and boost agricultural productivity. Continuous support and mentorship help young farmers sustain and grow their enterprises.

These case studies and success stories demonstrate the potential for significant progress in agriculture, food security, and export diversification through well-designed and effectively implemented interventions (Umeji, 2019). Key lessons include the importance of access to finance, public-private partnerships, technology adoption/adaptation, community investment, strategic planning, and youth engagement. By learning from these examples, Nigeria can further enhance its efforts to achieve sustainable development and economic resilience.

CONCLUSION

The agricultural sector in Nigeria is crucial for the nation's economic stability and development, but it faces challenges such as low productivity, inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and climate change impacts. Government initiatives like the Green Alternative and Anchor Borrowers' Program have shown positive effects but require more consistent implementation and support. Food security in Nigeria is threatened by factors like climate

variability, conflict, economic instability, and inadequate healthcare and education. High levels of food insecurity and malnutrition, particularly in vulnerable regions, highlight the urgency of addressing these issues. Export diversification is crucial for economic stability, reducing vulnerability to oil price fluctuations, and promoting sustainable growth. Agriculture, manufacturing, and services sectors have significant potential for diversification, but key barriers include infrastructure deficiencies, regulatory hurdles, and limited market access. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) can drive investment and innovation in agriculture and export sectors, leveraging private sector expertise and resources to enhance productivity and competitiveness. Coordinated and sustained effort from all stakeholders is needed to realize Nigeria's vision of a prosperous and food-secure nation.

Policy Recommendations

Policy recommendations to tackle agriculture, food security, and export diversification in Nigeria include modern farming techniques, improved infrastructure, access to finance, and strengthening agricultural extension services. Climate-Smart agriculture is also emphasized, promoting resilience to climate change. Social safety nets are strengthened, healthcare and nutrition education improved, and conflict resolution strategies implemented. These measures aim for sustainable development and economic stability.

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Appraisal Of State Response To Terrorism And Insurgency In Nigeria: Boko-Haram In North-East Experience.

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Abstract

The security of lives and properties remains a fundamental and constitutional responsibility of the state. This has however taken a different dimension in recent years, following the upsurge of terrorism and insurgency in the Northeast of Nigeria and beyond. The attacks on Nigerians particularly, the people in the Northeast by the Islamist Sect called Boko Haram, has continued to wreck havocs on the security and peaceful coexistence of the various tribes and culture that constitute the Nigeria body polity. To this end, this paper examined state response to terrorism and insurgency in the North-east of Nigeria and how it has affected development in the region. The study adopted the secondary method of data collection, derived from Journals, Textbooks, Mimeographs, Newspapers, and Publications by Governmental and Non-Governmental institutions. Findings revealed the impact of state response to the activities of Bokoharam insurgency and terrorism in Nigeria. Its socio-economic and political effect such as, the closure of businesses and the non-conduct of elections in some parts of the areas affected amongst others. furthermore, the study recommends some ways to mitigated, through proper collaboration with the relevant security apparatuses. It also canvassed the need for government to ensure justice and equity in the handling of state affairs at all times, to avoid feelings of deprivation and inequality in the system. Finally, the study highlighted the over haul of some of the intelligence and information-sharing and communication strategies as a veritable tool for fighting the upsurge of Boko-Haram Sects in Nigeria.

Keywords: Terrorism, Insurgency, State, Boko-haram, Insecurity

Introduction:

A fundamental responsibility of the state as embedded in section 14, sub section 2, part B, of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) is the security of the life and property

of its citizens. Other responsibilities include the protection of its territoriality; sovereignty; guaranteeing its socio-economic and political stability etc. This threat has further been propelled by the emergence and rise of “Violent Non-State Actors” (VNSAs) according to Adesoji, (2014), argues that the process of globalization has further given advantage to the terrorists to carry out their nefarious and dangerous attacks on citizens, institutions and critical infrastructure of the state. Terrorism and its negative consequences date back to the pre-historic time otherwise referred to the period antiquity. Adetula (2011), argues that prevalence and escalation have been accentuated in the twenty-first century especially since the September 11, 2001 bombing of the World Trade Centre (W TC) in the United States by the Al-Qaeda terrorist network led by Osama Bin laden. That attack has been followed by many similar attacks in Africa, Asia, Europe, and other parts of the world. The ugly incidence of Boko haram in the submission of Adesoji, (2014), came as a result of factors such as religiously motivated crisis, proliferation of weapons of war, social and political injustice. corruption, unemployment, poverty, weak institutional structure, economic marginalization, lack of political will etc.

However, terrorism-related violence dates back to the late 1990s. On August 7, 1998, two massive bombs simultaneously exploded outside the United States embassies in Dares Salaam in Tanzania and Nairobi in Kenya, killing 224 people and injuring 5,000 others. Responsibility was quickly traced to Al-Qaeda. Four years afterwards, Al-Qaeda operatives struck again, killing 15 people in an Israeli-owned hotel near Mombasa in Kenya, and simultaneously fired missiles at an Israeli passenger jet taking off from Mombasa airport (Gabriel, 2018). However, since September 11, 2001, the Continent has experienced significant increase in planned and actual attacks by terrorist networks (Adelusi, 2011). Weak domestic security, governance failure, post-election violence, corruption, religious intolerance, porous borders, proliferation of weapons from destabilized countries in the aftermath of the Arab Spring and globalization have provided terrorist groups chapter four the leeway to carryout audacious attacks in Africa including Nigeria (Onuoha, 2012).. Blair (2015), identified Angola, Burundi, Central African Republic; Cote d’Ivoire, Ethiopia and Uganda as being at risk of increased terrorism due to the presence of the following four factors – extrajudicial killing, lack of women’s political rights, lack of intergroup cohesion and political instability. As Alexander, (2018) would say, Boko Haram represents an ugly paradox: Its ideas have limited appeal which is significantly concerned about power, hence government purposeful and proactive response becomes a key factor to the survival of the Nigerian state.

There is no gainsaying the fact that several studies on terrorism and insurgency in relations to Boko Haram as in the case Sanda, (2014), Osita, (2019), Thomas, (2016) and other notable scholars. Interestingly, in all of the studies and literatures consulted, none of them looked deeply from perspective of state responses to terrorism and insurgency in the Northeast, Nigeria, hence this work is out to fill some gap in knowledge and equally add to existing body of knowledge. Some other puzzles the work is set to ascertain the degree of damage done by the sects their network and strategies which has taken a global dimension and the overall challenge it poses to the nation and by extension, the world. This study amongst others examined state responses to terrorism and insurgency in the northeast of Nigeria. This is considered significant because its outcome would be of immense benefit and assistance to the Nigerian state, security apparatuses, and international community in the formulation of relevant anti-terrorism legislations and policies in their efforts to contend with the challenges of terrorism.

Terrorism

The concept of terrorism is not a new phenomenon in human history, especially in Nigeria. The term terrorism from the etymological concept had its origin from the French word 'terrorism' which in turn was derived from the Latin word, 'terreo' which means to frighten or give a threat. It is a concept that is complex, multifaceted and emotive. It is complex because it combines so many different aspects of human experiences, including politics, psychology, philosophy, military strategy, religion and history. Obi (2011); Ekanem; Dada and Ejue (2012) define terrorism as the use of unlawful, illegal and violent means by small group of people to achieve their selfish aim. Terrorism is emotive because experiences of terrorist acts arouse tremendous feelings and because those who see terrorists as justified often have strong feelings concerning the rightness of the use of violence in resolving differences among Mankind. In many cases terrorists internationally choose to attack innocent targets, to make their political or religious demands from the government or people with which they are in conflict, violating domestic and international laws. Ogirai, (2015) described terrorism as the use of threat or anxiety-induced extra normal violence for political purpose by any individual or group whether acting for or in a position to establish governmental authority where such action is intended to influence the attitudes and behaviour of a largest group wider than the immediate victims and through the nationality or foreign ties and its perpetrators. In the opinion of (Ekanem 2012, Juergensmeyer 2003), terrorism is a tool used to achieve a specific outcome by using force or violence on one segment of society with the primary goal of causing fear in the larger society to make change in that society. Terrorism is a form of violent conflict which is a form of unconventional warfare.

Terrorism includes a range of social and political problems whose behavioural scope is boundless and includes behaviour that appears to be abnormal. Friedlander, (2017) in his opinion argued that terrorism is often characterized by the use of violence against civilians, with the expressed desire of causing terror or panic in the population. At the individual level, some experts have distinguished rational, psychological, and cultural origins of terrorism (Simonsen & Jeremy 2000). Scholars such as Barkan and Snowkan (1986), also looked at the inherent nature and violence in humans contributes to the fast spreading rate of terrorism and insurgency as an inherent phenomenon. Terrorism in Nigeria in whichever dimension is often stimulated by economic considerations. For instance, the Niger Delta agitations were greatly underpinned by the bid of what (Ake, 1981) referred to as the primary material condition Obi (2011); Ekanem; Dada and Ejue (2012) define terrorism as the use of unlawful, illegal and violent means by small group of people to achieve their selfish aim. Terrorism is emotive because experiences of terrorist acts arouse tremendous feelings and because those who see terrorists as justified often have strong feelings concerning the rightness of the use of violence in resolving differences among Mankind.

Insurgency

Insurgency is characterized by some common strings: political, psychological, coercive, dynamic and deliberate. Its ideologies and activities is caused by human injustice, perceived oppression or man's inhumanity to man, marginalization, exploitation, greed, deprivation, poverty, corruption, oppression, and repression. The United States Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) as contained in Madunagu, (2007) described the act of insurgency as the unlawful use of violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population or any segment thereof, in furtherance of social objective or frivolous reasons. The phenomenon of insurgency has been widely examined in the extant literature, yet

there is no universally accepted definition. This act of insurgency also conveys terrorism impressions which are often viewed from different perspectives. Ogirai, (2015) described Insurgency as the use of threat or anxiety-induced extra normal violence for political purpose by any individual or group whether acting for or in a position to establish governmental authority where such action is intended to influence the attitudes and behaviour of a largest group wider than the immediate victims and through the nationality or foreign ties and its perpetrators. In the opinion of Ekanem (2012), terrorism is an “acts by non-state actors involving the threatened or actual use of illegal force or violence to attain a political, economic, religious, or social goal through fear, coercion, or intimidation as witnessed in Nigeria during the reprobate regime of General Sani Abacha between 1995 – 1998 when bombs were used as a terror weapon against Nigerians. In a world perceived as peaceful, an act of political violence may be considered as domestic terrorism, while the same act of violence can be considered justified by others who perceive the world to be at war. The United States Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) as contained in Madunagu, (2007) described terrorism as the unlawful use of force or violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population or any segment thereof, in furtherance of political or social objective Friedlander, (2017) in his contributions argued that the victims or objects of a terrorist attack have little intrinsic value to the terrorist but represent a larger human audience whose reaction the terrorists seek.

Theoretical Framework of Analysis

Morrison (1971) argued that a lot of theories exist for providing explanation to acts of terrorism and insurgency. The paper adopted the structural theory of revolutionary otherwise known as transformational theory which was development by an economists and sociologists to explain the process of economic development and society. Rostow, Chinney and Hirschman were the main advocates and the relative deprivation theory by both Garry Runciman and Ted Gurr in providing explanations to state response to terrorism and insurgency in the North East Nigeria. The theory tends to explain the problem associated in counter-insurgency efforts and the war against terrorism and how states can adapt faster and take over the enemy's own shifting tactics and innovations. Applying structural theory in the context of terrorism and insurgency, Barkan and Snowden (1986) observed that, Structural theories of revolution emphasize that weaknesses in state structures encourage the potential for revolution and a fragile system which by extension may lead to insecurity and terrorism. (Deleuze, 2002). This theory is relevant to this discourse because it's offers important suggestions for the fight against terrorism and insurgency to insure internal and international security.

The theory of relative deprivation became relevant to the study because, rather than examine the causes of a given situation alone, relative deprivation theory is interested in the genesis of the problem in either individual or social structures. Relative deprivation seeks to explain the process and emotion of crime, the fluidity of deviant activity and as such, connects to the contemporary issues. Deprivation should therefore be understood from the offenders' inner feelings because not all poor people criminals or may have the huge to commit crime. The central idea of relative deprivation theory suggests that individuals or groups feel deprived when their current circumstances are negatively compared to the situation of others. In sociology, relative deprivation theory is a view of social change and movements according to which people take action for social change in order to acquire something (for example, opportunities, status and wealth) that others possess and which they believe they should have too.

Operational Differences Between Insurgency and Terrorism

The distinction between terrorism and insurgency according Pape, (2005), is not merely theoretical as the appropriate responses to the two phenomena are very different. Before addressing preferred strategies to counter each, one should establish how they are alike and how they differ. Unfortunately, existing definitions do more to cloud than clarify the issues. Neither academic nor government experts agreed on a suitable definition for terrorism. Operationally, there is no clear cut difference between the goals of terrorist and insurgent groups and insurgencies, but certain characteristics might reflect distinctions. Despite, these allusions, certain differences still exist according to (Silke, 2011).

Dichotomy between Insurgency and Terrorism

S/N	TERRORISM	INSURGENCY
1	Terrorism is indiscriminate	Insurgency on the other hand is based on the selective use of violence against a people who do not comply politically with the wishes of the rebels or the government
2.	Terrorism may pursue political or even revolutionary goals but their violence replaces rather than c complements a political program	Insurgency combines violence with political programs in pursuit of revolutionary purposes in a way that terrorism cannot duplicate
3	Terrorist units are usually smaller and comprised of isolated teams not organized into formal military chain of command	Insurgency are usually in large number with identifiable purposes and reasons of operations
4	Terrorism is considered to be a method of pursuing political goal.	Insurgency is a political movement aimed at realizing a specific political goa
5	Terrorism relies on public impact, and is therefore conscious of the advantage of avoiding the negative connotations of the term "terrorists" in identifying themselves A terror group does not require and rarely has the active support or even the sympathy of a large fraction of the population.	Insurgents will frequently describe themselves as "insurgents" or "guerillas", terrorists will not refer to themselves as "terrorists" but describe it using military or political terminology ("freedom fighters", "soldiers", "activists"). The ultimate goal of an insurgency is to challenge the existing government for control of all or a portion of its territory, or force political concessions in sharing political power.
6	Terrorism does not attempt to challenge government forces directly, but acts to change perceptions as to the effectiveness or legitimacy of the government itself.	Insurgency need not require the targeting of non-combatants, although many insurgencies expand the accepted legal definition of combatants to include police and security personnel in addition to the military
7	Terrorists are by definition conducting crimes under both civil and military legal codes. Terrorists routinely claim that were they to adhere to any "law of war" or accept any constraints on the scope of their violence, it would place	Ultimately, the difference between insurgency and terrorism comes down to the intent of the actor. Insurgency movements and guerilla forces can adhere to international norms regarding the law of war in achieving their goals

	them at a disadvantage vis-vis the establishment	
8	One common characteristic of all insurgencies is their significant material inferiority to the counterinsurgent, at least in the early stages of the conflict.	One common characteristic of all terrorism is their significant material superior to the counterinsurgent.
9	External support, recognition or approval from other countries or political entities can be useful to insurgents, but is not required	Insurgencies require the active or tacit support of some portion of the population involved

Compiled by the researcher

Terrorists and Insurgents' Tactics and Weapons of Carrying out Attacks of the People

According to Walter, (1976), warfare comprises not just the encounter of individual soldiers, but (more importantly), a pattern of tactics and strategy in relationship to the opposing forces taken as a whole. Some of the tactics deployed by terrorists and insurgents as identified by Marighella (2002), are:

- i. **Propaganda:** Propaganda has proved to be a seminal weapon in the battle for hearts and minds. Successful insurgents use communication media to construct and disseminate information in a way that manages the relevant audiences' opinion and behaviour in their favour (Marighella, 2002). According to Mao Tse-Tung (1963), Propaganda is an instrument that tends to favour the insurgent over the ruling power. In contrast, the insurgent group free from such responsibility enjoys greater creative freedom when formulating its revolutionary propagandistic messages.
- ii. **Guerrilla Tactics:** This is a major approach based on intelligence, ambush, deception, sabotage and espionage, undermining an authority through long, low-intensity confrontation. It can be quite successful against an unpopular foreign or local regime as demonstrated by the Cuban revolution, Afghanistan War and Vietnam War. According to Times (2013), it is a major tactics used by the insurgent groups in actualizing their nefarious activities in society.
- iii. **Agitation:** Often grouped together with propaganda as agitprop, agitation is the use of agitators to stir up discontent both real and imagined with the regime and propose a course of action to right these perceived wrongs. The traditional targets of agitators have been the shop floor, students' unions and the junior officers' mess halls of the military. These tactics are useful
- iv. **Assassinations:** Insurgent groups have often employed assassination as a tool to further their course. Assassinations provide several functions for such groups, namely the removal of specific enemies and as propaganda tools to focus the attention of media and politics on their course. These tactics was used during the Irish Republican Army guerrilla of 1919-1921 which killed many police intelligence officers during the Irish war of independence.

- v. **Rebellion:** Insurgencies are movements to overthrow governments. The United States was founded by an insurgency, when the colonies fought England for independence. In the Star Wars movies, the rebel forces stage an insurgency. Around the world, many insurgencies exist, using violent and other means.
- vi. **Deception:** Insurgency employs a deception primarily for purposes of infiltration prior to an attack. This technique allows Boko Haram fighters to position themselves inside a village prior to an attack. On 14 February 2014, Boko Haram fighters exploited the hope that the Nigerian military would answer repeated calls to send soldiers to protect the village of Izghe in Borno State. 61 Boko Haram used a similar technique when they kidnapped the Chibok girls, as noted previously (Marighella, 2002).

Insecurity Situation and Boko-Haram's ad its Effects in Nigeria

Boko Haram insurgency could thus link to perceived discrepancy between the preferred way of life (to maintain the sanctity of orthodox Islam) and the actual state of their existence (secular state) that influence the dissonance. Prominently, it should be noted that the voice of few elements that initially reacted to the perceived dissonance is what the issue at stake requires in order to gain popular support and to a large extent, the personal dissonance grows to become group level grievances and discontentment. As a consequence, it transcends from a micro to macro level spectacle. Fundamentally, the crucial target of Boko Haram is to destabilize Nigeria, beginning with the northeast therefore make it ungovernable as this could lead to a situation of break-up of the country or imposition of Islamic ways of life.

The relevance of cognitive dissonance theory to this study is that, it reflects meaningful philosophy behind the existentiality of Boko Haram sect and to a large extent explains government inability to tame the challenges posed by the sec. Since then, the group has demonstrated remarkable adaptability, employing various tactics and methods to further its agenda. Notably, the movement has expanded into neighboring countries Cameroon, Chad, and Niger (see map below) and has also demonstrated its capacity to seize and hold towns and villages, particularly during the height of its insurgency between 2014 and 2015.

The situation has caused a lot of setback in various aspects of the nation's economy. On the education sub-sector for example, data gathered through secondary sources such as, textbooks, journals, media, unpublished work, government reports and Non-government reports showed the magnitude of impact/damage done to the sub-sector as a result of the activities of the terrorist and insult groups. The sector suffered a huge setback as government was forced to close down Schools and Colleges. This according to Chris, (2012) led the Nigeria government to effectively collaborate with the United State government and the international community in the training of over 30.000 troops since it started in 2015 to help secure schools in the region.

- i. **Effect on education:** The paper revealed the various ways Boko Haram insurgency and terrorism has affected Education in the Northeast region in Nigeria. One major sector that has suffered severe setback as a result of Boko Haram activities in the North East of Nigeria is the education sub-sector. During the period under study, Schools, Colleges, teachers and students formed the main targets and they all suffered immense damages. Schools were totally closed down by government for fear of possible attacks like in the case of the Chibok girls were over 230 school children were abducted with no trace of location. This according to Hassan, (2014) caused a lot of damaged to the already educational backward region in terms of education, hence adequate attention

according to Omorogbe, (2019) suggested the need for government to be proactive and not reactive.

- ii. **Effect on social activities:** As earlier indicated in this study coupled with the data in the table above, Boko Haram has had a serious impact on socio-economic activities not only in the affected areas but the entire country. Findings further showed that beyond religious, political and Psychological reasons other sub-sectors such as the social sector have equally been negatively affected. The phenomenon of internally displaced Persons has become a social problem and dangerous to economic development. The population of IDPs in the North is alarming because many of them are family men and women who ordinarily are supposed to fend for their family.
- iii. **Its Effect on political activities:** One other major areas that was drastically affected by Boko Haram activities is political activities. As a result of the intense insurgent activities, the study revealed that most persons who ought to participate in elections were disenfranchised. Investigation revealed that in Borno state for example, INEC Resident Electoral Commissioner, Muhammed Ibrahim provided the voting details at an interactive session organized by the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) for election officials, civil society organizations, political parties and journalists. It was gathered that out of the Twenty-Seven local government areas in the North East of Nigeria, only eight of them could hold elections due to Boko Haram activities in 2009.
- iv. **Psychological Effect:** The psychological implication of Boko Haram activities cannot be over emphasized. A lot of lives and properties have been claimed by the sect with huge injuries inflicted on thousands of people. Studies emanating from the University of Port Harcourt have shown that aside the physical disability which those who survived violent crimes and warfare sustained, psychiatric disorder is rife and manifest. The number of houses that have been destroyed by the sect since inception as revealed in the study in alarming.
- v. **Economic Effect:** One significant factor that has stimulated the drive towards violent extremism, recruitment and support for Boko Haram as revealed above is economic deprivation. Abject poverty and economic dislocation of livestock have drastically reduced the option of many young Nigerians in the northern region. As highlighted above, deducing from the structural violence paradigms, individual and group grievances, such as poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, discrimination, and economic marginalization, was identified as been used as a mobilizing by sinister groups as observed in the study to find support and recruits for terrorists' violence.

Impediments to Effective Response to Terrorism and Insurgency in the Northeast of Nigeria

The impediment to state and government in the fight against Boko Haram according to findings gathered from the various sources and as witnessed in some of the literatures captured above. The investigation identified six impediments confronting an effective fight against Boko Haram and insurgency as argued by Mohammed (2024) in the Northeast of Nigeria are as follows:

- i. Crisis of multifarious illegal roots around the Nigeria borders
- ii. Government inability to address the root cause serves as a major impediment
- iii. The endemic poverty in parts of the region which makes it very easy for the insurgents to recruit new members
- iv. Problem of weaponry. Study also identified the lack of sophisticated weapons in engaging the insurgents as a major impediment

- v. Corruption. Money voted to educate people or bolster campaign against Boko Haram end up in official pockets and private hands
- vi. Boko Haram huge collaborating network and influence and poor military strategy were also identified in this study as a major factor

Records available to the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS) according to Ogunlesi, (2015) revealed that there are over 1.400 illegal routs into Nigeria, 1316 more than the approved border control posts. This fact supports the reasons adduced in the study that is causing intensed insecurity in the Northeast of Nigeria. This fact agrees with Mayer, (2012) which posited that fighting terrorism would be difficult if the affected state is affected with porous boundary issues and without adequate formulas to deal with the situation. This finding supports findings and observations in other studies and literature. According to Odita and Akan (2014), in economic terms, what the Boko Haram insurrection created is a systemic distortion of existing economic patterns and structure in northern Nigeria. They further noted, Nigeria's northern region which has 78% of the country's land mass is the backbone of Nigeria's agricultural production in food and cash crops as well as livestock. argued that Boko Haram insurgency has affected agriculture especially in some of the country's main food-growing areas (Yobe, Adamawa and Borno states) worst hit by the insurgency, farmers are afraid to go to their farms as a result of fear of being attacked.

Conclusion

Conclusively, in recent times, Nigeria has emerged as a terrorism country in the eyes of the international community according to Nigeria Human Right Watch (2010, 2014). The growing rate of insecurity and the onslaught of terrorists' activities against the system particularly in the North, and other growing Muslim fundamentalist elements emerging in North of Nigeria does not only poses security concerns for the country and the international community, but are themselves huge symptoms of state weakness and possible failure. The inability of the Nigerian state to respond adequately to nipping the phenomenon of terrorism in the bud as observed in most literatures extracted, poses serious danger to the country's nascent democracy and economic development. There is no escaping the fact that terrorist attacks in Nigeria and globally have almost exclusively taking an escalating approach.

Recommendations

At the end of the investigation, the paper presented its recommendations as follows:

- i. That following the identified gaps identified in the area of collaboration among countries, Nigeria Government should involve a new mechanism geared towards combating terrorists' activities effective collaboration.
- ii. Budgetary provisions should be made for the acquisition of superior arms and weapons for effective counterterrorism operations.
- iii. That there is the need for steady information and intelligence sharing and communication amongst stakeholders and the general public on the need to be security conscious.
- iv. Nigeria government should put mechanism in place that will help arrest and control the influx of illegal immigrants and weapons into the country
- v. It also canvassed the need for government to ensure justice and equity in the handling of state affairs

- vi. Finally, there should be a deliberate effort by government to eliminate discrimination, nepotism, hunger, unemployment, inequality and all manner of deprivations inherent in the system.

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Herdsmen Attacks and the Challenge of Rural Development in Different Geo-Political Zones of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Another security challenge that has reared its ugly head over the years is the Herdsmen attacks on rural communities of Nigeria. The Herdsmen attacks have been experienced in different parts of the country by farmers and others alike. Though it is of high magnitude and highly destructive in recent years, the issue with the Fulani Herdsmen attacks like some other violence has its security implications. Lives and property are being destroyed virtually on daily basis by the attacks traced to the Herdsmen. The main objective of the work is to examine issues of herdsmen attacks and their impacts on rural development in Nigeria. The specific objects are to examine challenges of herdsmen attacks on rural development in Nigeria; examine the causes of the attacks by herdsmen; and elucidate on the tactics employed by herdsmen in launching attacks. The research work made use of the Frustration-Aggression theory. The methodology of the research work is qualitative. This involved the use of secondary sources of data like textbooks, journals, and newspapers. The paper found out that herdsmen have embraced violence in their day-to-day interactions with other people. The paper also realised that herdsmen attacks are usually grievous in nature with the use of sophisticated weapons. The paper recommends that both federal and state governments should look into the issue of drought and dessert encroachment, particularly in the North-East and North-West Geo-Political Zones. It also recommends that law enforcement agencies should be provided with necessary equipment in order to effectively protect the borders.

Keywords: Herdsmen, Rural Community, Development, Challenge, Violence.

Introduction

Globally, herdsmen have become known as nomadic people who engaged in livestock business as source of livelihood. The presence of the herdsmen was felt in Nigeria, with their migration to the country from Senegambia Region in the 13th and 14th century (Aniche and Ngwu, 2019). The herdsmen then moved about and lived peacefully with their neighbours. However, as Tsau (2016) noted, the herdsmen, known for going about with their sticks, for grazing are now roaming about with AK47 rifles and other dangerous weapons.

Herdsmen attacks on rural communities of Nigeria became prominent in 2016, and it has become unabated since then. The attacks are not limited to a particular geo-political zone. This is as southern Kaduna, Benue States and some parts of Plateau State have become killing fields. Parts of South East and North West have also not been spared (Punch Editorial Board, 2023). The attacks have resulted in killings of numerous Nigerians and scores injured and maimed. The herdsmen are also believed to have been responsible for thousands of death in Nigeria's Middle Belt region (The Pillar, 2022). Different reasons have been adduced for the attacks by herdsmen. The main reason behind the attacks as posited by Gursory (2019) is the

scarcity of resources like arable land and water; needed by both herders and farmers. It is imperative to mention that existing studies have dealt mainly on herders and farmers' clashes in the middle belt region of Nigeria. With the antecedents of herders and the concern over their activities, this study dealt with herdsman attacks in different geo-political zones of Nigeria.

The main objective of this study is to examine the issues of herdsman attacks and elucidate on their impact on rural development in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: examine the factors responsible for herdsman attacks on rural communities; examine the strategies utilised by herdsman in their attacks; elucidate on challenges faced by rural communities in terms of development based on the attacks; make recommendations on how the attacks would be reduced drastically.

Conceptual Clarification

The concepts that are worth clarifying in this study are rural development and nomadic herding.

Rural Development

Rural development has been variously defined by scholars. As Atkinson (2017) opined, rural development involves efforts which are economic and social in nature, aimed at encouraging the ideas of growth and expansion in areas outside cities and these include improving the quality of life of those resident in rural areas. This definition implies that rural development are social and economic efforts aimed at improving the quality of lives of the rural dwellers in terms of enhanced standard of living. The USDA (2006) in Adisa (2012:15) posited that, rural development is an "improvement in the overall rural community conditions, including economic and other quality of life considerations such as environmental health, infrastructure and housing". This implies that rural development concept is an all encompassing one, covering all aspects of rural dwellers welfare.

Sharma (2022:1) defined rural development as "planned efforts undertaken to eliminate poverty, enhance resilience, promote ecological sustainability and build capacity to meet these challenges faced by the rural areas". This denotes upliftment of the rural areas for better life. Rural development can thus be seen as any type of change that can be promoted by a state or federal government, whether political, economic and even social to enhance the living standard of rural dwellers.

Nomadic Herding:

This is one of the oldest forms of herding, nomadic herders move about with their cattle, and goats in small tribal and extended family groups having no home base. This is with the aim of providing meat, milk and hides for societal use (National Geographic Society,). The herdsman have also been seen as nomadic herders largely located in the Sahel and Semi-arid parts of West Africa and due to changes in climate patterns they have moved further South into the Savannah and tropical forest area of West Africa (Obiora, 2019).

Herders or pastoralists have had a long history of migrating and establishing relationships with various sedentary farming populations with which they co-exist, cooperate, and compete for shared renewable resources (Cabot, 2017) cited in Njoku (2021). The herdsman interaction with farming communities as Njoku (2021) posited, is often influenced by factors such as the reduction of water and pasture. In terms of occupation, herders rely on herding as means of livelihood and can hunt or practise agriculture in form of production of grains in exchange for other goods. Some herders continue to migrate seasonally in search of pasture for herds (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2024). The group of herders that engage in seasonal migration survive mainly on milk, meat, and blood gotten from the herds.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Frustration-Aggression theory. Breuer and Elson (2017) asserted that the theory was propounded by Dollard, Doob, Miller, Mowrer, and Sears in 1939.

The theory states that, “the occurrence of aggressive behaviour always presupposes the existence of frustration and, contrariwise, that the existence of frustration always leads to some forms of aggression” (Breuer & Elson, 2017:1). This in essence implies that without frustration there is no aggressive behaviour. It is frustration that triggers aggression on the part of the individual.

Frustration occurs when an individual's efforts aimed at attaining a goal is interrupted or thwarted. When the individual has no alternative way of surmounting the obstacle, he can put up aggressive behaviour (Crawford, 2015). This denotes that frustration arises from inability to meet some needs which are germane to the individual's welfare and this result in aggressive behaviour. In other words, aggressive behaviour comes up due to frustration. In essence, aggression does not occur without frustration (Breuer & Elson, 2015). In an attempt to define frustration, Jeranimus and Lacaille (2017) sees it as a key negative emotion that has its root in disappointment and it is a form of irritable distress with a wish colliding with an unyielding reality. Jeronimus and Lacaille (2017) further asserted, frustration is encountered when the individual has unresolved problems which may be contextual or psychological or obstructive in nature. This may be removed in order for the individual to be able to fulfil personal goals, drives, desires or needs.

Frustration-Aggression hypotheses has been criticised for its theoretical rigidity and overgeneralisation. Although, it is not specific or definite in its analysis (Mentovich & Jost, 2017 cited in Smarter n.d). It had also been asserted that the theory does not also state how aggressive behaviour might arise in different social settings devoid of provocation or feeling of frustration (Smarter n.d). In other words, the theory assumes that provocation or aggression is always a product of frustration in a social setting. Another criticism of Frustration-Aggression theory is that it leads to aggression that is targeted at person that caused it or provoked it, but displaced aggression can also occur in situations where the source of frustration is not visible or even tangible (Miller, 1941 cited in Crawford, 2015).

The benefit of this theory lies in the fact that it has been used to explain behaviour of animals and in recent times it has been used to study human behaviour in the social sciences and in particular, psychology and also medical research (Braver & Elson, 2017). This indicates that when an individual is frustrated there is tendency for him or her to become aggressive.

The theory is relevant to this study in the sense that the herdsmen in quest for suitable grazing land, water and other necessities for cattle often encounter confrontations from the rural communities, impeding the attainment of the set goals. These barriers and confrontations arise from the desires of the communities also for the same resources as herders, thus leading to conflicts. The herders become aggressive towards members of rural communities and as a result members of the rural communities are attacked by being killed, raped and mayhem. The attacks on rural communities take place in different geo-political zones of Nigeria, but are more prominent in the North-Central, North-East, and North-West.

Methodology

The methodology of this research work is qualitative. This is in the sense that it made use of secondary sources of data, like textbooks, newspapers, journals, and magazines. Descriptive analysis was utilised to analyse the data collected.

Identified Causes of Herdsmen Attacks

For a workable solution to herdsmen attacks on rural communities, there is the need to identify the causes of these attacks.

In the first place, there is drought and desert encroachment. This factor can be attributed to climatic changes ravaging the settlements and hamlets along the fringe of the Sahara. This had impacted severely on the land of the nomadic people that became very dry and dusty; with the resultant loss of millions of animals to the nomads (Jibunoh, 2018). The situation had being made worse by the continuous depletion of the ozone layer, which had also brought much sun

and heat across the Sahara. This had led to influx of herders to various rural communities in Nigeria, particularly the middle-belt zone. Over time, the influx became too much for the people in the middle belt to bear, as the number of the herders and their animals increased to millions and the migration became a permanent thing (Jubinoh, 2018). This no doubt pitched the indigenes against the nomads as they were gradually being deprived of arable land to cultivate crops to enhance their livelihood.

Secondly, there is the issue of porous borders that enables herders from Benin Republic, Burkina-Faso, Togo and Mali to take over some parts of Imeko-Afon local government in Ogun State. These herders with their cattle, not only destroyed farmers' crops but also engaged in criminal activities like armed robbery, and kidnapping (Ayinla, 2021). Similarly, the issue of porous borders enables herders to migrate easily to Nigeria from neighbouring countries like Niger and Cameroon, as the country posses a lot of greenery along the middle belt zone serving as a buffer. This makes such places to be attractive and Nigeria's herders now joined their brothers in the North to invade the different parts of the country under siege (Jubinoh, 2018). It is also not out of place to say that, the militants from war torn countries like Libya and Chad have also complimented the these nomads with their arms (Jubinoh, 2018).

The anti-grazing law that has been introduced in Benue and Ekiti States had also infuriated the herdsman. The Benue grazing law provides for procedure by which land could be acquired for ranching in the state. The amended law made it clear that if any cow is found moving about the owner will pay ₦500,000 as fine (Charles, 2022). Herdsman had found this law as unpalatable.

Ethno-religious sentiments also serve as another cause of the attacks on some rural communities in Nigeria by rampaging herdsman. Incidents worth mentioning are the attacks waged on the people of southern Kaduna State by herdsman. Even in its 5th year (precisely 2017), thousands of people had been killed in their homes and farms, with livelihoods of thousands destroyed. As at 2017, 53 villages were ruined and some of them occupied by herdsman and their cattle, a sort of forceful occupation (Ochonu, 2017).

Dispute between herders and farmers over land is another major cause of attacks on rural communities. While farmers depend on and cherish the farmlands for their crops, the herders also passionately desire same land and their crops to feed their cattle. The people of Egbeleli Agwu Council of Enugu State had of recent raised alarm over the invasion of their community by herdsman who have threatened and prevented them from entering their farmlands to harvest their crops and even killed two of the indigenes, burnt motorcycles and bicycles belonging to members of the community. Njoku (2023) further alleged that they often waylaid the women in the farm and rape and kidnap them. This was equally the situation in Ughelli, Delta State, when suspected herdsman attacked a mosque, kidnapped three worshippers and injured one (Osayanda, 2022).

At another time, suspected herdsman also attacked Owode-Ketu and Ijoun villages in the Yewa-North Local Government Area of Ogun State and two persons were killed in the attacks. They were alleged to have been killed on their farms by the herdsman (Olatunji, 2021). While virtually all the states of the federation have their share of herdsman attacks, the attacks in Benue villages have become worrisome. As at May, 2019, it was alleged that an estimated 7,000 Nigerians died between the year 2015 and 2019 as a result of persistent clashes between farmers and pastoralists, in the middle belt states of Nasarawa and Benue States (Sanni, 2019). The attacks on the farmers in the villages of Benue State had escalated to a very high level as the attacks are almost on daily basis, often with heavy casualties.

Cattle rustling is another reason for herdsman attacks. The herdsman having lose their cattle to bandits and impoverished often unleash terror on host communities or their neighbours who are not. Cattle rustling is a source of concern in some Northern states of Nigeria, with Zamfara State worst hit in the North West Zone. Here, bandits often kill herdsman and steal

their cattle (El-Kwerebe, 2016). As El-Kwerebe (2016) further asserted, as at February, 2016, 75 people were killed and many others were injured, while thousands of cattle were carted away by the rustlers. Some of the villages that were worst affected are Anguwar, Duke, Angwar Kawo, Malale, Sebuwar, Aguwa, Sawale and Renda. Consequently, the feeling of unjust treatment made herders to become criminals, engaging in kidnapping and other vices (Usman, 2021). It is therefore not surprising that Sheikh Gumi became and advocate of forgiveness and compensation for the herdsman, clamouring that they be pacified and offered amnesty and with these as he asserted they would drop their weapons (Nasiru, 2021).

Strategies of the Herdsmen in their Attacks on Rural Communities

The attacks have been regular, systemic and targeted in nature. Those that have been vulnerable to attacks are mainly farmers living in rural communities (Akinloye, 2021). The Global, Terrorist Index 2019 published by the Institute for Economics and Peace had attributed rise in terrorism to extremists who launched attacks that accounted for the majority of terror related deaths (Akinloye, 2021). Innocent individuals are target of attacks, the killings had somehow become the most organised and systematic “ethnic cleansing ever launched against a people in the country since the pre-civil war of 1966 and 1967 in Northern Nigerian when Igbos and some southerners were murdered” (Etim, 2023).

Nocturnal attacks by herdsman serve as another strategy of the herdsman. It has been realised that majority of the attacks by herdsman take place in the night. For instance, the Igangan attack started at midnight when the people were far asleep. The attackers struck and killed several persons and razed property (Taiwo-Hassan, 2021). In Taraba and Adamawa States, it has been asserted that farmers were being attacked in their homes by herdsman at night (Kazeem, 2018). This was also the situation in Agatu LGA, when marauding herdsman attacked the communities in 2015 at about 4:30am and killed several villagers. Their mode of operation is to attack at night and retreat to their hideouts.

The weapons of attacks by the herders are usually guns, machetes, and daggers, killing children, mothers and pregnant women, not even sparing the foetus (Ugwanyi, 2015). There is unfettered access to arms as a result of some countries like Chad and Libya were in war and some of the arms used were brought into Nigeria by herders. As Okoli (2017) pointed out, the militant herdsman now use modern weaponry as well as guns in their quest for the attacks of rural communities.

The herdsman are also known for reprisal attacks, which may not take place immediately or even for months. It has been asserted for instance that, the attack on Agatu community in February, 2016 was a retaliatory attack based on the killing of a prominent herdsman by the Agatu people years before. In a similar vein, “12 residents of Taraba, Mada, Migini and Angwan Barar communities in the Kokini Local Government Area of Nassarawa State were killed by herdsman, with houses and property worth millions of naira belonging to the residents burnt in a reprisal attack (Sunday, 2023).

Herdsmen Attacks and the Challenge of Rural Development in Nigeria

The challenges of frequent attacks by herdsman on rural communities have manifested unbearable consequences on rural communities and Nigeria as a whole.

There is the impending problem of food supply. The major occupation of rural dwellers in Nigeria is farming. With the continuous attacks of herdsman in the various rural communities in Ekiti, Benue, Plateau, Ogun, Oyo and even the South East states, there is shortage of food supply in the next few years. This is because, farmers have incurred massive loses in farm produce over the years. The herders are accused of feeding their animals with growing food crops to the disadvantage of the farmers (Adeniran, 2014). With persistent destruction of crops, the situation has brought loss and frustration on farmers and the decision of some of the farmers to engage in other traders. There has been threat from farmers in Saki, Tede, Iseyin and the whole of Oke Ogun region of Oyo State to quit farming and the food crops affected are cassava,

yam, sorghum, cassava flour and maize (Adeniran, 2014). The crops due for harvest are also affected by the attacks while those stored up in barns are not spared.

Loss of revenue is a serious challenge arising from herdsmen attacks on rural communities. A report from global humanitarian organisation, known as 'Mercy Corps' revealed that, conflict between farmers and herdsmen in rural communities across the North Central zone of Nigeria was costing Nigeria about \$14 billion revenues yearly. This report was issued by Mercy Corps (Ogundipe & Oluwole, 2016). Mercy Corps, funded by the British Department for International Development (DFID), based on its research work between 2013 and 2016 (Ogundipe & Oluwole, 2016). The issue of loss of revenue that would have accrued to individuals and served as a boost for rural development was buttressed by Governor Samuel Ortom, who observed that, between 2015 and 2018, Benue State lost over ₦400 billion worth of property (Ejembi, 2018). It has been revealed that due to the onslaughts, bustling farmlands have been deserted with its attendant negative effect on internally generated revenue which had reduced drastically in Benue State due to decrease food production (Duru, 2021).

Herdsmen attacks had also encouraged rural-urban migration. Rural-urban migration is the movement of people in the rural areas to the urban areas. As Ogunmakinde, Oladokun and Oke (2015) opined, such an internal movement had resulted in rural poverty, abandonment of agriculture and unbalanced population concentration. The implications of such movements for urban areas are socio-economic and political in nature. Some of these implications as posited by Johnson and Ifeoma are urban traffic congestion, high crime rate, armed robbery, drug abuse, inadequate refuse and waste disposal system (Johnson & Ifeoma, 2018). In addition, the aged women and children in some cases are left behind to labour on the farms with its attendant consequence on agricultural output, the gross domestic product of the nation and reduction in funds for development, income and standard of living of the rural dwellers (Johnson & Ifeoma, 2018).

Internal displacement is another challenge for rural development resulting from herdsmen attacks. As Okoro (2018) posited, displacement of persons internally abound based on herdsmen attacks. The case of farmers, the displaced farmers and their families have become liabilities to other farmers, as they have to beg for food for their upkeep. As a result of repeated attacks in Benue communities, by herdsmen, over one million residents have been displaced across the state (Charles, 2021). Life, however has not been easy for a number of internally displaced persons in Nigeria. As observed by Bolaji, Maria – Thereso and Peter (2019) in most of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps, the inhabitants looked pale, hungry and consciously waiting for the next round of handouts, which are often not enough to cover for their needs in Taraba, Plateau and Benue States. These have led to deaths being recorded in the camps.

Herdsmen attacks on rural communities had also promoted ethnic disunity in Nigeria. this is to the extent that political office holders like President Muhammadu Buhari are seen as ethnic bigot, that is always doing things in favour of the herders, which is his ethnic group. At different times, there had been verbal wars between the leaders of Miyatti Allah/Meccab and some other ethnic groups like the Odua Peoples Congress (OPC), Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), the Arewa Elders Forum and others alike. The ethnic dimension has been enhanced for instance, by President Muhammadu Buhari's decision in 2000 to lead the cattle rearers in Oyo State, to the then Governor of Oyo State, Alhaji Lam Adesina to protest the shock inflicted on them by Oke-Ogun farmers (The Cable, 2018). There was trading of wards between the leadership of the Pan-Arewa socio-cultural organisation, the coalition of Northern Groups and that of Oodua People's Congress over the killings of some residents of Igangan community, which occurred shortly after the arrest of Wakili, a herdsman in the town (Olorok, 2021).

Underdevelopment of rural communities also manifests from herdsmen attacks in Nigeria. Underdevelopment can be perceived as a situation that is characterised by

unemployment, underemployment, low per capita income, poverty, abundant but underutilized net worth resources, and low productivity (Jose, 2020). In Nigeria, poverty is particularly severe in rural areas as a large number of inhabitants live below the poverty line, and social services and infrastructure are inadequate (Paul, Agba, Chukura, 2014). This in essence implies that rural dwellers experience deprivation politically, socially, and economically.

Another challenge for rural development as a result of herdsmen attacks is that it has brought about the loss of able bodied men and women in their prime thus depleting the human resources needed for development in the rural areas. For instance, there has been “tales of alleged Fulani herdsmen attacks on some villages and gruesome killing of innocent people in the South West, and in some parts of Delta and Enugu States” (Adeniran, 2014, 42). Worst hit are the Middle Belt regions, in particular, Benue and Plateau States, it is on record that between 2015 and 2016, more than 170 lives were lost in Tiv land, while in Agatu community, more than 500 people had been hacked to death. The situation is worrisome as the herdsmen have occupied 15 out of the 25 local governments in the state (Ameh, Owumanan & Awoyinfa, 2016). Below is a table showing attacks by herdsmen on rural communities in different parts of Nigeria.

Selected attacks by herdsmen on some rural communities in different geo-political zones of Nigeria

S/N	Date of attack	Place of attack	Casualty
1.	September 21, 2015	Falae’s farm in Ondo State (Ilado village)	Abduction of Chief Olu Falae from his farm for 3 days
2.	September, 2016	Akachele village of Ibimo in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State	3 catholic priests were attacked by suspected herdsmen
3.	August, 2017	Ore, Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State	A grandmother was raped by Fulani herdsmen.
4.	October, 2017	Tudun Lambaga, Eggon Local Government Area, Nassarawa State	A 14 year old girl was raped by two Fulani herdsmen
5.	January 1, 2018	Attack on communities in Benue State	73 persons were reported to have been killed.
6.	January 6, 2018	Lau Local Government Area of Taraba State	55 villagers were killed
7.	13 th , 14 th and 15 th February, 2020	Avwon, Agadama and Ohoror communities of Uwhoru kingdom, Ughelli North Local Government Area of Delta State.	14 persons lost their lives.
8.	5 th January, 2021	Igangan in Ibarapa North Local Government Area of Oyo State	10 persons were reportedly killed

9.	17 th April, 2022	Kanam Local Government Area of Plateau State	142 villagers were killed
10.	12 th & 13 th April, 2022	Communities in Usi-Uzo Local Government Area of Enugu State	3 persons were killed
11.	31 st July, 2022	Jos South Local Government Area, Plateau State	7 persons were killed.
12.	3 rd April, 2023	Ugbobi Community, Apa Local Government Area, Benue State	The Ugbobi traditional ruler and several other people were killed.
13.	5 th April, 2023	Umogidi Community Entokpa Adoka district Otukpo Local Government Area, Benue State	46 persons including a policeman lost their lives.
14.	25 th April, 2023	Opaha, Odogbo and Edikwu Communities of Apa Local Government Area of Benue State	10 persons killed
15.	15 th and 16 th May, 2023	Several villages on the Mangu district of Plateau	About 80 people were killed

Sources: Abraham, J. (2022); Charles, J. & Adewole, S. (2023); Ochogwu, S. (2023); Olaniyi, O. (2021); Oluwagbemi, A. (2018); Ebiri, K., Okafor, N. S., Egbejule, M., Akpan-Nsoh & Osahon, J. (2020); Essien, H. (2022); Asadu, C. (2023); Ojoye, T. (2017); Charles, J. & Dada, P. (2018); Isiguzo, C. (2016); Duru, P. (2023); Nigeria Watch (2020).

From the table above, it would be seen that states in the North-Central Geopolitical zone, namely: Nasarawa, Benue, and Plateau States experienced a large number of attacks from herdsmen, with lots of casualty. For instance, on January 1, 2018, the attacks on communities in Benue State led to the death of 73 persons. On 17th April, 2022, Plateau State witnessed attack in Kanam Local Government Area with 142 deaths recorded, while several villages in the Mangu District of Plateau State recorded 80 death, on 15th and 16th May, 2023. In the South-East Geopolitical Zone, specifically in the Akachaele of Ibimo in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, three Catholic Priests were attacked in September, 2016. On 12th and 13th April, 2022, attacks on communities in Usi-Uzo Local Government Area of Enugu State led to three deaths. In Avwom, Agadama and Ohoror communities of Uwhoru Kingdom, Ughelli North Local Government Area, Delta State (South-South), 14 lives were lost due to herdsmen attack, while in Ondo State, Chief Olufalae was adopted on his farm in Ilado village on September 21, 2015 and a grandmother was brutally raped on her farm in Ore Ondo State by two herdsmen in August 2017. The attacks were perpetrated without intervention from the law enforcement agencies and left victims, their relatives and associates devastated. Some of those that were not dead or injured sought refuge in Internally Displaced Persons Camps in Benue State.

It is worth noting that most of the killings in the communities discussed above have been carried out without any genuine reasons.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the foregoing, it would be seen that a lot of factors like climatic issues, ethno-religious sentiment, and porosity of Nigeria's borders are responsible for the attacks by herdsmen on rural communities. It has also been realised that herdsmen employed different strategies in attacks on rural communities. These attacks have far-reaching consequences on the rural communities concerned in Nigeria.

It is hereby recommended that the Nigerian government should deal with the issue of drought and desert encroachment through massive tree planting, especially in the North-East and North-West Geo-Political Zones. There should also be protection of marginal lands in these geo-political zones in order to avoid further damage to the lands. The soil can also be enriched with required nutrients and alternative sources of energy can be provided in order to reduce felling of trees. In order to deal with border porosity, the law enforcement agencies, particularly the Nigeria Immigration Service should be provided with the necessary equipment and vehicles that will assist them in monitoring Nigeria's borders effectively. Efforts should also be made to improve the relationship among the different ethnic groups and religious groups, so as to enhance harmonious living among the different groups.

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A Continent at Risk: Interrogating the Power Dynamics in Hazardous Waste Trade in Africa

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Abstract

This paper examines the complex dynamics and implications of hazardous waste trade within the context of international relations and resource governance in Africa. It explores the roles of the various players/actors into trade in hazardous waste such as state parties, and private parties such as transnational corporations (TNCs). It utilises qualitative approaches; especially the use of secondary sources as journal articles, textbooks, and online sources in its methodology. The paper discovers that there are disparities in the power dynamics between exporting and importing states into hazardous trade in waste, the prevalence of illegal dumping practices, and the challenges faced by African states in enforcing environmental regulations and holding transnational corporations accountable for their actions. In order to mitigate the negative effects of hazardous waste trading and to promote sustainable development on the continent, the paper emphasises the urgent need to strengthen regulatory frameworks, increase transparency, and enhance cooperations among stakeholders. It contributes to the understanding of the complex web of political, economic, and environmental factors shaping the international politics of hazardous waste trade in Africa.

Keywords: Politics, Trade, Hazardous Waste, Africa

Introduction

In economic discourse, the Heckscher-Ohlin Model, dictates that differences in factor endowments amongst nations, compels trade among nations necessary, if not mandatory (Kopp, 2024). There is convergence amongst most economists who argue that international trade improves living standards worldwide. The accruable benefits from international trade are enormous and immeasurable to all countries of the world; several times, nations benefit more from trade with one another (McDonald, 2009). However, while the benefits from international trade are appreciated, incontestable and cannot be overemphasised; however, both within countries and between governments, trade can be one of the most divisive political topics (Reuveny & Kang, 1996; Madeira, 2014; Dorfman, 2016); especially that it can be harmful to sovereign states in diverse ways (FAO, 2022).

For example, international trade is capable of causing damage to human health, the economy of sovereign states, insecurity through illicit economies (such as smuggling through drug trafficking; human trafficking, prostitution; deforestation through illegal trade in timber, timber logging, trade in antiquities, etc.); illicit fishing, piracy, oil theft/bunkering, arms trafficking and the eventual proliferation of arms in the continent, etc. still international trade harms the environment through the transportation of hazardous or toxic wastes, trade in endangered species, exchange of pesticides, pollution of the marine and terrestrial environments (Frankel, 2009).

Particularly, international trade in hazardous waste presents peculiar complex and pressing issues, particularly in vulnerable African communities. While international agreements such as the 1989 Basel Convention aims to regulate the transboundary movement and disposal of hazardous waste, there are ongoing challenges and controversies surrounding the trade in hazardous waste in Africa that undermines the efficacy of regulatory instruments (Agbor, 2016). Research indicates that African states are disproportionately affected by the transboundary movement of hazardous waste, with detrimental effects on public health, environmental degradation, and socioeconomic development; however, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of the intricate web of actors, interests, and power dynamics involved in the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in the African context (Atteh, 1993).

This study addresses this gap by examining the following key problems related to the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in selected African states. First, is the lack of effective regulation despite the existence of international agreements such as the Basel Convention (Agbor, 2016). There are expressed concerns over the effectiveness of regulations governing the trade in hazardous waste in African states. Studies have shown that regulatory frameworks may be inadequate or poorly enforced, leading to loopholes and opportunities for illegal dumping and improper disposal of hazardous waste (Oteng-Ababio, 2018).

Second, is the power dynamics and environmental justice at play in the trade in hazardous waste which is often characterised by global power imbalance, with developed states exporting hazardous wastes to developing states. This raises questions of environmental justice and equity, as African states may bear a disproportionate burden of the environmental and health impacts of hazardous waste disposal (Doyle, 2017). Third, economic incentives and trade pressures that play significant roles in driving the trade in hazardous waste, with financial incentives influencing decisions to accept the importation of waste. African states facing dire economic hardship may be tempted to accept waste imports for monetary gains, potentially overlooking the environmental and social consequences of such actions (Sanchez, 1994).

Fourth, is the governance and capacity constraints, limited resources, and capacity constraints that weaken governance structures among African states that pose challenges to effective regulation and management of hazardous waste. The lack of institutional capacity, technical expertise, and financial resources often impede efforts to monitor and control trade in hazardous waste which leads to environmental and health risks for local communities (Doe, 2020); and fifth, the environmental and health impacts caused by the improper disposal and management of hazardous waste often have severe consequences, including soil and water contaminations, air pollution, and adverse health effects on communities living near toxic waste sites. Trade in hazardous waste raises concerns over the potential long-term environmental degradation and health risks faced by vulnerable African populations.

In light of the foregoing problems, this paper explores the dynamics of international politics of trade in hazardous waste in selected African states. The objective of this paper is to examine the complex dynamics and implications of hazardous waste trade in Africa within the context of international relations and resource governance. It does this by exploring the roles of the various players/actors into hazardous waste such as state parties, and private parties like transnational corporations (TNCs). The paper insists that by addressing the regulatory gaps, power dynamics, economic interests, governance challenges, and environmental impacts associated with the trade in hazardous waste, it aims to contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable solutions for managing hazardous waste in Africa.

To do the foregoing task, the rest of the paper is structured thus; following this introduction is Section II, the extant literature of the paper; dwelling on amongst other issues, including historicising hazardous trade in waste, understanding the international politics of trade in hazardous waste and stakeholder perspectives on trade in hazardous waste. Section III makes a critical assessment of the international politics of trade in hazardous waste. Section IV concludes the paper.

Extant Literature

There is a marked difference between legal and illegal trade in hazardous waste. Interestingly, not all trade in hazardous waste that is classified as illegal (Baggs, 2009). However, trade in hazardous waste becomes only illicit when it is:

undertaken without state permission, when contracts and concessions are secured through corruption or intimidation, when services involve fraud (e.g., false treatment of hazardous waste), and...Such illegal activities can have significant impacts on the health and sustainability of local populations and ecosystems. (FATF, 2021, p. 9)

This section examines literature related to the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa under the following subthemes:

a. Historicising Hazardous Waste Trade: From the Local to International Scales

Hazardous waste refers to the global exchange of hazardous waste materials for recycling, disposal or treatment. This practice has been around for several decades and has had far-reaching environmental, social, and political implications (Strohm, 1993; Clapp, 1994). Hazardous waste trade on an international scale has a long and complex history with various significant developments shaping the current landscape of global waste management (Anyinam, 1991; Bisschop, 2016). Trade in hazardous waste can be traced back to the 1960s

and 1970s when industrialised states of the global North began exporting hazardous waste to developing states in the global South with less stringent regulations. This practice was driven by economic considerations as it was often cheaper to export waste to states with less stringent domestic environmental regulations governing the management of hazardous waste. However, the trade in hazardous waste soon attracted criticism from environmentalists and human rights activists, who raised concern about the risks posed to local communities in receiving states.

These concerns were highlighted in the 1980s by high-profile cases like the Probo Koala incident in 2006, involving the dumping of toxic waste in the Cote d'Ivoire by a Dutch company, and which resulted in widespread health and environmental impacts (Puckett, 2003). This singular incident highlighted the need for stronger regulations and enforcement mechanisms to prevent the illegal trafficking of hazardous waste. The 1989 Basel Convention on the Control of Trans-boundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal, amongst others, was one of the key international action efforts at curtailing hazardous waste trade. The Basel Convention was a response to the growing concern over the environmental and health impact of unregulated trade in hazardous waste, particularly in developing states. The convention established a framework for regulating the transboundary movement of hazardous wastes and aimed to minimise their generation and disposal (Smith, 2019).

Since the adoption of the 1989 Basel Convention, there has been several amendments and protocols to strengthen its provisions and adapt to new challenges in managing hazardous waste. One notable amendment is the Ban Amendment, adopted in 1995, which prohibits the export of hazardous wastes from developed to developing states for disposal. This amendment was a significant step towards preventing the export of hazardous waste to states with inadequate facilities for their safe disposal (UNEP, 2018).

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the need to address the root causes of hazardous waste generation and promote more sustainable and environmentally sound hazardous waste management practices on a global scale. The concept of a circular economy, which aims to minimise waste generation and promote the recycling and reuse of material, has gained attraction as a way to reduce hazardous waste trade. International initiatives such as the Strategic Approach to International Chemical Management (SAICM); the 21 October 2001 Waigani Convention, the 1998 Rotterdam Convention, the 1991 Bamako Convention, the 2001 Stockholm Convention, the OECD Council Decision on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Wastes, amongst others, provide legal regimes for the prevention and regulation of transboundary movement of hazardous waste for whatever reasons; essentially to protect human health and the environment (Ansari, et al, 2019; Ogunola, et al, 2020).

These key events, treaties, and regulations have played crucial roles in shaping the landscape of hazardous waste trade by establishing mechanisms for international cooperation, promoting transparency and accountability, and safeguarding human health and the environment. However, challenges remain in ensuring effective implementation and enforcement of these agreements, as well as in addressing emerging issues such as e-waste. The effectiveness of international agreements in regulating hazardous waste trade in African states has been mixed. One of the key limitations is the lack of capacity and resources in many African states to effectively implement and enforce these agreements. This often result in weak regulatory frameworks and inadequate monitoring of hazardous waste shipments, leading to improper disposal and environmental pollution (Mabunda & Edeme, 2017).

Furthermore, the illegal trade in hazardous waste remains a significant challenge, with criminal networks exploiting regulatory loopholes and weak enforcement mechanisms. This

illicit trade not only poses risks to human health and the environment but also undermines the efforts of legitimate authorities to regulate hazardous waste trade.

b. Understanding the International Politics of Trade in Hazardous Waste

Understanding the international politics of trade in hazardous waste is significant due to its implications for environmental sustainability, economic development, and social justice. The intricate dynamics of hazardous waste trade intersect various disciplines and require a nuanced understanding of global governance, environmental regulations, and sustainable practices as demonstrated hereunder:

First, is the need for environmental sustainability; especially that trade in hazardous waste has direct consequences on the environment, including pollution, soil contamination, and health hazards to local communities (Bürgerin & Schemel, 2017). Second reason dwells on the need for economic development in that proper management of hazardous waste has enormous impact on economic development among African states, particularly, in influencing investment decisions, trade relations, and industrial practices. It is also crucial for policymakers and stakeholders to navigate the balance between economic growth and environmental protection, fostering sustainable development practices in the way (O'Connor, 2015); and,

Third, is on social justice because it borders on the premise that hazardous waste trade often raises concerns over environmental justice, as communities disproportionately affected by pollution and waste disposal may face social inequalities and health risks. Examining the international politics of hazardous waste trade in African states shed light on issues of environmental equity, community empowerment, and the need for transparency in decision-making processes (Zhang, 2018).

c. Stakeholder Perspectives on Trade in Hazardous Waste

Stakeholder perspectives and interests in hazardous waste trade vary significantly by their diverse roles and motivations. Government regulators are key stakeholders with a mandate to enforce regulations and ensure compliance with environmental and health standards (UNEP, 2021). On the other hand, industries that generate hazardous waste may have conflicting interests. Some industries may view hazardous waste trade as a cost-effective solution to disposal and compliance challenges. However, concerns have been raised over the potential for companies to use trade as a means to evade stricter regulations in their home states, leading to environmental degradation in receiving nations (UNEP, 2021).

Environmental groups, on their part, often oppose hazardous waste trade due to the inherent risks it poses to ecosystems and human health. They advocate for stricter regulations and a shift towards sustainable waste management practices. Furthermore, pro-environmental groups also advocate for the cooperation of local communities situated near hazardous waste facilities or transport routes that are directly impacted by these activities (Ogunola, et al. 2016).

Like pro-environmental groups, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) also play crucial roles in advocating for the interests of affected communities and pushing for stronger regulations and engaging in oversight functions in attempt to curtail hazardous waste trade. NGOs often collaborate with local communities to raise awareness, monitor trade activities, and hold stakeholders accountable for their actions (UNEP, 2021). International organisations such as the United Nations Environment Programme work towards establishing global frameworks to govern hazardous waste management practices (UNEP, 2021).

In contrast, some primate interests including recycling companies partake in hazardous waste trade as an opportunity for obtaining raw materials for recycling processes. By

participating in hazardous waste trade activities, these companies insist they contribute to reducing the environmental burden of waste disposal. However, the challenges lie in ensuring that the recycling processes are conducted responsibly and do not lead to further environmental harm in the recipient states (Ogunola, et al, 2016).

The International Politics of Trade in Hazardous Waste in Africa

An ensuing power dynamics and diplomatic relations play significant roles in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa. Amongst others, historical legacies, economic interests, regulatory frameworks and geopolitical considerations influence the power dynamics in hazardous waste trade (Wynne, 1989). Essentially, the importance of power differentials in shaping environmental governance is emphasised as more dominant and powerful states and other actors often exert influence over regulatory processes and decision-making. This power dynamics impacts how regulations are formulated and implemented; which benefits the interests of the more powerful actors involved in hazardous waste trade (Dryzek & Schlosberg, 2017). This manifests in unequal bargaining power between African states and wealthier states of the global North and their transnational corporations (TNCs).

Diplomatic relations between African states and global actors also impact on the regulation and management of hazardous waste trade. Obviously, policy differentials in environmental regulations promote trade in hazardous waste (Kellenberg, 2012). In this context, African states often grapple with conflicting pressures from different stakeholders, including other states, and non-state actors like TNCs and international organisations in the face of diverse international environmental treaties and agreements that shape this ever-unfolding diplomatic interactions (Moss, 2018). Apparently, these diplomatic negotiations influence the ratification and enforcement of international conventions or environmental agreements such as the Basel Convention on the Control of Trans-boundary Movements of Hazardous Waste and Their Disposal.

Moreso, economic interests and incentives also play significant roles in shaping the power dynamics in hazardous waste trade. It is obvious that economic incentives do influence decision-making and thus shape diplomatic relations with global actors involved in hazardous waste trade. Hence some African states derive economic gains from importing hazardous waste for recycling or disposal, despite the associated environmental and health risks (Sarr & Baram, 2017). The pursuit of economic gains obviously outweighs environmental concerns; and which of course explains the complex interplay of factors that shapes the politics of trade in hazardous waste.

At the risk of repetition, power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors are pivotal in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste in Africa. However, what considerations or explanations are identified and responsible for explaining how global factors influence decision-making and governance in the management of hazardous trade in waste products. The underlisted explanations are being identified as being culpable in explaining how external actors influence decision-making and governance among African states over trade in hazardous waste:

a. Historical context

Historical context of power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors in shaping the international politics of trade in hazardous waste is crucial in understanding the complexities and challenges faced by African states in managing trade in hazardous waste. Colonial legacies and ties have continued to influence relations between African states and global actors shaping trade in hazardous waste. No doubt, colonialism has had a profound impact on the power dynamics of hazardous waste trade in Africa through the exploitation of natural resources, coupled with the imposition of unequal trade relations by colonial powers that has left a lasting legacy of economic dependency and imbalanced power relations between African states and their former colonial masters (Akere, 2019).

Furthermore, a legacy of historical exploitation of African resources has also influenced diplomatic relations with global actors involved in hazardous waste trade. The legacy of economic disparities and the perception of Africa as a dumping ground for hazardous waste has shaped how African states negotiate with foreign states, their governments and TNCs in regulating the transboundary movement of hazardous waste (Agyei-Mensah, 2016). In this whole gamut of unequal trade relations, the historical context of environmental injustice and the ensuing social inequalities in hazardous waste trade cannot be overlooked. The disproportionate burden of environmental degradation and health risks borne by toxic impacted communities in Africa reflects power differentials and diplomatic interests over social and environmental considerations (Narteh, 2018). Indeed, an understanding of this skewed historical context is essential for policymakers, researchers, and environmental activists seeking to address the challenges of hazardous waste management and promoting environmental sustainability in Africa.

b. Regulatory frameworks

Effective regulatory frameworks, both at national and international levels, play critical roles in shaping power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states and global actors in the international politics of trade in hazardous waste on the African continent. The need to explore the significance of regulatory mechanisms in influencing decision-making processes, fostering cooperation, and addressing power differentials in hazardous waste management cannot be overemphasised (Kellenberg, 2012).

Nationally, robust regulatory frameworks are essential for establishing standards, guidelines, and enforcing mechanisms to govern the import, export, and disposal of hazardous waste within the borders of a state. This is because strong national regulations provide a foundation for ensuring environmental protection, public health, and social responsibility in hazardous waste trade practices (EPA, 2019). The effectiveness of national regulations is known to influence the power dynamics between governments, industries, and community stakeholders, in shaping how hazardous waste is managed and controlled within the jurisdiction of a state.

Additionally, the harmonisation of national regulatory frameworks with international agreements and conventions is crucial for promoting transparency, accountability, and cooperation in hazardous waste management. International treaties such as the 1989 Basel Convention provides a framework for regulating transboundary movements of hazardous waste and which ensures that exporting and importing states adhere to common standards (Basel Convention, 1989). By synchronising, harmonising and aligning national regulations with international norms, African states can mitigate power differentials, enhance diplomatic relations, and foster mutual trust with global actors in hazardous waste trade.

The efficacy of regulatory frameworks in shaping power dynamics and diplomatic relations are underscored by their role in promoting dialogue, negotiation, and collaboration among stakeholders involved in hazardous waste management. Clear and enforceable regulations create a level playing field for all parties; especially in enabling African states to engage in meaningful discussions with global actors on hazardous waste trade practices, and sustainable environmental responsibilities (UNEP, 2020). Additionally, regulatory coherence and compliance contribute to building trust and credibility among states into trade in hazardous waste, which fosters stronger diplomatic ties and cooperative partnerships in addressing shared environmental challenges.

In essence, the effectiveness of regulatory frameworks at national and international levels, is instrumental in shaping the power dynamics and diplomatic relations among African states vis-à-vis global actors into trade in hazardous waste. Chiefly, prioritising regulatory alignment, enforcement, and collaboration, African states should be empowered to navigate the complexities of hazardous waste management, promote environmental sustainability, and uphold their interests in a globalised waste trade landscape.

c. Environmental justice

Trade in hazardous waste presents a complex and challenging issue of environmental justice (EJ) for African states, as they navigate the dynamics of power and diplomacy with global actors. Environmental justice is crucial in that it emphasises equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, as well as fair treatment in environmental decision-making processes. In the context of trade in hazardous waste, EJ plays the role of determining how the impacts of trade in hazardous waste are distributed among different communities, particularly within African states (Kazakeviciute & Juodkaite, 2019).

African states, like many other developing states, often become destinations for hazardous waste due to lax regulations and lower costs of disposal (Kellenberg, 2012). This creates a situation where toxic impacted communities, often the most vulnerable and least equipped to deal with the negative environmental and health impacts, bear the brunt of these activities. Principles of EJ insist on a reevaluation of these power imbalances and advocate for the inclusion of the voices of marginalised communities in decision-making processes related to hazardous waste trade (Pellow & Brulle, 2005).

The salience in environmental justice is that it underscores a deeper understanding of the complexities and challenges faced by African states in managing and regulating trade in hazardous waste; which often do open up potential avenues for promoting more equitable and sustainable practices in the handling of hazardous waste with profound implications for policy-making and international cooperation.

d. Geographical considerations

The location of African states; especially, their proximity to major global markets, and the presence of natural resources all impact the dynamics of hazardous waste trade on the continent. The geographical location of the African continent in relation to other continents influences the involvement of global actors in hazardous waste trade; especially that powerful states and their TNCs usually exploit or capitalise on geographical factors to gain control over waste disposal sites or to export waste to regions with less regulatory oversight (Kellenberg, 2012). These actions often perpetuate a cycle of environmental injustice, environmental unsustainability, public health, adverse economic development and place a disproportionate

burden on African states that lack the resources and institutional capacity to effectively regulate trade in hazardous waste (Watts, 2012; Adam, 2018).

Be that as it may, the uneven distribution of hazardous waste facilities and disposal sites within Africa often lead to disparities in environmental burdens and risks among different regions and states. This uneven distribution also give rise to tensions and conflicts over the disposal of waste, as states may seek to offload their waste onto neighbouring states with lax regulations (Batur, 2019). A deeper understanding the interconnectedness of geography, power, and diplomacy in the context of hazardous waste trade in Africa, there is need to develop more informed policies and strategies to promote sustainable development and environmental justice in Africa.

e. Transparency and accountability

The primacy of transparency and accountability in trade in hazardous waste is not farfetched. For example, transparency in hazardous waste trade, amongst others, (a) it provides access to information, data, and decision-making processes related to waste management practices; (b) it increases the visibility and public awareness of African states on hazardous waste trade activities; (c) it enables stakeholders to hold governments and global actors accountable for their actions; (d) it helps to build trust between governing bodies, industry stakeholders, and local communities; (e) it fosters positive relationship and promoting cooperation in addressing environmental challenges associated with trade in hazardous waste (Gore, 2018).

Accountability is equally important in shaping the power dynamics and diplomatic relations in trade in hazardous waste. Establishing clear lines of responsibility and mechanisms for oversight holds actors involved in waste management accountable for their actions and decisions. When adequate accountability measures are in place, African states can ensure that regulations are enforced, environmental standards are upheld, and the rights of affected communities are enforced (Jones & Smith, 2019). Accountability fosters a culture of responsibility and ethical conduct, which can influence diplomatic relations with global actors who prioritise environmental stewardship and adherence to international norms

Conclusion

This paper examines the intricate dynamics and ramifications of the trade in hazardous waste. It also explores the diverse roles played by state parties and private entities, including transnational corporations (TNCs) in the hazardous waste trade. It reveals power imbalances in the trade in hazardous waste between exporting and importing states, illegal dumping occurs frequently, and that African states have difficulty enforcing environmental laws and holding transnational corporations into hazardous waste trade culpable for their deeds.

It further highlights the critical needs for improved stakeholder cooperation, more openness, and stronger regulatory frameworks in order to reduce the detrimental effects of hazardous waste trading on the environment and impacted communities and advance sustainable development in the continent. Overall, the paper advances scholarly knowledge of the intricate network of environmental, political, and economic variables influencing the global politics of the trade in hazardous waste in Africa.

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Government Funding Scheme and its impact for Small and Medium Enterprises Development in Nigeria: Bayelsa State in Perspective

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Abstract

This paper investigates government funding scheme and its impact for small and medium enterprises development in Nigeria and the research was confined to Bayelsa state. Governments in the world have set out to solve the plights of the people in different means and with the mind of improving the living standard of the citizens and this brought about the introduction of several funding schemes for sustainable development. This development led to the emergence of small and medium enterprises (SMSs) which do exist in every country. Small and medium enterprises have impacted positively in the development and growth of the economies. The essence of (SMSs) is to increase employment generation, advance socio-economic growth, create mutual linkages with big industries and the improvement of entrepreneurship, improving local savings, bring down the level of poverty in order to firmly hold onto sustainable development. It is with these reasons; governments have brought about the interest of funding and supporting small and medium enterprises programmes in Nigeria and Bayelsa state respectively. The study relied on qualitative approach and relied on content analysis for its findings. The study frames its arguments from the structural-functionalism framework of analysis. It is recommended that; government should encourage and effectively fund small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state; the federal government should enact appropriate policy to strengthen small and medium enterprises in all states.

Keywords: Development; Enterprise; Entrepreneurships; Poverty; SMSs.

Introduction

Governments in alleviating poverty and improving the welfare of its citizens had involved in different forms of funding schemes. As a result of all these interest of improving the standard of living Small and Medium Enterprises emerged and it have greatly contributed to the Nigerian development in terms of employment, growth and development, and marketing of goods and services. The Nigerian government at present is turning to small and medium scale industries and entrepreneurs as a means of developing the economy and solving problems (Latinwo & Ayozie, 2010). A great percentage of all registered companies in Nigeria are constituted by small scale industries and they have been in existence for a long time (p.45).

Some governments have specifically formulated policies to aid the empowering, growth, development and performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, while others have assisted through loans and fiscal incentives (Onugu, 2005). According to Central bank of Nigeria report (2003) SMEs are very important economic catalyst in developing and industrialized countries, in developed countries 98% or more than belong to the small and medium scale sector. In Japan, 80% of industrial labour force is employed by small firms, 50% in Germany and 46% in USA are employed by smaller businesses.

According to the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) developing countries can conquer poverty and inequality by democratizing, deregulating, and liberalizing the integration of global economy. Recent studies have shown that SMEs contribute to over 55% of GDP and over 65% of total employment in high income countries and also that SMEs and informal enterprises account for over 60% of GDP and over 70% of total employment in middle income countries (OECD, 2004). SMEs are important role players in contributing to the transition of agriculture led economies to industrial ones, SMEs help in the absorption of productive resources at all levels of the economy and contribute to the building of flexible economic system in which small and large firms are interlinked (Fida, 2008). Kongolo (2010) posited that SMEs are responsible for the growing forces of the largest growing economy as China in terms of national GDP contribution which amount up to 60% diversification of product, scale of assets and creation of employment.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) pronounce more in the private sector of the Nigeria economy. Almost all of them are starved of funds. The relative importance of the enterprises differs from one type of business to another. The major areas of business enterprises activities are in manufacturing, rendering services and product distribution. Banbeck (1983) as cited in Tambou (2018) posited that more than one-third of all the manufacturing firms in Nigeria employ fewer than five persons or none at all and that close to two-thirds employ fewer than twenty workers. His study on the whole revealed that five per cent of non-farm business of all kinds employs fewer than fifty workers each. The characteristics of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) largely constitute the basis of their problems and special needs that have attracted different authorities and sectors in recent past.

The development of Small Scale Business by the government is a move in the direction to increase economic growth. Ekpeyong and Nyong (1992) suggested that SSBs are organic part of a viable structure for sustainable economic development in less developed countries like Nigeria. They have the tendency to produce greater benefits for the economy than large enterprises because they have higher multiplier effects. Ojo (2009) put forth one of the solutions to the problems of development in Nigeria is the promotion of entrepreneurial development scheme. A veritable way to do this is government promotion of small scale businesses. Entrepreneurship has been identified as vital for the continued vitality of the modern market for more businesses to emerge; hence, competition and economic growth are improved (Klapper and Love, 2011 as cited in Adeusi & Aluko, 2014, p. 86)

With these efforts, the Bayelsa State government in alleviating poverty and to raise a modest businesslike state went further to established the State Micro Finance and Enterprise Development Agency in 2014. The agency was formed to promote small and medium enterprise. Since formation the agency has carried out several empowerment programmes in reducing poverty in the state. The agency with it primary role of improving the wellbeing of the people in the state has embarked on several training programmes of SMEs and also carried out quarterly seminars, workshops for enterprises. More so, as part of the government funding

scheme for small and medium enterprises development in Bayelsa state and in alleviating poverty towards even development, the agency has also partnered with national and international development agencies like: CBN, Bank of Industry, World Bank, India SME Forum in other to foster rapid development to the people.

Conceptual Clarification and Analysis

Small and Medium Enterprises

The unemployment conditions of Nigeria indicate that many individuals who are skilled, capable and willing to be engaged are unemployed or underemployed. The situation is an indication that opportunities are not available. In most countries, job opportunities are created by individuals who establish one form of business or the other as entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs are known to establish business and nurture them to become lofty ventures. In countries such as China, India, Japan, America, Germany and South Africa, entrepreneurs have taken the challenge of industrialization through the creation of small scale business, which help to create job opportunities there by reducing unemployment and to great extend poverty. Udu and Udu (2015, p.213).

Egbo(2009) supported the view that Small Scale enterprises have some common indicators such as the size of capital investment, value of annual turnover and number of paid employees. The need to develop a virile small business enterprise is increasingly being recognized by developing countries. SSEs boost employment as they employ a large number of people per unit of investment capital than the large-scale capital intensive enterprises. For Lubo (2019) small and medium enterprises are firms that are into sales of consumable goods and they are into finished products that help in the growth and development of organisations. Leader (2018) asserts that Small and Medium enterprises entails business ventures that involves few individuals towards the development of their organisation and the country the business exist.

SMEs are non-subsiary, independent firms/organizations which employ fewer numbers of employees. This number varies across countries. According to the European Union (EU), SMEs are categories of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises which employ fewer than 250 persons and which have an annual turnover not exceeding 50 million Euros. In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria in its monetary policies circular No. 22 of 1988 defined SMEs as enterprises which have an annual turnover not exceeding Five Hundred Thousand Naira (N500, 000). For the sake of clarity, the National Policy on Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) has given a clear distinction of enterprises, based on employment and Assets. SMEs are organizations which can best be described through their capital, scope and cost of projects, annual turnover, financial strength and number of employees amongst other things. Such organizations must and can be registered under any part of the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) in order to do business in Nigeria. Nevertheless, it is usually advised that SMEs register under Part B of the CAMA. (Uche, 2018).

Ogechukwu (2006) identifies more general and comprehensive criteria for defining small and medium scale enterprises in different countries to include number of employees, annual turnover, local operations, sales volumes, financial strength, managers and owners autonomy, relatively small markets compared to their industries and capital usually supplied by individual or shareholders. The factors that determine the performance and relevance of the SMEs include policy of the government such as regulation and deregulation, infrastructure, access to external

finance, technology, competition and corruption in the business environment in which they operate (Cited in Clement, 2018).

Small and Medium Enterprises Development and its Characteristics

Ayyagari (2007) in Amagonou (2018) noted that small and medium scale enterprises have been long recognised as an instrument of economic growth and development. The growing recognition of this fact has led the World Bank group on SME's sector to ensure that it is the core element in its strategy to foster economic growth, employment generation and poverty alleviation.

Kurfi (2007) described SME as being characterized by the following:

1. Management. The initiators are managing it and they make decisions without consulting any superior persons(s). The proprietor/owner perform all management functions, with division of labour and functional delegation of responsibilities largely absent (Lewis, 1977).

2. Simple organisation structure. The organisation structure of most SSEs is simple due to small number of employees. The functions of management are common (basic) to all types and sizes, of SSE. However, the conditions under which they are performed vary considerably from one-man "operation" to a "linear organisation structure"

3. High percentage of business failure. Reactions adduced for their failure varies but included management related problems (inexperience, incompetence's, inefficiency, lack of support), individual problem (arrogance, lack of faith, behavioural problem), production problems, financial problems, tax problems and marketing problems. Others are indulgence in fraud and stealing natural calamities, negligence of entrepreneur, government policies and market competition.

4. Lack of specialized managers. There is shortage of specialized managers due to limited opportunities. This results in the owner exercising all levels of management functions.

5. Limited employees. Usually the average number of employees in most SSEs is about 10 persons. Thus the owner/proprietor knows the employees.

5. Low capital base. Most SSEs have difficulties in sourcing funds from stock Exchange and even commercial banks. The costs of sourcing fund may be too exorbitant for management of SSEs.

Olokoyo (1995) asserted that a small business has at least two of the following characteristics:

1. The managers are often the owners
2. An individual owner(s) or a small group furnishes capital
3. The area of operation is local (though market served need not be local)
4. Size within the industry is relatively small (in Egbo, 2009, p. 176)

Government Roles and impact of Funding Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria and Bayelsa State.

Small scale industry plays important and crucial roles in the industrial development of any country (Ahmed, 2006). According to Ojo (2009) small-scale industry has a better prospect for developing domestic economy through the generation of goods and services that propels the economy of Nigeria. The need to focus on small scale industry became important in Nigeria because it was a means of ensuring self-independence, job creation, and import substitution, effective and efficient utilization of local raw materials (Ojo, 2009). Small businesses in Nigeria contribute to employment and a path to entrepreneurship. The focus of small businesses has shifted from providing only social goods but as a vehicle to entrepreneurship (Thurik & Wennekens, 2004) Therefore, it serves as a source of job creation and economic growth. This may well be the reason policy makers in Nigeria pay attention to small businesses in Adisa, et al. (2014, p.5).

With the need to create massive employment and reduce poverty among the people, the Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprise Development Agency hosted the Africa SMS roundtable in 2014, 2018. The agency also gained international recognition by bagging the 2017 World SME Excellence Award at the Habitat Center in New Delhi, India during the 21st International Conference on SME's jointly organized by the World Association for Small and Medium Enterprises and Grant Thornton International in the "Organisation Category". It was observed that the Bayelsa State Micro-finance and Enterprise Development Agency was recognised as a champion in promotion, support and development of the micro, small and medium enterprises ecosystem. They particularly made reference to the agency's efforts at spearheading and attracting over N4 billion, which is equivalent to over \$10 million, to entrepreneurs in the sub-sector and also employing the mind of creating over 7,000 direct and indirect jobs to the people.

The Bayelsa State government established the State Micro Finance and Enterprise Development Agency to midwife and promote the SME in the state, it was established by law in April, 30 2014 since then it has kicked the ground running, and the agency since inception has carried out various schemes giving loans to women cooperatives in the state; and to stimulate the economy also government established the Izon-Ibe Micro-Finance Bank (IMFB) not just in Yenagoa, the state capital but in all the local government areas within the state and this efforts had helped to advance the existence of small and medium enterprises across the state and in relation to Nigeria. The state agency has provided awareness campaign to help the rural people informed on the need of small and medium enterprises development for even development, with this gesture the Bayelsa State Government has key into the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) window for the N2bn Micro Small and Medium Enterprise Development Fund MSMEDF and it has accessed over N1.5bn and Bayelsans are accessing the loan at a single digit interest of two per cent. The agency has opens window with Bank of Industry (BoI) for another N2 billion loan scheme and other international agencies, as well as collaboration with industrial donor agencies. Therefore, the agency is working in line with its mandate to develop and promote the SMEs development sector in the state and that in their vehicle is to stabilise the economy, by creating wealth, jobs, and also birth prosperity and economic development in Bayelsa.

The agency employs the following efforts in supporting small and medium enterprise development: The Bayelsa State government has accessed a loan from CBN at 20 per cent and land to the agency at nine per cent and through the Participating Financial Institutions (PFIs) such as Equator Micro-Finance Bank, Num Micro Finance Bank, Crystabel Micro-Finance

Bank, Izon-Ibe Micro-Finance Bank, the loans are given single digit interest and that in the best any borrower can get and enjoy.

The agency creates a data base and also employed the know your customer approach in giving out the loans to beneficiaries and this aspect greatly help to foster a mutual understanding between the agency and the beneficiaries. The government has also embarked on programmes and policies geared towards the development of this sub-sector. These programmes include micro credit scheme, Bayelsa State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (BY-SEED), co-operative development Credit Scheme among others aimed at developing and enhancing the viability of the SMEs (Atalaowei, 2018,p.87).

Table showing Bayelsa State Micro Finance Banks across the Eight (8) Local Government Areas and the Head Agency of Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprises Development Agency (BYMEDA) and their Purposes and Activities .

Name of Banks /LGA	Activities /Programmes	Kick off / Remark
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Yenagoa	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to help the needy	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start but not fully implemented
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Southern-Ijaw	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start / still at the implementation stage
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Sagbama	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to assist the poor / access loan to start up	25million was given by Bayelsa state government to start/ on going
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Ekeremor	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ programme not complemented
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Ogbia	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ yet to complete the programme
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Brass	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ still at the completion process
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Nembe	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ on going

	assist the poor and access start up capital	
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Kolokuma/Opukoma	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to assist the poor/ access loan	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ implementation process
Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprises Development Agency	Total number of beneficiaries (cooperatives and individuals) over 1500	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Bank of Industry (BIO) gave the agency 4.0 billion Naira to MSMEs/ ongoing

Source: Bayelsa Small and Medium Enterprises Bulletin 2019/2023

For Governor (2019) small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state has helped in the following ways; improving the living standard of people within the state, carrying out small business, keeping the people of the state always busy as regards to their respective businesses, making the government to recognized their business across the state, promoting the people businesses within the local communities.

Challenges Faced by Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria and Bayelsa State

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria has not performed very well. They have contributed just a small percentage of the GDP unlike the other emerging economies in the world. The challenges being faced by our own SMEs are very many. These challenges have been responsible for the slow growth of SMEs in Nigeria. Some of the major challenges include:

Poor managerial skills - From interaction with most SMEs especially the one-man business owners, the common problem is poor leadership. One main reason for this is lack of training and poor capacity building. Most people go into businesses without adequate knowledge or entrepreneurial skills on how to run businesses.

Poor or inadequate infrastructure - The poor state of infrastructure in the country has been a major obstacle to the growth of SMEs. Only few entrepreneurs can survive without power. The epileptic or irregular power supply has contributed significantly to the high cost of doing businesses in the country. Apart from power, lack of good access roads and other social amenities have also hindered the growth of SMEs.

Lack of access to funds- Most SMEs find it difficult to access funds or capital. Most Nigerian banks do not support start-ups and even existing businesses do not have the required collateral. For SMEs that go to non-conventional banks, the high interest rate is always a burden. The issue funding or finance, therefore, is a major challenge for SMEs in Nigeria.

Unfair competition- Most SMEs in Nigeria cannot compete with items or products from other countries especially China and other Asian tigers. The government has also not helped in this area because of dumping of fake and sub-standard goods, and smuggling activities in the

country. When combined with the high cost of production in the country, locally made goods can hardly compete in the area of pricing.

Government Bureaucracy-Another challenge faced by SMEs is bureaucratic bottle neck of various government agencies like CAC, NAFDAC, and Customs etc. For instance, getting NAFDAC approval for food item or drug can take years. In most cases you spend 5 times the official price to facilitate the approval. You can spend as high as N250, 000 to get NAFDAC approval for just one product even after meeting all the specified requirements. Even with the recent government initiatives on ease of doing business, a lot still need to be done to address this issue.

Low Demand-In Nigeria, there is still preference for imported goods over locally made goods. Even government agencies and departments do not patronize our own SMEs. All these combined create marketing problems for SMEs in Nigeria. No wonder many of them closed down within the first few years of operation. No business can survive in the long run without enough sales to cover operational costs

Multiple Taxes and Levies- SMEs are subject to so many taxes and levies from local government to federal government. So many agents are involved in the collection of taxes and levies. This has given room for unauthorized levies and taxes. The impact of this on the operational costs of SMEs cannot be overemphasized (As cited in Ojo, 2017).

The challenges of the SMEs are induced by the operating environment (government policy, globalization effects, financial institutions etc) others are functions of the nature and character of SMEs themselves. (Onugu, 2005 in Atalaowei,2018).

For Leader (2018) the existence of small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state faces many challenges and those problems greatly disturbed the smooth running of their businesses across the state. These challenges include:

- Lack of enough funds to carry out the enterprises - Government finds it difficult to provide enough fund for the Bayelsa small and medium enterprises in other to carry out their business effectively. Lack of adequate funds to a large extend affects the operation of SMEs in Bayelsa state. That is, the state government does not budgeted adequate funds to finance SMEs in the state and this greatly reduce the level of seriousness of the entrepreneurs.
- Government influences on whom to be given the loan- Another challenge is the issue of government overwhelming influence to who will benefit from the loan. That is, government used to select those who will be given the loan to execute the business at their direction. More so, loans are given to those who have direct link with the state government personnel's.
- Lack of training on how to manage the loan- SMEs are not usually trained on how to manage loans and business. Lack of training to a large extend lower their technical know-how in handling their enterprises
- Inability to access the next Tranche Loans from the CBN because of not recovering the 70 percent Returns- Another challenge facing government funding scheme on small and medium enterprises is the issue of accessing another trench of loans from CBN because the government is unable to get returns of 70 per cent returns from the entrepreneurs.

- Political instability – The change of leadership also affected the various enterprises in the state, for instance the entrepreneurs billed to be cleared by the previous government was cancelled by the current administration. Political instability to a large extent causes the smooth running of funding SMEs in the state.

Awini (2019) posited that funding small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state is a difficult task all together. The operation of SMEs in Bayelsa state has the following challenges: lack of adequate funding from the state government to strengthen the smooth running of SMEs, government unfavourable policies on the means of accessing the loans by beneficiaries, poor awareness from the government to the owners of the various enterprises and the general public on the nature of loans and grants taking, problem of favouritism, nepotism and tribalism in giving out the loans, lack of planning on the time frame in disbursing the loans to beneficiaries, inability to train the entrepreneurs on the nature of their various businesses, another challenge is the delay in the implementation of budget, problem of record keeping and the improper management of information relating to grants, loans .

Theoretical Analysis

The framework of analysis used in this paper was the structural-functionalism which emerged through the writings of Herbert Spencer (1820-1930). Spencer believes that different parts within an organ function together in having a whole system to perform effectively and efficiently.

For Izugbara, (2004 ,p. 137) structural –functionalism assumes that social behaviour is structured in the sense that social interactions between members of a society are guided by laws and rules. Values provided the guidelines for social behaviour, and translate more concretely into specific directives in terms of statuses, roles and norms. The structure of society can be seen as the sum-total of normative behaviour. The parts of society; polity, educational system, economic system, religion, health, and familial system are major aspects of social structure. These parts are called social institutions and consist of interconnected, interrelated and interdependent roles. Structural-functionalism maintains that for any social structure to work, the various parts of the structure must fulfil their respective functions. Simply defined, function means effect. Thus the function of the family is the effect it has on society in general. Function also means the contribution of a given institution to the survival of the whole society. Society has certain basic needs which must be met if it is to survive; these are known as functional pre-requisites. It is the function of all these institution to satisfy their functional pre-requisites. From the structural-functionalist perspective, society is regarded as a system; for a system to survive, its constituents must be compatible and stable. This notion connotes value consensus, stability and solidarity.

Okoye (2012) Opines that the basic assumptions and postulations of the structural-functional framework are:

- It takes the society as a single, inter-connected system, each element of which performs a specific function. The basic feature of such a system is the interaction of its components for the maintenance of its equilibrium.
- If society is a system as a whole, it has parts that are interrelated. A social system has a dominant tendency towards stability that is maintained by virtue of built-in-mechanism. If there are deviations or tensions, they are resolved. Thus, change in a social system is not sudden or revolutionary, but gradual and adjustive.

- Underlying the whole social structure are broad aims and principles that are observed by the members of the society (Johari, 2005, p. 86-87).

In applying this theory to this research, it has been observed that government as one of the system consist of many parts/ structures and its numerous tasks in providing developmental needs of different people at different interval. More so, the study revealed that for government to provide funding scheme in reducing poverty to citizens through small and medium enterprises, many agencies like CBN, loan banks, and small and medium enterprises agency in the state would work together for the overall success of the stated goals of the government.

This process greatly account for coordination and implementation of the agency mission and vision in line with the policy of the Bayelsa state government, World bank, CBN, financial loan banks in carry out the small and medium enterprises activities in the state, because if one part fails to deliver, then it would lead to poor implementation of the business activities in the state.

Methodology

The method employed in this research was the qualitative approach and it relied purely on secondary source of data collection and analysis towards the study of government funding scheme for small and medium enterprises development and the population was Nigeria, while the sample sized adopted was the Bayelsa state. The study used purposive sampling technique.

Findings and Conclusion

It was observed in the study that funding small and medium enterprises by the government to a large extent helps in the overall growth and development of the economy. Because the purpose of forming and funding small and medium enterprises is a way of adding to the increased of employment generation, a planned process and advance socio-economic growth, it helps in creating and advancing interdependent linkages with big companies across states , it pave ways to the act of improving the level of entrepreneurship, it also help to create and improve local savings between business owners , it help also to drastically bring down the high level of poverty that will geared towards the drive of sustainable development.

Findings also revealed that funding small and medium enterprises are difficult considering the conditions and criteria used in giving out the loans and the challenges like: government influence in giving out the loans, political instability, government policy, multiple taxes consideration, challenges from the government side to access other tranches, government bureaucracy, poor managerial skills and inadequate communication network. This position was clearly associated by Ojo (2017), Leader (2018), Atalaowei (2018) and Awini(2019) , when they posited that forming and funding small and medium enterprises in Nigeria and especially in Bayelsa state have help in promoting the Bayelsa state small and medium enterprises policy and this also helped to project the state globally.

The paper concludes that, government plays so many roles in funding small and medium enterprises and without government support; it would have being a great threat in doing small business in Bayelsa state. Government support in forming small and medium business has enabled the entrepreneurs to perform better and this has encouraged them to continue with the business. And the continues funding of small and medium enterprise by the government greatly

serve as a catalyst for socio-economic development and its leads to positive impact on the people.

Recommendations

From the above findings, the study recommended the following:

1. There should be special budget provided by the government to fund small and medium enterprises in the state
2. Government should strengthen small and medium enterprises in all states for efficient mutual relationship for the development of various enterprises.
3. Government should revisit the procedures and steps used in accessing the loans, so that it will not be too stringent for entrepreneurs to access such fund.
4. Government should provide a medium of communication to enlighten the public of the importance small and medium enterprises on the use and purpose of the loans
5. The government should have a cordial relationship between the enterprises on training needs, workshops, and lectures on business
6. Government should establish more grants, loans agencies that will specifically fund small and medium enterprises in the state and country.
7. The state government should link up and collaborate with international donors to specifically fund small and medium enterprises in the state.

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An Empirical Analysis of Influence of Social Media on Voters' Choices during the Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Elections in Edo State

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Abstract

Media and communication are essential components of democracy. Media platform can be electronic, visual or social and are drivers of democratic deepening as well as instrumental to grooming anarchy on the other hand. In other words, there have been sustained debates among shades of opinion on the actual role social media play in electoral politics and democratic sustainability. Whereas social media has acted as catalyst for popular mobilization for political engagement it has also created platforms for mobilizing its teeming audience for rebellion and disruption of democratic order at some points such as Nigeria's experience with the infamous EndSars Protests of 2020. The paper explored the Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT) as its theoretical framework. To achieve its set objective, a sample of 240 registered voters was taken using purposive and convenience sampling techniques to draw sample of 40 respondents from six selected local government areas across the three senatorial districts of Edo State for the purpose of questionnaires administration. In addition to the questionnaires administered. The hypothesis of the study was tested using chi square analysis. This paper found that social media platforms were powerful tools in the rapid dissemination of political information throughout the Nigeria's electoral process of 2023 acting as critical conduits for political discourse, enabling the swift transmission of information to a broader audience. The paper further established an association between the frequency of social media interactions involving political contents and voters' preferences during the 2023 presidential elections among the voters in Edo State. This paper recommends that Edo State government should provide incentives towards open and free media access down to the communities' level to increase the prominence of social media as an information-sharing platform so as to engender the possibility of a more inclusive and engaged citizenry and robust voter participation as a remedy to perennial voter apathy. It was concluded that social media did not only booster voter participation but shape electoral outcomes during the 2023 presidential elections and that the influence cut across distinct demographic, social, economic and cultural spectrum.

Keywords: Democracy, Elections, Media, Presidential Elections, Social Media, Voters' choices

Introduction

The use of new social media in politics has continued to grow in many parts of Africa since the 21st century. The role of social media networks such as mobile phones' SMS, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube in deepening the democratization of Nigeria in recent times cannot be overemphasized. For example, 2019 elections witnessed a massive use of mobile phones' SMS, Facebook, Twitter in the general elections in Nigeria. The social media networks like Facebook, Twitter and YouTube are amongst the most visited websites in Nigeria. Due to their participatory, interactive and cost-effective nature, they have become veritable instruments for carrying out election campaigns and other electioneering activities, political engagement and mobilization among others (Oladimeji, 2023).

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, has a complex political history characterized by democratic transitions, military rule, and socioeconomic challenges. The

2023 presidential elections marked another significant milestone in the country's democratic trajectory, as citizens exercised their constitutional rights to elect leaders who will shape the nation's future. While existing research acknowledges the growing role of social media in shaping political outcomes globally, there is a paucity of in-depth studies that specifically investigate its influence on voters' behaviour within specific states in Nigeria. The 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria, spanning federal, state, and local levels, present an opportune moment to explore the dynamics of social media influence on voters' choices in Edo State in particular.

Edo State, known for its politically conscious population and active civic engagement, offers an intriguing setting for examining the interplay between social media engagement and electoral decisions during the last presidential elections held on February 25 2023. Located in the south-south region, Edo State is known for its rich cultural heritage, vibrant politics, and diverse socioeconomic dynamics. The State's political significance, coupled with the spiraling influence of social media formed the base of this study. Edo State's political landscape is characterized by a multi-party system, vibrant political campaigns, and deeply rooted voter loyalties. The state has historically been a political battleground, with frequent shifts in power dynamics between major parties.

Lastly, by scrutinizing the role of social media in shaping voters' choices during the 2023 presidential elections, this research aimed at contributing insights to the broader discourse on the democratization process in Nigeria. Therefore, the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria were held against the backdrop of a nation striving for political and social stability and this study offered a unique opportunity to examine the intricate relationship between influence of social media and voters' choices in Edo State during that election.

It is widely held notion that social media has the possibility of being misused during election because the crowd-source technique it uses are from local communities who are sometimes with partisan interests and biases. Similarly, the platforms are often used to give false information, abuse, and incite violence, thus, social media advantage in promotion of democracy and electoral harmony became more of a contentious discourse. It is in the light of this that the paper investigated the ways and extent to which social media engagement influenced voters' choices during the presidential elections in Edo State. Whereas it is implied that since the ingredients of democracy include freedom of expression, association and freedom of speech as part of fundamental rights entrenched in the 4th Schedule of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria (as amended). Thus, social media engagements should be allowed to fester without hindrance; but such democratic rights should not amount to infringement of the rights of other citizens and political actors within the same democratic space.

Methodology

This paper adopted survey method for data collection and quantitative method of Chi Square in analyzing its findings based on the assessment of the influence of social media engagements on voters' behaviour during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo State. The survey instrument adopted is questionnaire aimed at eliciting relevant information from respondents. In analysing the data collected, quantitative data was presented using descriptive statistics of frequency tables and analysis of the hypothesis was carried out using the inferential statistical method of Chi-square.

Literature Review

According to Mackenzie (1968), elections are ritual of choices and that their binding character are derived from the participation of the individual as a chooser in a social act which offers legitimate authority in the person chosen. Mackenzie recognizes the importance of elections as legitimizing the power of elected individuals. It also enables the citizens to participate in the political affairs in their respective polities by exercising their franchise rights to choose candidates of their choice. One of the possible shortcomings of this definition was that, it failed to acknowledge the tendency at which elections can be marred by irregularities which consequently usurp the power of the individual voters and thus create questions on the legitimacy of elected office holders.

However, Huntington (1991) submitted that, election has great importance in all democratic regimes because it facilitates the competitive choice of principal officers of government and enables political participation of the bulk of the population in any given society. Democratic systems thus have a common institutional core that establishes their identity and from where they derive their legitimacy. Thus, he signifies the fundamental aspects of election which include: one, it allows candidates to compete under different political parties` platforms by wooing voters to vote for them. Second, it also differentiates the type of political systems – democratic or dictatorial regimes and the source of the former legitimacy.

Dahl (1971) defined elections as "polyarchic contests," highlighting their role in determining who governs in a pluralistic society. For him, elections serve as a means of access to political offices and are indicative of a democratic society's distribution of power. H further asserted that elections serve as a means of access to political offices and are indicative of a democratic society's distribution of power. He emphasized the concept of "inclusion" in elections, where all eligible citizens have the opportunity to participate in the decision- making process through regular and free elections. Dahl's definition emphasizes not just the act of voting but also the importance of political equality and genuine competition among various political options.

On social media, Boyd and Ellison (2007) cited in Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023) described it as "a web-based service that allows individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system." This definition emphasizes the interactive nature of social media platforms and their role in enabling users to connect, communicate, and share information within their networks. Typical examples of social media platforms, as defined by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), include applications like Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Flickr, 2go, and Youtube, as well as interactive features on these platforms like retweeting on Twitter, commenting on Facebook, and sharing on Whatsapp. These instruments are referred to as media since they are tools that may also be employed for information storage and transmission. Unlike traditional media such as television and radio, however, most social media platforms allow its users to communicate and share information freely, as well as express their opinions on the World Wide Web at their leisure.

According to Campbell et al (2011) cited in Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023), it is much more about what people do with technology than the technology itself, because rather than simply retrieving information, users are now creating and consuming it, and thus adding value to the websites that allow them to do so. Web 2.0 has progressed from merely retrieving information to interaction, interoperability, and collaboration. Sinclair

and Vogus (2011) described social media as a broad term that describes software tools that create user generated content that can be shared." However, some basic features are required for a website to meet the requirements of a social network website: the site must contain user profiles, content, a method for users to connect with one another and post comments on each other's pages, and join virtual groups based on common interests such as fashion or politics.

Lastly, Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawa (2023) opined that the role of social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp, has grown exponentially in political discourse. These platforms have emerged as powerful tools for political communication, enabling candidates and parties to reach a wide audience instantly. However, the impact of social media on voters' decision-making processes remains relatively unexplored, particularly within the context of states such as Edo. While social media offers numerous benefits, it also introduces challenges and potential negative consequences. The spread of misinformation, echo chambers, and online manipulation are concerns that need to be addressed.

Theoretical Review

This paper predicates on Uses and Gratification theory as the theoretical perspective for analyzing the core objective of the paper. Coined in the early 1940s by Katz and Blumer (1974), the Uses and Gratifications Theory was initially developed as an alternative to the traditional "effects" models of communication. Instead of focusing solely on how media content influences audiences, UGT shifts the focus towards the audience's active role in selecting and interpreting media content based on their psychological and social needs. Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch refined the theory over the years, suggesting that individuals use media to satisfy specific needs, including cognitive, affective, personal integrative, social integrative, and tension release needs (Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawa, 2023).

Applying the Uses and Gratification Theory as theoretical framework. Social media platforms, with their diverse content and interactive features, have provided fertile ground for the application of UGT. Individuals engage with social media for various reasons, aligning with the theory's core principles of seeking specific gratifications. One primary cognitive need met by social media is the acquisition of information. Users turn to platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram to stay informed about current events, industry trends, or even personal updates from friends and family. The abundance of user-generated content empowers individuals to curate their information sources, thus enabling the satisfaction of their cognitive needs (Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawa, 2023).

Empirical Analysis of Influence of Social Media on Voters' Decisions during the Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Elections in Edo State

Table 1: Analysis of Copies of the Questionnaires Retrieved

LGAs	Copies Administered	Copies Retrieved	Percentage
Akoko Edo	40	39	98.0
Esan Central	40	37	92.5
Esan North East	40	37	92.5

Etsako Central	40	38	95.0
Ovia North East	40	38	95.0
Ovia South West	40	37	92.5
Total	240	226	94.2

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 2: Are you familiar with social media?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	226	100%
No	0	0%
No Response	0	0%
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 3: How frequently do you use social media platforms?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Multiple times a day	143	63.3
Once a day	48	21.2
A few times a week	31	13.7
Rarely	4	1.8
Never	0	0
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 4: Which social media platforms do you use?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Facebook	71	31.4
Twitter	46	20.4

Instagram	29	12.8
Whatsapp	56	24.8
Tik Tok	24	10.6
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 5: Were you aware of the 2023 General Elections in Edo State?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	226	100
No	0	0
No Response	0	0
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 6: Did you changed your political preferences or opinions based on content you encountered on social media during the 2023 General Elections campaign?

Responses	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	182	80.5
No	38	16.8
No Response	6	2.7
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

Table 7: Do you believe that social media interactions play a role in shaping the outcome of the 2023 General Elections?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	136	60.2
No	82	36.3
No Response	8	3.5

Total	226	100
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Source: Field study (2024)

Table 8: Have you ever encountered information related to a political candidate or an election on social media that later turned out to be false or misleading?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	136	60.2
No	83	36.7
No Response	7	3.1
Total	226	100

Source: Field study (2024)

H0: There is no association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 general elections in Edo State.

H1: There is association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 general elections in Edo State.

To test hypothesis with chi square analysis, the responses in tables 6 and 7 were used.

Table 9: Computation of Observed Frequencies

Question No	A	B	C	Total
D	182	36	6	226
E	136	82	8	226
Total	318 (70.4%)	120 (26.5%)	14 (3.1%)	452

Table 10: Calculating Expected Counts from Observed Counts

	A	B	C	Total

D	226x318/452=159	226x120/452=60	226x14/452=7	226
E	226x318/452=159	226x120/452=60	226x14/452=7	226
Total	318	120	14	452

Table 11: Computation of Chi square

	<i>Observed Frequency (O)</i>	<i>Expected Frequency (E)</i>	<i>Deviation (O-E)</i>	<i>Deviation Squared (O-E)²</i>	<i>Squared and Weighed (O-E)²/E</i>
A	182	159	23	529	3.3270
B	38	60	-22	484	8.0666
C	6	7	-1	1	0.1424
D	136	159	-23	529	3.3270
E	82	60	22	484	8.0666
F	8	7	1	1	0.1424
Total	452	452			23.072

Calculated $X^2 = 23.072$, $df = K - 1 = 6 - 1 = 5$, Alpha level = 0.05, Table value = 11.070.

In view of the above computation, chi-square calculated is greater than the table value i.e. $23.073 > 11.070$. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1); in other words, there is significant association between the frequency of social media interactions and voters' preferences during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo State.

The period prior to, during and after the 2023 general elections in Nigeria was characterized by social media mobilization for political and election discourses and actions, the impact of social media interactions on voters' attitudes, preferences, and choices takes center stage. The data presented in Table 6 revealed that a substantial 80.3% of respondents claimed to have changed their political preferences or opinions due to content encountered on social media during the 2023 General Elections campaign. This statistical data underscored the significant influence that social media platforms wield over political discourse and voter behaviour. Traditional media channels have long held the power to shape public opinion, but social media's interactive nature allows for personalized content consumption and the potential for more revolutionary response, fast and decisive.

The fact that 16.8% of respondents reported not changing their political preferences or opinions based on social media content suggests that social media's impact is not uniform across all users. This discrepancy could be attributed to factors such as individual exposure to diverse viewpoints, critical thinking skills, and pre-existing political leanings. However, even this subset of voters that remained unchanged may have still been exposed to political content on social media, even if it did not overtly influence their stance. It's

important to consider the role of confirmation bias, where individuals seek out information that aligns with their existing beliefs. This bias could lead to the polarization of opinions as users interact with content that reinforces their viewpoints. Additionally, the 3.3% of respondents who claimed indifference might indicate a level of apathy or scepticism towards the influence of social media on their political attitudes.

Table 7 presented an equally significant finding: 60.2% of respondents believed that social media interactions play a role in shaping the outcome of the 2023 General Elections. This statistic reflects a widespread recognition of social media's potential to sway election results. It suggests that the majority of voters perceive social media as a powerful tool for political engagement and persuasion. Conversely, the 36.3% of respondents who did not believe in the assertion that social media influences election outcomes might hold a more skeptical view of the platform's influence or might have a different understanding of the factors driving electoral results. It's worth considering whether this skepticism stems from concerns over the authenticity of information shared on social media, potential algorithmic biases, or simply a belief in the resilience of traditional campaigning methods. The 1.7% of respondents who provided no answer might signify a lack of awareness about the role of social media in politics, reflecting a need for more comprehensive education and awareness campaigns regarding the influence of online platforms on political processes. But as the responses of the majority of the respondents showed and hypothesis two tested revealed, social media interactions have the potential to impact voters' attitudes, preferences and choices during election.

Exploratory studies done in Nigeria during the 2015 elections indicated that social media played a significant role in turning popular support amongst young voters against the then incumbent federal government. Ijioma and Kogah (2020) argued that the use of social media influence political opinion and voting behaviour and hold that social media, has become vital in Nigerian politics, playing a role in enabling Muhammadu Buhari to win the 2015 Presidential elections. Similarly, Aduloju (2016) noted that youth networks helped to shape the 2015 elections in terms of exposing and preventing insecurity and fraud. By the 2019 presidential election, social media had come of age, and instead of the dominance of that space by young millennial and young adults, we observed that even older people were relying on social media for political information and political debates (Dakuku, 2022).

Thus, as Olowookere and Audu-Bako (2019) aptly captured it, social media is now used to inform and mobilize voters by various stakeholders during elections. It is therefore not surprising that the 2023 General Elections witnessed an unprecedented level of social media engagement and interaction among voters. This digital era has redefined the dynamics of political communication, giving rise to questions about the extent to which these interactions impact voters' attitudes, preferences, and choices. The frequency of social media interactions related to political content has exhibited a positive correlation with substantial changes in voters' attitudes and preferences. Several mechanisms contributed to the association between the frequency of social media interactions related to political content and changes in voters' attitudes during the 2023 presidential elections. Firstly, the sheer volume of political content available on social media platforms provides voters with a diverse range of perspectives, enabling them to engage with narratives that resonate with their existing beliefs or challenge their viewpoints.

The findings from this study provided valuable insights into the complex relationship between social media interactions and voters' attitudes, preferences, and

choices in the context of the 2023 presidential elections. The data underscores the significant influence that social media wields over political discourse and its potential to shape electoral outcomes. Political discussions on social media can quickly escalate and shape public sentiment. During the 2023 Nigeria presidential elections, for instance, hashtags like #NigeriaDecides trended globally on Twitter, reflecting both domestic and international interest in the electoral process. This not only amplified political conversations but also enabled citizens to voice concerns, opinions, and grievances directly to political candidates.

What is evident is that social media played a pivotal role in increased youth participation in the discourse and campaigns. Socio-economic problems, including incessant university strikes and high youth unemployment, apparently contributed to their engagement. The finding of this study also shows that the viral nature of trending topics, hashtags, and posts can amplify certain narratives and influence public discourse. The "bandwagon effect" and "spiral of silence" are psychological phenomena that can contribute to the belief in social media's impact on electoral outcomes. The bandwagon effect suggests that people tend to align with perceived majority opinions, while the spiral of silence theory posits that individuals are more likely to voice their opinions if they believe they align with prevailing societal views. On social media, the prominence of certain political messages can create an illusion of overwhelming consensus, leading users to adopt or reinforce those views.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study embarked on a comprehensive exploration of the symbiotic relationship between social media and voters' choices during the 2023 presidential elections in Edo State, Nigeria. By harnessing the power of agenda-setting theory, social influence theory, and user gratification theory, the study unveiled the transformative impact of social media platforms on the dissemination of political information, the fluidity of voters' attitudes, and the democratization of the electoral process. As Nigeria continues its democratic journey, the insights gleaned from this research underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of the role of social media in shaping political narratives and, consequently, influencing the trajectory of the nation's democracy. The study's findings hold the promise of a more engaged, informed, and participatory electorate, positioning social media as a pivotal player in the ongoing evolution of Nigeria's political landscape. The recommendations of the paper are:

1. There is the need for policymakers to recognize the growing influence of social media in political processes. It is thus important to develop guidelines or regulations that ensure transparency, accuracy, and fairness in political information shared on social media platforms. These regulations could help mitigate the spread of misinformation and ensure a more informed electorate.
2. There should be implementation of media literacy programs at both educational institutions and community levels. These programs can empower voters to critically assess information received from social media, helping them distinguish between reliable sources and misleading content. By fostering media literacy, voters can make more informed decisions.

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Nigeria's Socioeconomic Challenges, Local Government Autonomy As Panacea

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's Local Governments Councils in Nigeria have, for some time, been emasculated by state governors who literally take charge of their finances, impose lackeys as leaders of local government councils in their states either through sham elections or outrightly illegally appointing caretaker administrators. The adverse effect has been far-reaching. Nigeria today is in some turmoil - socially, economically and in terms of insecurity ravaging the country. This research findings indicate that a key factor responsible for the inflation and insecurity in the country is the failure of local government administration in Nigeria. The study employed the qualitative approach where data was collected and analysed from existing literature and official documents and employs the Structural Functionalism theoretical paradigm in its analysis. The study traces the origin and development of local governments in Nigeria and observes the various attempts by several presidents to strengthen that level of government. It's findings indicate that the local government councils is central to improving on the socioeconomic conditions of Nigeria and Nigerians, it has suffered adverse mismanagement chief of which the lack of autonomy and recommends several legal and political measures to be undertaken to strengthen the local government and make Nigeria developed and to a state of human security towards the Overall development of the Nigerian state.

Keywords: Local Government, Federalism, Autonomy, Federal Accounts Allocation Committee (FAAC), Constitution, Federal Character, Supreme Court

INTRODUCTION

Local Government both as a concept and practical reality across states in the international system has been a matter of intense discussions and disputations among Scholars and Researchers, Politicians and Activists alike. This has elicited multifarious conceptualization of local government across nation-states and political systems. Different concepts and meanings have been adduced globally with reference to local government and its status as a tier of government. (Etebom & Junior, 2022). Nigeria, a federal state has a three-tier federal system that is, the Federal Government, thirty-six (36) State Governments and the third is the 774 local government areas. Perennially, Nigeria has faced multifarious socioeconomic, political and security challenges raging from widespread violence such as the Boko haram insurgency, militancy in the Niger Delta region, separatist movements in the South east geopolitical zones, farmers-herders clashes, internecine conflicts (Ife-Modakeke, Aguleri-Umuleri, Ezza-Ezillo), disputed elections and election-related violence to the multi-dimensional poverty in Nigeria. Analysts have averred that the solution to these challenges lie with the enthronement of 'True Federalism' or for some, fiscal federalism, yet others talk about 'restructuring'. No matter the title with which the agitations are centered around or framed, the general idea is that there is something fundamentally wrong with the current federal arrangement. Whether it is the seeming over-reaching powers of the federal government as encapsulated in the Exclusive List of Legislative Powers in the 1999 Constitution, or the emasculation or gradual killing off of the local government areas across the country by State Governors, the cacophony of voices are alleging that government is meeting their yearnings and aspirations. At the root of all the

agitations, it seems is that the people are not feeling the impact of government in their lives in line with the social contract conception of the state. And the fate of local government councils, which by its nature is meant to be the government closest to the grassroots, is one in which election into offices is a sham, where the revenue yielding functions of local government have been hijacked by their respective state governors and the federal allocations to local governments are almost entirely appropriated by the state governors, leave much to be desired.

THE EVOLUTION AND CONTEMPORARY REALITIES OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS IN NIGERIA

Local Government Councils essentially refers to the level of government closest to the citizens at the grassroots level. It is that tier of the three tiers of government in Nigeria (federal, state and local) that administers and superintends over the daily activities of the citizens whether at the urban, semi-urban or rural levels of society. The country, Nigeria is subdivided into 774 parts each of which is a local government. According to Etebom and Junior (2022), the concept of local government was in effect operational before the advent of colonialism in Nigeria. This is so because even the colonialists, particularly in its indirect rule, leveraged on the pre-existing local governance structure to effectively administer the affairs of the country.

According to Agagu (2011), local government administration in Nigeria has experienced difficulties in its evolution till date, from the Regional differences in the pre-colonial epoch, through the various constitutional reforms during the colonial era particularly with respect to Sir Frederick Lord Lugard's experimentation through the different post independence republics and military-guided local government creations. Or from pre-colonial, through colonial, independence and republican epoch's military regimes at intervals, the 1976 local government reforms to the third and fourth republics. The product of these today is that there is no uniform system in place for the administration of local governments councils across the federation with respect to upholding democratic principles, relative autonomy as a constitutional tier of government, good governance, due process, rule of law, as well as free, fair and transparent elections for local councils as conducted by their respective states' Independent Electoral Commissions, despite clear, extant constitutional provisions to that effect (Mimiko, 2011, Etebom & Junior, 2022). Aluko, (2010) avers that despite all the movements in the governance and public sector space at the national and sub national levels , there's been some retrogression at the level of local governments with the debilitating implications of true federalism and it's corollary, democracy eluding those at the grassroots. The added implication is a distinct lack of government presence being felt especially with the provision of socio-economic development and infrastructure at the local level which ought to be a spring board for nationwide security and infrastructural development (Aluko, 2010).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine whether the mode of operation of the State-Local Government Joint Account has retarded Local Government Administration in Nigeria
2. To examine whether the local government administration has been effectively playing statutory socioeconomic and security roles under the practice of our federal system

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the relationship between the management of the Joint State-Local Government account and the poor state of local government administration in Nigeria?

2. How effective have local government administrations been in playing their statutory socioeconomic and security roles under our federal system

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. H_R: There is a significant relationship between the management of the State-Local Government Joint Account and the poor state of local government administration in Nigeria;
2. H_R: Local government administration have been effectively playing their statutory socioeconomic and security roles under the practice of our federal system

METHODOLOGY

This Research will adopt the use of the Survey method of data collection. It will also adopt the use of secondary data for the analysis. This data collected will be reviewed and analyzed to draw conclusions based on the research questions and hypothesis that form the foundations for this research effort. Secondary data collection and analysis involves the review and use of existing data. This achieves a number of goals

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Paleker (2006), there are three broad categories of theories of federalism. These are the classical, origin and functional theories of federalism. He posits that the major proponents of the classical theory of federalism include K C Wheare, A V Dicey, R Garran, Bryce, Moore and Jethrow Brown. Paleker (2006) quoting Garan defined federalism as a type of governmental system whereby sovereignty and the powers of the state is distributed between the federal/central government and the local governments, such that either of them, within their respective spheres is independent of the other. Lord Bryce on his part described the two levels of government as distinct and separate in the performance of their action while comparing the federal system to a factory where a dual set of equipments working with an interplay of their wheels, while each set of machinery carries out its work without impacting adversely on the other. (Paleker, 2006). The renowned Federalism authority, K C Wheare, as quoted by Paleker, (2006) puts the logic advanced by Lord Bryce to task when he avers that 'does a system of government embody predominantly a division of power between general and regional authorities, each of which, in its own sphere, is coordinate with the other and independent of them? If so, the government is federal'. This suggests a two tier government, general and regional, and that is the central theme of the classical school of federalism. The relevance of the classical school of federalism is the fact that it identifies the precondition of distinct and independent levels of government along central and sub-national levels, as a precondition for effective federalism. This provides a form of template for the evaluation of the propriety and functionality of a federal state like Nigeria where for example, a tier of government, ie the local government areas have almost become moribund and ineffective due to the overbearing influence of another level of government. A situation where this occurs, its pertinent to ask if this will not lead to a failure of the system and government's ability to provide the public goods.

LOCAL ADMINISTRATION IN THE PRE-COLONIAL AND COLONIAL ERA

Before the onset of colonialism, Nigeria has been experiencing some form of highly developed local administration from the Old Oyo Empire in the so-called, Western Region, to the Hausa Fulani Empire/ Empire in the Northern Region and to the acephalous kingdoms of the then Eastern Region. Across board, there were established traditional instrumental governance

and administrative apparatus in effect which served as the platform upon which the colonialist launched their native administration. These traditional administrative arrangements had at the helm kings, Emirs, Obas and heads of families, depending on what region one was at, exercising local administrative control over their subjects using the traditional councils in existing communities in pre colonial Nigeria. (Ola & Tonwe, 2009). The nature of these pre-colonial, local councils include a centralised system of government in the Hausa-Fulani Emirate, a decentralised system of government in the Old Oyo Empire and a no clear-cut government system in the acephalous Igbo /Eastern Region. Rather, the latter operated a system that was family compound controlled with every such family compound coming together to constitute the local administrative structure in each community (Etebom, 2022).

The 1914 Amalgamation of the Colony and Protectorates of Northern and Southern Nigeria also led to the introduction of the system of Indirect Rule or Native Administration across Nigeria. This system of Indirect Rule was largely effective and successful in the Hausa-Fulani Emirate in the Northern Region of Nigeria and the Old Oyo Empire, where incidentally, the traditional institutions were very well organized and respected by all. The purposeful adoption of the system of Indirect Rule by the Colonialists was to preserve and leverage the authority of local institutions for convenience and effective administration. The native administration system had evolved over a several decades and the pace of development had intensified as a result of initiatives from varied sources and directions such as the establishment of regional councils and a wide ranging review of the system of native authority by the Sir Arthur Richards Constitution of 1946 (Onajite, 1946). Furthermore, the colonial objective could not be actualised if they upended and replaced the well established system of norms, traditions and native institutions of the colonised people. (Mukoro, 2003).. The McPherson Constitution of 1957 also introduced what it termed the 'local council law' in Nigeria following from the native authority law enacted by the Sir Arthur Richards constitutional reforms of 1954 while the key actors were chief and council, the chief-in-council, the federated native authority county and municipal councils. (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

The Eastern Regional Administration pioneered a paradigm shift in the mechanism for the administration of local government as early as 1950. This was due to the widespread disillusionment with the system of native authority due largely to corruption and the already highlighted acephalous nature and custom of the people. (Agagu, 2008, Etebom and Junior, 2022). There was also a comprehensive overhaul of the local government statutes which were instituted in the 1957 constitution while the Northern Region largely refrained from reviewing the native authority system bequeathed to it by the Colonialists' Indirect Rule since it aligned with its cultural and traditional system of governance that predated the advent of colonialism (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN THE POST COLONIAL ERA

As earlier noted, local government administration under Sir Frederick Lord Lugard's colonial rule was structured under the system of Indirect Rule or Native Administration. And this system experienced varying levels of success across Regions. While it succeeded exceptionally in the Northern Region, largely due to the pre-existing and well established, centralised traditional system of local administration, the situation was radically different in the then Eastern Region as the Indirect Rule administrative mechanism was at variance with the acephalous cultural and traditional system prevalent there. The period after independence, particularly between 1960 and 1976, was central to the development of the local government in Nigeria. During the period of colonialism, the operation and mechanism of local government administration varied

depending on the region in question as local government areas in each region developed at their own pace but what is common to them all, as Etebom and Junior (2022) put it, the history of local governments, post independence is sine qua non to military rule as virtually all developments recorded post independence in local government administration were embarked upon by the military. Furthermore, the reforms that were put in place, the 1966 coup, the hijack literally by the Regional and then State governments, which was succeeded by the rolliut of different systems of local government across the country further diminished the chances of local governments. (Mukoro, 2003; Ola & Tonwe, 2009). In the North for example local government reforms led to the watering down of the powers of the Emir and the scrapping of the divisional administration and the system of native authority. In the South East region, a system was introduced which was aptly tagged "Development Administration" with local administration replaced by local government. Further, in the South West, the Sole Administrators system was introduced and then replaced with the Local Advisory Council which was a 10 member Advisory committee while the District Officers served as chairman. The critical element in these reforms was the transfer of powers, finances and staff from the local government to state ministries. With the increasing number of states from 12 in 1967 to 19 in 1976, there was a marked shortfall in revenue accruing to state governments. To change this, state governments began usurping the powers and functions of local governments that were deemed lucrative / revenue yielding. This resulted in the pauperisation of local governments councils as they were now cash-strapped and increased overbearing influence of state governments. The Local Government Councils were thus unable to embark on their constitutional roles (Egonmwan, 1990; Etebom and Junior, 2022). In a bid to reverse the ugly trend, the federal military administration introduced the Public Service Review Commission. Part of the terms of reference of the commission was the review of the Nigerian Local Government System. Although its recommendations included ways to enhance the state of local government but the white paper wasn't released before a counter coup outside the military regime. It however led to the 1976 Reform Guidelines for Local Governments and the enactment of Local Government Edicts by State Governors.

THE 1976 REFORMS OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

A paradigm shift was recorded in 1976 in local government administration in the country. with the introduction of the 1976 Local Government Reforms. That Reform policy was aptly described by several scholars as a watershed in the evolution of local governments in Nigeria. Etebom & Junior (2022), quoting Ola (1979) stated that it was the first time the federal government was acting directly in a way that unified local government system across the states in the country. It was also the first time the local government was being recognised as a tier of government. This recognition as a tier of government, with defined boundaries, implicit functions and clearly defined provisions of human and material resources to work with, was the distinguishing factors from earlier reforms. The federal government noted then that the local government has had their powers incrementally whittled down by state governors who encroached on the exclusive preserve of local governments in terms of funding and institutions making them moribund, modest progress impossible due to politicking making the people seemingly alienated from government even at the most basic level (Etebom and Junior, 2022). Agagu (2011) adds that the overall objective of the Local Government Reforms was to revive and revitalise the local government system nationwide with regards to the functions, structure, financial resources, relationship with state governments and traditional institutions as well as law enforcement. (Etebom & Junior, 2022).

The reforms clearly listed the local government as a third tier of the Nigerian federation. Section 5 of the reforms provided for the exclusive, concurrent and permissive (residual) lists of legislative powers. These powers and functions were subsequently enshrined in the 4th Schedule of both the 1979 and 1999 constitutions of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Some of the highlights of the 1976 Local Government Reforms included:

A. The introduction of a multipurpose, single tier local government structure for the entire country with the population of each ranging between 150,000 and 800,000 indigenes;

B. Funding was required to be from the federation account via the Federal Accounts Allocation Commission (FAAC) and internally generated revenue (IGR);

C. The relationship between the host state and their respective local government councils was one of superordinate and subordinate status with each state establishing a Ministry of Local Government (and Chieftaincy Affairs);

D. The express exclusion of the traditional institutions from direct involvement in the running of local government councils. The traditional Rulers were only assigned consultative and advisory roles while the local government councils played a direct supervisory role;

E. The 1976 local government reforms also allowed for democratic processes with popular participation in the election of representatives in all the local government councils in the country ie election of chairmen and councillors representing local government areas and wards respectively, were to be by freely contested direct elections. For all the positives highlighted however, there were some notable drawbacks in the 1976 local government reforms. These include

A. Local government administrations were not empowered to maintain law and order. This denied local governments the powers of enforcement of bye-laws and other governmental legislations

B. The universal rule it emplaced which made local government administration uniform across the country meant that the local governments lost their individual identities based on the uniqueness and diversity of their localities (Adeyeye, 2016; Etebom & Junior, 2022).

It's noteworthy that the 1976 Local Government Reforms failed because its policy recommendations could not be fully implemented, particularly the democratisation of local governments institutions. However, while the reforms did not succeed on its own merit, it served as the foundation for the enactment of constitutional provisions on local government in the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, which in turn served as the Grund Norm and elixir for all subsequent constitutional provisions in the 1989 Constitution, 1999 Constitution and all subsequent amendments of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. During the second republic, local government elections were held in December 1976 throughout the country on a zero-party basis. Between then and 1979 when the Shagari administration came on board, the Military regime in power took noteworthy and laudable steps to address all challenges encountered in the process of implementation of the 1976 local government reforms with particular reference to funding and human resources. It's interesting to note that throughout the second republic, 1979 to 1983, local government neither had the benefit of experiencing democratic norms as elections were never held over the period as state governors dissolved the local government administrations across the federation immediately the civilian administration of Shehu Shagari came into office. This was the situation until the military returned on the 31st of December, 1983. During the period under review, rather than hold elections to produce democratically elected leaders for the local government councils, the political class appointed management committees to run the affairs of local government councils. This was rather ironic as the constitutional guaranteed and legal means of choosing leaders for local governments was jettisoned during the supposed civilian political rule. The succeeding administration led by Buhari, upon coming into office in 1983, immediately dissolved the so-called management committees of local government councils across the

federation and set in motion initiatives to revive and revitalise the local government administration which was the constitutional third tier of government in the country. It set the 1976 local government reforms policy as its template, appointed senior civil servants as sole administrators of local government areas and inaugurated a 20-man committee led by Ibrahim Dasuki to review the challenges besetting the local government system in Nigeria. The committee in its report, upheld the 1976 local government reforms and noted that the challenges were rather operational in nature. It highlighted the lack of equitable provision of Social amenities across the wards in each local government as well as the deleterious roles of state governments during the last administration. On a sour note however, the Gen Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida led counter coup d'etat in August, 1985 meant that no white paper was either released nor was the report of the Dasuki committee implemented by the Buhari regime.

THE STATE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS UNDER THE BABANGIDA ADMINISTRATION (1985-1993)

The General Ibrahim Babangida Administration gave another breath of life to local government councils in Nigeria. This it achieved by giving local government administrations all the apparatus and accoutrement of a presidential system of Government to ebb the gradual reversal of local government autonomy. First it directed the abrogation of the Ministry of Local Government (and Chieftaincy Affairs) in all states of the federation - a tool the state governors were using to micromanage the local government areas in their respective states. (Ola, 2009). Secondly unlike the Shagari administration, the Babangida led Administration, conducted local government council elections in all states of the federation on the 12th of December, 1987 on a zero-party basis. Thirdly, the Babangida led Administration scrapped the State - Local Government Joint Account and rather sent the revenue accruing to the respective local governments from the federation account to them directly. It further set up a Civil Service Reforms Committee in 1988 led Prof. Philip Adedotun. Among its terms of reference was to propose an wholesale reform to the Administrative Structure and funding of local government areas across the federation. It also included the professionalisation of the local government work force to enhance productivity and service delivery at that level of government bureaucracy. The white paper of government on this 1988 Reforms indicated that the local government chairman shall be the chief Executive and Chief Accounting Officer of their respective local government councils, (although as the Chief Accounting Officer, he is not allowed to sign official cheques), made provisions for the appointment of Supervisory Councillors by the Chairman who shall form part of the executive council and head various departments within the local government council. The 1988 Local Government Reforms also provided for popularly elected Councillors who shall each come from the different wards in the local government area. The elected Councillors shall make up the legislative arm of the local government. A subsequent election was held in December, 1990 on a partisan basis where again, the elections led to the direct election of Chairmen, Vice Chairman and Councillors of local government councils. (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

A subsequent election was held in December, 1990 on a partisan basis where again, the elections led to the direct election of Chairmen, Vice Chairman and Councillors of local government councils. (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

Major highlights of the 1988 local government reforms Guidelines or the basic constitutional provisions amendment decree of 1991 include:

- A. The Elected Ward Representatives (Councillors) shall constitute the legislative arm of the local government area charged with lawmaking powers, while one of the Councillors shall be elected from amongst themselves, as the leader of the legislative arm of the local government;
- B. The Chairman shall be the Chief Executive officer and a member of the local government council;
- C. Supervisors (or Supervisory Councillors) shall be appointed by the Chairman from within or without the local government council. They shall be in charge of a portfolio or responsible for a department within the council. They shall make up the executive arm of the council along with the chairman and vice chairman of the local government;
- D. A secretary to the local government shall be appointed who will serve as the Chief Administrative Officer of the local government council.

From the foregoing, it's observed that the Executive and Legislative arms of government are properly accounted for in the local government councils. However the Judiciary is not provided for as is the case with other tiers of government that is, the state and federal government.

The 1989 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria further entrenched provisions that addressed the local government Administration on the country. First, it increased the number of local government areas from 307 to 449, states were empowered to create a maximum of seven development areas which correspond historically with the historical and traditional tiers, demographic considerations and administrative experience. A third provision of the 1989 constitution which relates to local government administration was the requirement that the State Auditor General audits the accounts of all local government areas annually and the audited report be presented to the State's House of Assembly. One thing is clear from the foregoing , as Agagu (2011) avers, the Babangida Administration introduced the highest number of local government reforms in the history of Nigeria with the overall objective being to make the local government councils the third tier of government in practice.

A noteworthy last line is that the several reforms introduced by successive military administrations led to the present structure of local governments in Nigeria.

NIGERIA'S LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN THE FOURTH REPUBLIC

During the brief transition government led by Gen Abdus-Salami Anubakar, after the demise of Gen Sani Abacha, local government council elections were held across the country in December, 1998 as a first step in a series of elections that included the state legislative and presidential elections. Their tenure was for three years. Significantly, this local government councils elections were conducted by the national military government. Upon the completion of their three year tenure, in 2002, the general expectation from the populace was that elections would be held especially because the military junta had now handed over to a civilian president and elected state governors and national and state assembly members. The challenge included the fact that the elected leaders were not interested in promoting democratic values at the grassroots and the 1999 constitution did not place much emphasis on the process of election of leaders at the local government level unlike the 1989 constitution which gave much attention to issues relating to local government from process and guidelines for elections to powers of elected local government officials to their tenure in office as well as local government service (Etebom and Junior, 2022; Agagu, 2011! Ola, 2009).

All these were however sadly not enacted as part of provisions of the 1999 constitution (as amended). This is the foundation of the present challenges that the local government councils in Nigeria are grappling with. Etebom and Junior (2022) quoting Ola, 2005 notes that this is a period of uncertainty on the fate and future of local government areas in Nigeria because although the 1999 constitution makes provision for the establishment, structure, funding, structure and composition of local government areas, there's still high level of uncertainty surrounding local governments and their officials. Rather they have been at the mercy of state governors who whimsically dissolve, suspend and upend elected local government council officials and often impose caretaker committees or hold sham elections which put lackeys at the helm of local government councils. (Agagu, 2011; Etebom and Junior, 2022).

THE FATE OF LOCAL COUNCILS IN NIGERIA TODAY

Etebom and Junior, (2022) unequivocally assert that the fate of local government councils as the third tier of government in Nigeria today is at variance with the extent provisions on local governments in the 1999 constitution (as amended) as well as the 1976 Local Government Reforms which among others made provisions for a universally consistent structure for local government councils across the country with democratically elected officials. The challenge however which is being exploited by state governments is the ambiguity surrounding the place of states houses of assembly and their respective governors . The reality is that most of the statutory functions of the local government councils have been literally hijacked by state governments. According to Etebom and Junior, 2022; Adeyeye, 2016; Aghayere, 2010 and Ola & Tonwe, 2009; the functions of the local governments have been delineated into three broad categories viz the general, concurrent and exclusive functions.

1. The general functions of the local government include the discharge of duties imposed on it by law, assisting in maintaining law and order as well as good governance within its defined boundaries, prevent lawbreakers from committing offences and reporting any act or conduct that is capable of breaching public peace to the appropriate legal cum judicial authority.

2. The second category of duties enshrined in the constitution to be carried out by the local government administration are the exclusive functions ie functions that they can exclusively legislate upon by way of bye-laws. These include: the establishment, control and management of vehicle parks and markets; sanitation, refuse and sewage disposal as well as sanitary inspections; establishment, control and regulation of abattoirs; registration of births, deaths and weddings; establishment, management and control of cemeteries and mortuaries; provision and maintenance of public conveniences; provision and maintenance of recreational and community centres; establishment and management of parks, gardens and open spaces. The list of exclusive functions further include the licencing of vehicles like bicycles and trucks; licencing, regulation and supervision of eateries and bakeries; control and regulation of advertisement services and use of loud speakers in and around public buildings and spaces; naming or numbering of roads and streets, as well as buildings and plots of lands; collection of vehicular parking fees; regulation and collection of property taxes and sundry designated revenues sources and rates including radio and television licences; as well as regulation of traffic and parking.

3. The third category of local government functions as earlier noted is the concurrent list of duties. The concurrent functions refer to those roles that the state governments as well as other agencies and organisations are empowered to carry out or partake in the performance of these functions especially where the local government councils as constituted do not have the capacity to perform such functions. These include provision of primary health care facilities

like maternity and communicable diseases clinics, ambulances services, primary educational institutions / schools, development of agricultural and natural resources like forestry, public enlightenment and information dissemination, water supply, grading and tarring of trunk C roads, street lights and drainages, promoting local arts and culture, water supply, pollution control prevention of street begging, prostitution and destitutes. The concurrent list of functions also include establishment of orphanage homes and homes for the destitute, provision of public utilities like water boards for water supply, development of mass / public housing programmes, town planning, control of soil erosion among others.

CHALLENGES FACED BY LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS UNDER THE CURRENT DISPENSATION

The local government councils in Nigeria are in this fourth republic indeed face a number of challenges. These range from lack of democracy. By this it is meant that state governments do not usually conduct elections for local governments in majority of the states. And in the few where elections are held, it is marred by either rigging of elections or imposition of candidates to appointment of sole administrators. This is at variance with the clear provisions of the 1999 constitution which stipulates that the system of local government run by democratically elected local government councils is guaranteed under the constitution. Furthermore, the other major challenge besetting our local government councils in Nigeria today is the lack of autonomy despite being a constitutional tier of government. Although the 1999 constitution makes provision for the independence of local government councils, the situation local governments face across the states is more or less the whimsical dispositions of their respective state governors. This is perhaps the greatest impediment impacting adversely on the deepening of democratic values at the grassroots particularly with regards to citizens' participation, popular representation, efficient and effective service delivery, and good governance. (Etebom, 2022). We cannot envisage local government autonomy where the citizens are not allowed to elect their leaders themselves or funds accruing to local governments are illegally taken over by state governments.

CONCLUSION

This paper dealt with the challenges besetting the third tier of government in Nigeria and its inability to deliver on its constitutional roles. The panacea therefore is in granting the local government full and unencumbered autonomy in public policy making and financial autonomy. In addressing these issues, this paper highlighted the historical, underlying issues besetting the local government administration in the country as the level of government closest to the populace. These challenges, the paper notes have hampered the ability of local governments in discharging their constitutional roles as captured in the residual lists of legislative powers enshrined in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). This paper therefore calls for the full and immediate implementation of the recent Supreme Court ruling on full autonomy for local governments in Nigeria as it is not just now a constitutional matter but now also a final adjudication of the Judicial branch of government. This paper concludes that this will lead to the amelioration of the immense socio-economic challenges the country is facing. And recommends that there should be prosecution of state actors who act ultra vires so that local governments in Nigeria can experience a new lease of life so they can play their statutory roles and meeting their obligations towards enhancing sustainable, socio-economic development across the country.

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Corporate Governance and Financial Performance Of Deposit Money Banks In Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examine the impact of corporate governance and financial performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria from 2012-2022. The study utilized secondary data obtained from CBN annual statistical bulletin. Corporate governance was proxied by board composition (BC) audit committee independence (ACI), and board gender diversity (BGD), while financial performance (DMBs) was proxied by Earnings per Share (EPS). The ex-post facto research design was adopted and the data were analyzed using panel regression analysis methods using Stata 14. The study found that ACI has an insignificant relationship with EPS, BS has a significant negative relationship with EPS, BGD has a significant positive relationship with EPS.. The study concludes that corporate governance has both significant benefits and drawbacks on the performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria. The study recommends that policy makers may need to conduct thorough review of existing regulations governing board composition, particularly focusing on BS and asses their impact on financial performance, the review should consider both the specific challenges faced by DMBs in Nigeria and international best practices. Policies should capture gender diversity on corporate boards and should also consider setting realistic but aspirational targets for gender representation so as to foster transparency and accountability

1. Introduction.

Corporate governance is the connection between the framework that comprises the rules, guidelines, and regulations that dictate how businesses, institutions, and organizations are managed. Therefore, its main goal is to fairly distribute the organization's profits to all of its stakeholders—the government, the host community, managers, shareholders, suppliers, and customers—while maintaining a single vision. Experienced corporate governance involves the government of stakeholders to the management of the corporate and welfare of the host communities in its schedule of operations. It also entails measures put in place to ensure that there is fairness and transparency in business operations.

However, given its mandate to provide a financial boulevard between the supply and demand sides globally, where it collects customer deposits and offers financial intermediation services, including loans and other financial products, and relays these to the effective investment segment of the economy, the bank intermediaries significantly contribute to the Nigeria's economic advancement. This makes it more imperative to have a system to ensure that the operations of deposit-taking institutions are above board and instill stability in the polity. According to Adegbelemi et al, (2013), Nigeria's banking industry has grown over the years in a manner that are measured in based on size, ownership pattern, coverage and intensity of

activities and consolidation strategies. Because of the aforementioned elements, which include but are not limited to regulatory frameworks, financial sector deregulation, globalization skirmishes, and technological innovation. The goal of all of these initiatives was to enhance the Nigerian banks' operational procedures in order to raise their level of performance.

As it is well known, across the years, service organizations, particularly those in the banking sector are highly prone to unethical practices, fraud and their eventual demise. One such case is COVID 19, which in 2020 precipitated the global financial crisis, as well as other scandals from recent decades. One word, corporate governance, best describes the primary reason for these financial scams and company collapses (CG). The analysis of the circumstances and events that led to the scandals has met with varying degrees of success and, in certain cases, produced no beneficial outcomes due to the broad and convoluted nature of the weak CG structure. Examining how these elements impact corporate governance procedures is necessary in order to assess how corporate governance enhances performance, risk management, and overall stability of DMBs in Nigeria.

1.2 Statements of the Problem

Irrespective of the numerous reform initiatives and regulatory reforms by the regulator, DMBs in Nigeria are still befuddled and struggling with business leadership issues like compliance, ethics and integrity, and disclosure concerns. This has led to doubts on the effectiveness of the business leadership systems put in place to improve accountability, transparency, and sound management in deposit-taking institutions.

In addition to the above, the effectiveness of the leadership structures that steer the corporate direction of institutions is a thing of persistent weariness to the various stakeholder groups in the sector. This is because, as evidenced by the recent acquisition of several Nigerian banks by other financial organizations, a large number of firms and occasionally even banks have been closing in recent times. This questions whether corporate governance is being applied in this industry or whether corporate governance standards aren't robust and efficient enough to account for the effects of moral hazard as a result of these failings.

Based on the foregoing, this study evaluate if the audit committee is an independent composition of the board, and gender diversity affects the performance of deposit taking institutions in Nigeria.

2.0 Concept of Corporate Governance and Mechanisms

Adesu et al, (2017) and Ehiedu, (2022) indicated that the rules and charges, which encompasses the management of an organization, is called corporate governance. According to Ehiedu and Ogbeta, (2014) positive statement of corporate governance is an institutional structure to regulate excess of managers and executives.

(Anastasia and Olga, (2012) defined corporate governance as a compendium of laws that guide the operations of corporations. This means that, at its core, corporate governance essentially fulfills the balancing of interests of the various stakeholders within a company. It represents an established framework that gives direction on behavioural strategies, procedures, policies, and decisions that define corporal conduct (Muhammad & Fahmida, 2017). These rules could comprise of written and unwritten agreements involving the various stakeholder groups and their interests. The idea between all these is to ensure the managers of the corporation are fair and their operations are done with utmost good faith (Toyin & Leye, 2012). Lastly, a check and balance strategy is implemented using information, control, and suitable control methods (Michael, 2016).

Gender Diversity

Despite the general consensus that gender diversity is advantageous for the corporate sector, very few women hold high positions (Salma & Cesario, 2010). In explaining how gender diversity on boards fosters creativity and innovation by bringing a wealth of complementary experiences, expertise, and abilities, Salama and Cesario, (2016) posits that the performance of

many businesses are attributed to the presence of female managers occupying board level positions. Decaerma and Sori, (2012) affirmed this position by stating that there is a significant and favorable correlation between gender diversity and organizational effectiveness.

Board Composition

This comprises of the number of persons in the board of the company. It is belief that the larger the board, the more transparent and forthright their operations would be. According to Beasley, (2015), unethical practices with respect to the preparation of the statement of financial position would be more pronounced when the density of the board is sparse. This means that when the density is broad, it tends to cause a decline unethical practices and corruption tendencies (Firth et al, (2012); Beekes et al, (2014). The propensity to fabricate financial records and earnings lessens when the board is composed of people with impeccable character and do not have direct ties or cannot be easily influenced by the managers of the firm. This means that external professions should have a considerable slot at the board. Records indicate that this strengthens the overall health and the financial prospects of the corporation in countries like the United States and New Zealand (Antti & Jensen, 2013).

Audit Committee

"Where is the place of power when there is no supervision, when there is no accountability, when there is no control, and when there is no supervision?" asked (Normanton, 2013). Normanton explained that the requirement for supervision ensures utmost good faith. This well-known statement encapsulates the idea that an audit is an essential independent proof of corporate officers' accountability to the body that decide the strategic direction for the firm and all the stakeholders especially when there is dilution of ownership.

The audit committee plays an essential role in ensuring probity of the records of cash inflows and outflows of a corporation. This makes it more imperative to ensure that the independence of the committee. In Nigeria, the CBN in 2006 set the legal framework "financial reporting, risk management, accounting and auditing, industry transparency, and standards for the appointment, structure, and composition of the Board of Directors" for financial institutions under its regulatory purview.

Financial Performance

The ability of a firm to optimize it inflows above its cost of doing business in relation to its capital base determines the financial health of that firm. A stable and resilient financial system is a product of the financial health of the corporation. When a firm's earnings exceed its expenses, the firm is said to be profitable (Onore & Kusa, 2013). They added that a company's ability to turn its commercial operations into profits is determined by its rate of return.

In the deposit banking industry, an organization's profitability is primarily determined by its return on assets (ROA), which measures its ability to generate income through the optimization of assets relative to equity, and its profit after tax (PAT), which is the amount left over after all tax-related expenses have been subtracted Gül et al, (2011). Some DMBs appear to be in financial difficulties, while others are doing well in the business.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

To comprehend the connections between the various facets of corporate governance, there are numerous theories available. However, the theoretical examination in this article is centered on these ideas because of the doctrines of these theories, which are based on business, psychology, sociology, and economics and are currently being used in Nigerian banks.

Stakeholder Theory

The shareholder hypothesis, proposed by (Friedman, 1970), provides theoretical underpinning for the study. It highlights that the interests of shareholders should come first and discusses how industry leaders should behave in professional settings.

This theory holds that the company's only goal is to serve the wants and interests of business owners; in other words, its goal is to maximize shareholder wealth. According to this idea, the

market value (also known as shareholder value) of the corporation serves as the sole yardstick for evaluating performance. According to (Basman, 2017), corporations exist to maximize shareholder wealth. Making the most money possible for shareholders guarantees that they receive fair compensation for the risks taken. Dividends and, more significantly, the capital growth of investors' investments make up shareholder wealth.

This hypothesis has been criticized for being extremely misleading in stating that shareholders are the only remaining claimants of the business, particularly in situations where the business is not insolvent. The shareholder company's position is not more susceptible than that of other stakeholder groups because of its private investment. When a firm performs poorly, as well as when suppliers and other stakeholders play a part in its success, employees suffer as well. The crux of this is that the firm should prioritize the interests of shareholders to the greatest extent feasible (Freeman, 2014). Because corporations are so big and have such a broad impact on society, (Solomon, 2012) suggested that the foundation of stakeholder theory should be accountability, not just to shareholders but too many sections of society as well.

Agency Theory

The study of Corporate Governance originated with (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), agency theory. Theoretically, the principle designates a representative to do the task or assigns it to them. In this type of collaboration, one party acts on behalf of the other. The traditional AT (Uwuigbe, 2011); Sami, et al, (2009) states that issues emerge when principals' and agents' interests don't always align.

The objectives of an organization manager frequently conflict with those of the business's real owners. Consequently, business owners ought to tie their monetary interests to the managers of the company's salary and other kinds of compensation (Vo & Phan, 2013). Fikri is in favor of the fresh board entrants, the employment of alluring compensation schemes, and the board's ongoing reporting, assessment, and adoption of the policies in place. The results of this distinction may be explained by other studies or by the use of different organizational governance indicators, despite the fact that certain studies indicate that excellent governance can save corporate costs and boost income for business owners Sami et al, (2009).

2.4 Empirical Literature

Anderson et al, (2004), "The larger the board of directors, the smaller the board of directors will be due to the fact that managers have the ability to monitor the low cost of debt, because creditors believe that such companies are more effective observers of the accounting process." The argument put up by Adeusi et al, (2013) that "increasing the size of the board of directors improves the performance of banks" is supported by these findings. (Kajola, 2008) used 2000 to 2006 data to posit that the magnitude of board diversity on the ROA of DMBs is not significant. In buttressing this, (Kajola, 2008) further concluded that "the performance of banks tends to deteriorate if there are more external managers."

Conversely, (Prakash & Martin, 2001) held that there is the likelihood increase in returns when there is diversity in the composition of the board. Similar studies concluded in like manner (Bawa & Lubabah, 2013; Kamau, 2018).

Ajola et al, (2012) used OLS estimator to examine the effect of business leadership on the returns of banks in Nigeria and found that the number of participants in the board significantly impedes the returns of DMBs in Nigeria. Similar studies further found that increase the participants in the board causes a decline or impedes the returns accruable to DMBs (Akpan & Roman, 2012; Asuagwu, 2013).

Sani et al, (2019) study analyzed panel data of banks and found that the leadership dynamics and composition of the board is a significant determinant of the returns accruing to deposit-taking institutions in Nigeria. A similar study by Ahmed et al, (2019) analyzed data from 2014 to 2016 to determine the effect of business and financial knowledge affects ROA of 14 DMBs in the country. The study alludes that the variables are negatively related.

Hawkar et al, (2021) examined the role of the board ownership, board independence, and board of directors on ROA of banks in Iraq. The data support the notion that board ownership and independence has a progressive effect on ROA while board of directors impedes the growth rate of ROA. The study held that to guarantee a congruence of interests between Decemblers and shareholders, management should be more independent from non-executive directors.

Okoye et al, (2020) used GMM to investigate the relationship between bank profitability and governance procedures in Nigeria. The results show that BS, management shares, and fs would have a major role on the returns of DMBs in Nigeria. Additionally, the study demonstrates that lagrone has a significant impact on output. It conclusion that corporate FP is significantly impacted by corporate governance. Reducing rivalry in the boardroom is suggested by maintaining an optimal BS.

(Özili, 2021). An overview of Nigerian corporate governance research highlights issues and new advances in the literature while offering some ideas for further study possibilities. The results show that board of directors play a significant role in giving strategic leadership and future prospects of corporation in Nigeria.

Eni-Egwu et al, (2022) found that whereas the number of the participants at the board and ACI impedes ROA and ROE, the proportion of males and females and the board committee have a positive relationship with corporate ROA and ROE. According to the report, businesses want to lower Bs to within 10 points, and they also want to cut Bs to external (or non-executive) directors.

(Okolie & Uwejevan, 2022), used data from 2011 to 2020 to conclude that board membership, independence, and shareholding of the Board and Audit Committee had a significant impact on ROA in Nigeria. On the other hand, it appears that the Nigerian conglomerate's fp had little effect across the board.

(Benvolio & Ironkwe, 2022) looked into DMBs in Nigeria in connection to BC. The data from 2011 to 2021 was compiled using the yearly financial reports of all 14 DMBs in Nigeria. The study observed that BC significantly affects a company's FP, contributing around 85.1% of the total variation in a company's market value.

3.0 Methodology

The study followed the Kerlinger, (1970), who claimed that post investigations are conducted following an incident. Studies, also known as examination trials, are a kind of research where trials are started after an incident has happened without the involvement of researchers (Salkind, 2010). The study employed a post-mortem research technique due to the aforementioned reason. As of December 31, 2022, the population is made up of all 24 DMBs. However, data spanning 2013 to 2022 was collated from the records of only twelve (12) DMBs in Nigeria.

Model Specification

The study adopted the econometric model of Abdulazeez et al, (2016) to make its contributions on the discourse of corporate leadership and the earnings per shares (EPS) of DMBs in Nigeria.

$$EPS_{it} = \partial_0 + \partial_1 ACIND_{it} + \partial_2 BSIZE_{it} + \partial_3 BGDIV_{it} + \partial_4 FSIZE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

- EPS = Earnings Per Share
- ACIND = Audit Committee Independence
- BSIZE = Board Size
- BGDIV = Board Gender Diversity

Table 3.1: Operationalization of Variables

Control Variable

Variable Name	Measurement	Sources
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Earnings per Share	(In per share basis) EPS is calculated as net income after tax divided by paid-in shares	Reguera-Alvarado, De Fuentes, and Laffarga, (2017).
Board Gender Diversity	The BGDIV is calculated as the ratio of female managers to the size of the overall board of directors.	Chapple and Humphrey (2014).
Board Size	The size of the Board of Directors is calculated as the total number of all directors of the bank, including the Chairman plus the Vice-Chairman plus the CEO / General Manager In addition, Executive Directors + Independent directors, except non-executive directors or bank secretaries	Shittu, Ahmad and Ishak, (2016).
Audit Committee Independence	(in percentages) The independence of the Audit Committee is calculated as the ratio of the non-board members of the Audit Committee to the size of the Audit Committee	Modum, Ugwoke and Onyeonu, (2013).
Firm Size	The size of the business is calculated as the natural logarithm of the total assets of the bank.	Oktaviani, (2020).

= Firm Size

∂_0 = Model intercept

$\partial_1, \dots, \partial_3$ = Coefficient to be estimated, where $\partial_1, \dots, \partial_3 > 0$

i_t = Cross Section of listed companies with time variant

$\sum i_t$ = stochastic error term

Authors Compilation 2024

4.0 Discussion of Results

This study looks into the connection between Nigerian deposit money banks' financial performance from 2012 to December 2022 and their corporate governance features. This

section specifically offers descriptive statistics, tests for data normality, regression analysis, correlation analysis, and hypothesis testing.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Descriptive statistics are examined in this study for both the explanatory and consequential variables of interest. Every variable is examined in light of the maximum, minimum, standard deviation, and average values.

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics for the study.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
eps	120	1.959167	2.111395	-1.28	7.79
bgdiv	120	18.83142	10.78104	0	50
bsize	120	13.63333	3.217425	6	21
acind	120	55.378	15.75559	40	100
fsize	120	9.23975	.4119078	8.19	10.07

Source: Authors' Computation

According to table 4.1 descriptive statistics results, earnings per share have a mean value of 1.95 and a standard deviation value of 2.11, with lowest and highest values of -1.28 and 7.79, respectively. Data on gender diversity on the board shows a maximum value of 50 for the studied period, with mean and standard deviation values of 18.83 and 10.78, respectively. The audit committee independence variable showed a mean value of 55.38 with the greatest value reaching 100 during the period under examination, while the board size variable showed an average value of 13.63 with the largest size peaking at 21 during the review period. The average firm size in this study is 9.24, with minimum and maximum values recorded throughout the study period of 8.19 and 10.07, respectively.

4.1.2 Data Normality Test

In particular, if the probability values of the z statistics (Prob > z) are more than 0.05 when testing for normality, it suggests that the data are normally distributed. In contrast, non-normality of the data is indicated when the probability values of the z statistics (Prob > z) are less than 0.05.

Table 4.2

Data Normality Test Result

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
eps	120	0.84409	15.002	6.068	0.00000
bgdiv	120	0.98355	1.583	1.029	0.15172
bsize	120	0.99287	0.686	-0.844	0.80068
acind	120	0.78906	20.298	6.745	0.00000
fsize	120	0.98604	1.343	0.661	0.25446

Source: Authors' Computation

The Shapiro-Wilk normality test result for the data used in this investigation is displayed in Table 4.2. As the probability of the z-statistics are significant at the 1% level, it is noted that the dependent variable of earnings per share (Z=6.068; Prob>Z=0.00000) is not normally distributed. Given that the probability of the z-statistics is significant at the 1% level, the table

indicates that the audit committee independence ($Z=6.745$ Prob> $Z=0.00000$) is not normally distributed in the case of the independent variables. Nevertheless, the results show that the variables of board gender diversity, board size, and firm size are statistically negligible ($Z=1.029$; Prob> $Z=0.15172$, $Z=-0.844$; Prob> $Z=0.80068$, and $Z=0.661$; Prob> $Z=0.25446$). The interpretation is in line with Jarque and Bera's (1987) theories.

4.1.3 Correlation Analysis

Since several of the variables used in this investigation displayed a pattern consistent with a normal distribution, the Spearman rank correlation was utilized. Table 4.3 displays the results obtained from the Spearman correlation.

Table 4.3 Correlation Analysis Result

	eps	bgdiv	bsize	acind	fsize
eps	1.0000				
bgdiv	0.2288	1.0000			
bsize	0.0165	0.1070	1.0000		
acind	0.0749	0.0933	-0.2116	1.0000	
fsize	0.7995	0.1561	0.1307	0.1317	1.0000

Source: Authors' Computation

There is a positive correlation between earnings per share (0.2288) and the independent variable of board gender diversity during the study period, according to the results of the Spearman rank correlation between the independent and dependent variables, which are displayed in table 4.3. During the study period, there was a negative correlation found between the independent variable of audit committee independence and board size (-0.2116). During the study period, there was a positive correlation observed between board size (0.0165) and the dependent variable, earnings per share. Lastly, for the study period, there is a positive correlation between audit committee independence (0.0749) and the dependent variable. Given that the positive and negative correlations are weak (less than 0.80), multicollinearity between the variables may not be expected.

Table 4.4 Earnings Per Share Regression Result

Variables	Board gender Diversity	Board Size	Audit Committee Independence	Firm Size	Constant
Fixed Effect Model					
Coefficient	-0.013	-0.049	-0.008	4.309	-36.498
t_Statistics	(-1.13)	(-1.08)	(-1.20)	(7.64)	(-7.43)
Probability_t	{0.262}	{0.284}	{0.233}	{0.000} ***	{0.000} ***
No. of Obs = 120		Prob. F statistics = 0.0000		R ² = 0.4070	
Random Effect Model					
Coefficient	0.033	-0.137	-0.011	3.490	-28.447
z_Statistics	(2.52)	(-3.02)	(-1.17)	(9.74)	(-9.05)
Probability_z	{0.013} **	{0.003} **	{0.244}	{0.000} ***	{0.000} ***
No. of Obs = 120		Prob. Wald Chi ² = 0.0000		R ²	Mean VIF = 1.50
= 0.5027					
Hausman = 0.4082					

Note: t & z -statistics and respective probabilities are represented in () and { }

Where: ** represents 5% & *** represent 1% level of statistical significance

Source: Authors' Computations

The researcher specifically adheres to Gujarati (2004), who states that in order to prove the lack of multicollinearity, the mean F must be smaller than 10. But the outcome revealed a mean of 1.50, which is within the 10-point cut off. A detailed analysis of the data from the effects models (fixed and random) in Table 4.4 reveals that both models of interest indicate suitability with respect to the dependent variable of earnings per share over the study period. Nonetheless, given the hausman test's p -value is negligible at both the 1% and 5% levels, a glance at its p -value (0.4082) suggests acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that, statistically speaking, the random effect findings are typically more appealing than the fixed effect results. Additionally, the wald statistics (29.06) and its corresponding probability value (0.0000) indicate the random effect model's goodness of fit, and they both show a 1% statistically significant level, indicating that the model as a whole is significantly fit and suitable for use in policy interpretation and analysis. With a r^2 value of 0.5027, the independent and control variables in the model account for roughly 50% of the variation in the dependent variable. As a result, this study uses the random effect model to explain the data and recommend policies.

5.1 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study investigating the relationship between listed deposit money banks in Nigeria's financial performance and corporate governance from 2012 to 2022. Board size, gender diversity on the board, and audit committee independence are the independent variables of interest used in this study. Corresponding with the body of existing literature. Firm size was chosen by the study to be a control variable in the given model. In particular, pre regression analysis—which encompasses examination of correlation, normalcy of data, and descriptive statistics—was carried out. The hausman specification test was used to select the most appropriate model, and the results indicated that the random effect model was the most appropriate. As a result, this model was used to test the study's hypotheses. Panel data's nature necessitated panel regression analysis that included both fixed and random effects models. In specifically, the panel regression analysis's result revealed that: For the time under review, there was no statistically significant correlation found between the independence of the audit committee and the company performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. During the review period, there was a statistically significant negative correlation between board size and the firm performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria and during the study period, listed deposit money banks in Nigeria showed a statistically significant positive correlation between board gender diversity and business performance will significantly increase. In light of the findings of our investigation, the study concluded that corporate governance has a considerable positive and negative impact on the financial performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money institutions. Therefore, the study recommends the following

1. Policymakers should examine and possibly improve the current rules or guidelines regarding board composition in the banking industry, given the regression result showing that a larger board significantly lowers earnings per share (EPS) in listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. In light of this, legislators might need to thoroughly examine the laws already in place governing board composition, paying special attention to board size, and determine how they affect the company's financial success. This evaluation ought to take into account both global best practices and the unique difficulties that DMBs in Nigeria encounter.
2. One important advice for policymakers is to put rules in place that would foster gender diversity on corporate boards, given the positive correlation that has been observed between an increase in board gender diversity and an increase in earnings per share in listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Notably, laws mandating businesses, particularly deposit money banks, to

reveal their gender diversity data can be used to accomplish this purpose. In addition, aspirational yet attainable goals for gender representation should be set by these rules in order to promote accountability and transparency.

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Poverty And Security Situation In Nigeria: An Evaluatory Study

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Abstract

Nigeria is a country endowed with technocrats, intellectuals, and copious amounts of mineral resources. But the vast majority of its people live in extreme poverty due to leadership and insecurity. Poverty has a negative impact on society and even on an individual level; a poor man is a problem for society and even for himself; he is never productive, always angry, and turns to militia activities for support. Poverty is a major contributing factor to insecurity in Nigeria, which this study looks at the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Using a descriptive method and non-probabilistic sampling techniques. Data were gathered via a survey of six hundred (600) respondents. The study's foundation is derived from the frustration-aggression theory. With the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21, the data were analyzed using correlation and linear regression analysis. Among other findings, the study demonstrated that poverty has a positive and significant relationship ($r = 0.783$) with insecurity in Nigeria. As expected, it also showed that poverty has a positive and statistically significant impact ($r^2 = 0.716$) on insecurity in Nigeria. Consequently, the study suggests that the Nigerian government, at all levels, should prioritize the welfare of the people by addressing their basic needs.

Keywords: Nigeria, Security, Insecurity, Poverty, Frustration, Aggression

Introduction

Nigeria is the biggest producer of oil in Africa and the sixth oil producer in the world but despite its vast resources, it ranks among the poorest countries in the world. A recent World Bank (2010) report released at a United Nations summit rated her as second poorest country in

the world with most Nigerians living below poverty line. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS 2012) about 60.9% of Nigerians in 2010 were living in 'absolute poverty'. In 2011, the figure rose slightly to 61.9% and in BBC news (2012), the number of Nigerians living in poverty was put at 61%. The highest poverty rates are recorded in the North-West and North-East geopolitical zones with a poverty rate of 77.7% and 76.6% respectively (NBS 2012). The reason is not far-fetched considering that these zones are riddled with conflicts. Absence of basic services, unemployment, bad governance and corruption, provide an avenue for disgruntled members of the society to be radicalized.

Insecurity in the North led to the declaration of a state of emergency in three states in the zone namely; Yobe, Adamawa and Bornu states. Despite this, the killing continues and the worst aspect of it is that in recent times, educational institutions have become targets with many male students killed and hundreds of young girls abducted. Besides, there is a spill-over effect with insecurity spilling over to other parts of the North like Zamfara state which had for long been a peaceful state compared to other states in the North. On Saturday 5th April, 2014, about 112 people were reported killed by insurgents who stormed Yar'galadima village in Dansadau District of Maru LGA of the state (DailyTrust Newspaper April 7, 2014).

Poverty is a cause and effect of conflicts between Niger Delta's minority ethnic groups and Multinational Oil Companies (MNOCs) with the former who felt they were being shortchanged and demanded for a share of the 'petrol dollar' as compensation for environmental degradation among others. The violence that erupted as a result of this has not only led to the destruction of means of livelihood but in most cases the loss of bread winners. In addition, it has impeded business investments in the areas of economic growth and productivity, encouraged inflation and unemployment affected negatively the living standards of the people. As a result of disenchantment with the activities of MNOCs, various militant groups in the Niger Delta emerged and resorted to abducting foreign oil workers for ransom (Okorie, Onyema and Bassey, 2019).

In the North Central Zone, insecurity is also rife. In places like Plateau state, conflict between the Hausa-Fulani and the Berom people has left many dead while in Benue state the recent conflict between the Fulani herdsmen and the local people led to many deaths and villages being sacked. Nasarawa state is another conflict-ridden state in the Zone. Communal conflicts have become pervasive to the extent that virtually every local government area has an unresolved conflict at various stages of escalation or de-escalation (Ayih, 2003; Gyuse and Ajene, 2006). There is conflict between the Eggon-Koro/Migiliin Obi Local Government, the Alagos and Hausa are locked in internecine conflict with the Tiv Community in Awe Local Government over land matters while there is conflict in Nasarawa Local Government between the indigenous Afo and the Hausa/Fulani over chieftaincy dispute. Insecurity in the regions no doubt affects the nation's national income as it discourages investors (Okorie, Onyema and Bassey, 2019).

In South-East region, conflict between Herders and Farmers which had claimed lives and property in Nimbo community in Uzo-Uwani Local government area of Enugu state in 2016 is another dimension of insecurity. Also, the incessant kidnapping/ killings along Ugwu-Ogo Nike Opi-Agu/Agu Ekwegbe Nsukka road is another dimension of insecurity in the country. Many farmers could not attend to the farming activities as a result of insecurity, which metamorphosed into the increase in poverty rate to the entire zone. Fear of the unknown attacks dwindle and retard the supply of food from the rural areas to the urban settlement, which increases poverty and hunger. Imo state has been another dungeon of insecurity and kidnapping

in the South-East. On this note, this paper tries to investigate the impact of poverty on security in Nigeria

Statement of the Problem

Despite having an abundance of intellectuals, technocrats, and natural wealth, the majority of Nigerians live in extreme poverty. Financial crimes, transnational organized crimes, armed robberies and other related thefts, kidnappings, farmers-herdsmen clashes, political assassinations, vandalism of government infrastructure, insurgency by Niger Delta Militant, and terrorism by Boko Haram Sect are just a few of the crimes that Nigeria has witnessed recently (Adegoke, 2015; Osawe, 2015). One of the reasons behind the formation of a militia group that uses improvised explosive devices (IEDs) and heavy weapons is poverty. It has grown to be a significant issue that is acknowledged both domestically and globally, that needs immediate action, particularly in Sub-Saharan African nations like Nigeria. Because of the nation's high level of corruption and institutional fragility, majority of Nigerians live in substandard conditions that have become phobic and defied all solutions presented (Ikyase and Namu, 2018).

In Nigeria, poverty's effects are widespread and can result in violent act. For instance, a destitute individual poses a challenge to both society and himself and he is constantly irate, unproductive, while being desperate to survive by joining a militia. This could be due to economic marginalization, unemployment, inequality, and a lack of education. In light of this, this study explores the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria and identifies the policy measures that governments should take to combat poverty and deal with the seemingly unabated and multifaceted insecurity in order to prevent unintended consequences that could jeopardize Nigeria's very existence as a federation.

Objectives of the Study:

The following study objectives and null hypotheses were developed in accordance with the literature review.

- i. To examine the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria
- ii. To evaluate the effect of poverty on insecurity in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of poverty on insecurity in Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study:

H1: There is no significant relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria

H2: Poverty does not have a significant effect on insecurity in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Poverty

The concept of poverty has evolved over time and differs in extent and magnitude amongst countries. It has therefore become extremely difficult to come up with definitions that are universally accepted (Akwara, Akwara, Enwuchola, Adekunle & Udaw, 2013). Nonetheless, there are widely recognized measures of what defines poverty. The widely recognized definition of absolute, relative, and material poverty divides these variables into three major groups. The incapacity of an individual or community to supply necessities for bodily sustenance and preservation of human dignity, such as clothing, food, housing, and clean water, as well as basic education, transportation, and gainful employment, is known as absolute poverty. It decreases one's involvement in society to the point where it hinders the realization of personal potentials.

Poverty can be defined as a state of not having access to healthcare, income, or empowerment. Nwagwu (2014) asserts that "to be poor is to be powerless." It also implies being scorned and denigrated. It entails receiving unfair treatment. Above all, it denotes a dearth of elements that contribute to sound physical and mental health. Karl Marx observed that economics is the key to the class system. Therefore, poverty is an extreme condition in which a person is unable to take advantage of the resources available to him in order to better himself in any way—be it socially, politically, economically, or otherwise (Okorie, Onyema and Basse, 2019).

Insecurity

It would be better to start with introducing the idea of security in order to fully comprehend the concept of insecurity. The definition of this is "the existence of conditions within which people in a society can go about their normal daily activities without any threats to their lives or properties," according to Ogunleye, Adewale, Alese, and Ogunde (2011), referenced in Ighomereho and Akpo-Robaro (2015:80). To put it simply, security is the safeguarding of individuals' lives and belongings within the political community. It is a state's primary justification for existing (Ikyase & Namo, 2018). Security, on the other hand, can also be defined as follows: safety or protection from psychological harm stemming from the assurance that one is wanted, accepted, loved, and protected in one's community or neighborhood and by people around; predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect); protection from crime (feeling safe); and freedom from instability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income).

According to Nwanegbo, Umara, and Ikyase (2017) security is the ability to shield the populace from famine, illness, unemployment, poverty, and natural calamities. A high standard of living is enjoyed by the populace in nations where the proper development paradigm is in place and being followed. This is evidenced by the government's willingness to provide jobs, portable water, electricity, affordable housing, decent food, and roads, among other basic necessities. A lack of dread, threat, worry, tension, and apprehension over the loss of life, liberty, goals, and values is likely to occur in a secure environment. Thus, security entails tackling Nigerians' extreme material poverty.

Therefore, insecurity can be defined as an act that could endanger one's life or cause pain or make life unpleasant, it is the opposite of security. However, the concept of insecurity

has typically been assigned multiple interpretations in relation with the many ways in which it impacts individuals or groups due to the myriad ways in which it influences human life and existence. Loss of safety, risk, hazard, uncertainty, loss of confidence, questionable, insufficiently guarded or protected, unstable, disturbed, lack of protection, and dangerous are some common descriptors of insecurity (Kukati, 2012).

Ighomereho and Akpor-Robaro (2015), characterizes insecurity as "a condition of anxiety or fear resulting from a real or perceived absence of safety." To put it succinctly, insecurity is the state of being vulnerable to injury and loss of life, property, or source of income. Nigeria is currently dealing with a number of issues, including escalating incidents of insecurity, a recurring pattern of attacks on individuals, and agitations stemming from ethnic divisions. The nation is facing challenges related to survival, stability, and security as a result of a number of ongoing insecurity cases in Nigeria, such as the roving herdsmen militancy, the new face of militancy in the Niger Delta, the Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East, the vocal separatist agitations in the South-East, and the recent wave of kidnappings, armed robberies, abductions, and other violent crimes (Nwanegbo et al., 2017).

Poverty and Insecurity in Nigeria

According to Adegoke (2015), there is a correlation between unemployment and the rise in crimes, terrorism, and sectarian violence. Nwagwu (2014) suggests that unemployment leads to poverty. Poverty leads to a high prevalence of state insecurity in Nigeria, which borders on armed robberies, kidnappings, abductions, and other criminal activities, as well as ethno-religious disputes and the difference between indigenous people and settlers. In Nigeria, unemployment and poverty have been major contributing factors to the emergence of multiple ethno-religious crises. This is due to the nation's massive reservoir of impoverished individuals who, frustrated, are easily available to belligerents and eager to act as mercenary combatants (Nwagwu, 2014).

Ighodalo (2012) submitted that "one of the main causes of the nation's political, social, and economic strife is poverty." Poverty is incompatible with the values and fundamental principles of democracy. When there is enough around, poverty breeds discontent and pushes people into violence. The people's capacity to make autonomous decisions and actively engage in the decision-making process is restricted, and their self-worth is diminished as well as their capacity to hold elected officials accountable. The relentless growth of youth militias in Nigeria is a result of poverty (Jike, 2017). This bolsters the claim made by Nwagwu (2024) that young people without salary-earning jobs comprised the Niger Delta youths, the Oduduwa People's Congress (OPC), the movement for the Actualization of Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), and the resurgence of Boko-Haram, a faceless religious sect devoid of ideology

Similarly, Nwagbosa (2013) maintains that one of the main reasons for insecurity in Nigeria is the inability of the country's successive administrations to address issues of poverty, unemployment, and unequal wealth distribution among ethnic groups. Despite the numerous policies and initiatives put in place by the various governments of Nigeria, including the Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP), the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), National Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), SURE-P, N-Power, Trader money, among others may seem, their failure to impact the intended audience—young people—reflects the gap that exists in Nigeria between the formulation of policy and its actual execution. According to Maduagwu, (2006), referenced in Toby and Akani (2014), among the

reasons why previous attempts to reduce poverty in Nigeria were unsuccessful were the following:

(i) The politics of personal rule is a unique kind of political system where the main factors influencing political life are not impersonal institutions, ideologies, public politics, or class interests, but rather the rivalries and conflicts of strong, determined men.

(ii) The Abuja method's top-down, big-men strategy, which emphasizes the master-servant dynamic in poverty alleviation initiatives. Studies have linked Nigeria's high rate of poverty to a deeper, more significant issue than just the country's rising crime rate (Osawe, 2015; Etim, Duke & Ogbinyi, 2017). Thus, there is a clear connection between Nigeria's high rate of property and life insecurity and poverty.

Theoretical Framework

The adoption of frustration-aggression Theory provides the theoretical foundation for examining how poverty affects insecurity in the state of Nigeria. This traditional view explains why people commit violent crimes (riots, rebellions, coups, etc.), particularly young people. A variety of sources of frustration, including a lack of money or the inability to get respect as a result of economic disadvantages, have been linked to juvenile criminality, particularly among lower-class kids (Greenberg, 1977). The frustration-aggression theory, which contends that frustration is only the act of blocking someone from making an advancement, development, or achievement in life, further supports this premise by suggesting that this obstruction almost certainly results in discontent when a person or group chooses to respond violently (aggression) in order to express disapproval of obstacles to their success. These can lead to sentiments of rage, which can then result in violent conduct and feelings of aggression (Zumve, Ingyoroko, & Akuva, 2013).

Anger, or the emotional willingness to act aggressively, is produced when frustration gives rise to animosity. Adegoke (2015) quoted Ivo and Feierabend, 1972, who used the frustration-aggression theory to examine political instability in 84 different countries. It was shown that individuals in quickly developing modern countries become more conscious of material improvement as they get more urbanized and have higher levels of literacy, as is the case in Nigeria today. The state's incapacity to coordinate its efforts and fulfill its fundamental duty of safeguarding its population has been greatly attributed, among other reasons, to its incapacity to manage insecure situations. Nigeria may be considered a Fragile State given the increasing wave of instability that is sweeping the entire nation. According to Sara (2008), a country that has significant developmental issues such limited institutional capacity, bad governance, political instability, unemployment, low economic development, and poverty is referred to as being in a fragile state.

Leading proponent of the frustration-aggression theory in Nigeria, Salawu (2010), contends that "the unfortunate breakdown of such indigenous vehicles of social control of human behaviors that characterized the Traditional African Societies, such as the family units, pre-school age indigenous education and native laws, religion and traditional political system that molds human behavior, is one of the major causes of what we now see as ethnoreligious conflicts in Nigeria." conventional governmental structure that fosters moral character, values human life, and prioritizes the welfare of all constituents. The breakdown of these established institutions has led to a rise in violent crimes, including Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East, ethnic and communal conflicts, loud separatist protests in the South-East, and a new face

of militancy among herdsmen in the Niger Delta. It has also seriously jeopardized the basic foundation and continued existence of state security agents in Nigeria. He connected the failed state to widespread unemployment, illiteracy, and poverty, which drove people—especially young people—to turn to crime as a means of subsistence. In Nigeria, violent conflicts and criminal activity are direct results of anger, which is directly linked to poverty.

METHODOLOGY

The aimed of the study was to examine the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. The descriptive methods and causal research design were adopted and data was collected via a survey of 600 respondents comprises of Christian leaders, Muslim leaders, leaders of Civil Society groups, Traditional leaders and Youth leaders randomly selected in each geopolitical zones as shown below.

Table 1: Population of the Study

Variables	North-West	North-Central	North-East	South-West	South-South	South-East	Total
Christian Leaders	Sokoto (20)	Plateau (20)	Taraba (20)	Lagos (20)	Bayelsa (20)	Ebony i(20)	120
Muslim Leaders	Kaduna (20)	Kwara (20)	Adama wa (20)	Osun (20)	Akwa-Ibom (20)	Anambra (20)	120
Civil Society Groups Leaders	Zamfara (20)	Niger (20)	Bauchi (20)	Oyo (20)	Rivers (20)	Enugu (20)	120
Traditional Leaders	Kebbi (20)	Kogi (20)	Borno (20)	Ogun(20)	Delta (20)	Abia(20)	120
Youth Leaders	Kano (20)	FCT (20)	Yobe (20)	Ekiti (20)	Edo (20)	Imo (20)	120
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	600

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

Sampling Technique

The positive non-probabilistic method was adopted to target respondents with knowledge about the specific issues captured in the study. The sample was drawn from the six geopolitical zones to elicit views on the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using correlation and linear regression analysis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.

Reliability and Validity of the Instruments

A structured questionnaire was designed to elicit needed information from the respondents. The reliability was established through a trial test conducted on 40 respondents in the South-South zone who also took part in the study. Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument as shown in the table below.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics of variables

Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Poverty	9	0.753
Insecurity	11	0.714

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

The results yielded a coefficient of 0.753 and 0.714, which satisfied the general recommended level of 0.70 for the research indicators (Cronbach, 1951). Experts also judged the face and content validity of the questionnaire as adequate. Hence, researchers' satisfied both the reliability and validity of the scale.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 3: Distribution of Questionnaire and Response Rate

S/N	Geopolitical zones	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire Retrieved	Percentage (%)
1	North-West	100	51	8.5
2	North-Central	100	66	11.0
3	North-East	100	42	7.0
4	South-West	100	62	10.3
5	South-South	100	75	12.5
6	South-East	100	69	11.5
	Total	600	365	60.8

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

Out of the 600 questionnaires administered across the six (6) geopolitical zones, 365 were retrieved and analyzed given us a response rate of 60.8%. While a total of 235 questionnaires representing 39.2% were not returned. This indicated that majority of the questionnaire distributed across the states of the Federation were returned and were utilized for the study as presented in this study.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

Variables		Poverty	Insecurity
Poverty	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 365	.883** .000 365

Insecurity	Pearson	.883**	1
	Correlation	.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	365	365
	N		

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2-tailed)

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 shows the correlation between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. There exists a significant positive high correlation between poverty and insecurity ($r = .883$, $n = 365$, & $P < 0.005$). This implies that poverty has a strong and positive relationship with insecurity in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5: Moderated Linear Regression Analysis showing the Effect of the Independent Variable on the Dependent Variable.

Independent Variable	R ²	Adj. R ²	Coefficient	F-stat	R. Sig.	T-stat	Tsig.	D.W
Poverty	.785	.743	.319	22.513	.000 ^a	-.212	.000	1.927

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

In table 5, drawing on the model summary displayed by the linear regression analysis, we observed that R² value which is the coefficient determination was 0.785. This implies that poverty accounts for a 78.5% increase in insecurity in Nigeria. While the remaining 21.5% causes of change in insecurity are explained by other factors not included in the model, but taken care of by error terms. The Adjusted R² value which was 0.743 in the linear regression model further indicated that coefficient of determination, when adjusted for the degree of freedom, yielded approximately 74.3%. The Durbin Watson statistic, which is 1.927, implies the absence of serial autocorrelation in the regression analysis and therefore, the model can be relied upon in making policies related to the subject matter. The F-statistic value of 22.513 at $\text{prob}(\text{sig.}) = .000^a$ conducted at 5% level of significant depicted in the regression results revealed that overall, there exists a statistically significant linear relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Similarly, the T-statistic of -.212 at P-value (sig.) of .000 obtained in the model which is less than 5% or 0.05 level of significant also indicated that there is a significant relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.319 further indicated that a one percent increase in poverty results in a 31.9% increase in insecurity in Nigeria.

FINDINGS

Research indicates that violence, animosity, and insecurity are fostered by poverty and inequality in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results amongst others revealed that there is a strong and positive relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Osawe (2015) and Etimetal's (2017) studies which revealed a direct relationship between poverty and insecurity. As predicted, the results also showed that poverty exerts a positive and statistically significant impact on insecurity in Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Ighodalo's (2012), Nwagwu's (2014), Adekoge's (2015) and Jike's (2017) views that poverty is responsible for the spate of insecurity of lives and properties in Nigeria. Good governance is the main function of an effective, visionary, transparent, trustworthy, and credible leadership whose motivation is to improve the general well-being of the populace through carefully thought out, skillfully carried out economic policies and human development initiatives. Consequently, accelerating economic growth and reducing insecurity are necessary to end poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Taking into account should be devoted to incorporating poverty alleviation into the country's broader development/policy management framework and making it an explicit constitutional problem.

Conclusions

The study's apparent conclusions have demonstrated that poverty in Nigeria significantly influenced insecurity. Furthermore, it was established that poverty and insecurity are significantly related in Nigeria. From the study's results, we deduced that poverty in an affluent environment breeds discontent and violent behavior, limits people's capacity to make their own decisions and actively engage in the political process, lowers people's self-esteem, and makes it harder for them to hold those in positions of power accountable. Those who lack the funds and other necessities for a comfortable living—such as access to quality healthcare, wholesome food, a place to live, clothes, and other social amenities—are considered impoverished.

The gap between policy formation and implementation in Nigeria is evident in the numerous policies and programs, no matter how lofty and admirable they may seem, that have not been able to impact the real target, the youth despite being launched by successive Nigerian governments. Examples of these programs and policies include the Better Life Programme (BLP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Family Support Programme (FSP), Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), National Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), SURE-P, N-Power, Trader money, etc.

Recommendations

The following policy recommendations were offered in light of the study's theoretical and empirical findings:

1. To guarantee Nigeria's political stability, economic stability, supply of sufficient social services, and other infrastructure development, the government at all levels should step up its efforts. It should be thought about include poverty alleviation in the country's overall development/policy management framework and making it an explicit constitutional concern.
2. All levels of government should enact laws to shield the populace from hunger, disease, unemployment, natural disasters, poverty, and other threats. The grassroots population should also be sufficiently involved in the selection and execution of projects and initiatives that have an impact on their daily lives.
3. The federal and state governments need to come up with practical plans to use the nation's resources to generate income and jobs in order to lower poverty. It is necessary to amend the 1999 Constitution, which restricts the states and centre

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The Effect of Economic Corruption and Political Instability on Nigerian Economy

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Abstract

Corruption and instability has been a great challenge in Nigeria and have affected virtually all facets of the economy and the political system. The study focused on the effect of economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria on real economy in Nigeria. The study used secondary data from 1997 to 2022 and sourced the data from the Central Bank of Nigeria and World Development indicators of various editions. The ordinary Least Square estimator and Granger causality test were used to achieve the stated objectives of the study. The results revealed that economic and political instability exert adverse effects on the aggregate economy real output in Nigeria, while other control variables did align with their a priori expectation because of the interaction of economic and political instability in the system. The causality test showed that economic corruption has the predictive power to cause changes in the political system. Therefore, it was recommended that the government should consciously reduce corruption in the system by strengthening the institutions and political structure in the country.

Keywords: Accumulation by Dispossession. Economic Corruption, Economic output, Political Instability, Rentier Capitalism, Real Output

Introduction

The neoliberalism movement accentuated by Margaret Thatcher in the United Kingdom (UK) and Roland Reagan in the United States (US) instigated the prompting of the spread of globalization beyond the 1980s to the global South with the transfer of overconcentrated accumulated capital seeking diffusion to penetrate fragile economies where unexploited opportunities can be converted into profit maximization (Standing, 2016). This was not a charitable venture; it was typically engineering of spatial fix to recalibrate local economies that needed capital for expansion to stimulate economic growth. The attraction of foreign capital to the local economy (like Nigeria) had required neoliberal reforms taking the shape of privatization of public assets (buy over), rollback of the state in economic organizations from enterprises and public intervention, deregulation of financial and social service sectors, and the liberalization of the market as the allocative institution predisposing dominance over society (Christophers, 2020; Harvey, 2020; Standing, 2016).

Critically, Nigeria is entangled in this relation of neoliberal reforms mainly from its development by invitation synchronism, and dependency posture to partially possess and extract crude oil resources, since it lacks the technology and funding for the project. This invitation had colonial linkage taking the form of a predatory complex extending beyond mineral extraction, technology deployment, financialization, market liberalization, labour, and societal displacement (Ebohon, 2013; Falola, 2021; Falola & Heaton, 2008; Lewis, 2006).

The neoliberal economy is typically analyzed from the perspective of promoting efficiency through competition, privatization of ownership structure, control of capital, and the

socialization of production, distribution, exchange, and consumption. The ownership of capital and technology of extraction tend to create hegemony in scarce resource investment and management. As the Nigerian State claims ownership of mineral resources in the country, it requires foreign capital and technology to extract and refine the resources. The capital injection and technological deployment facilitated by foreign multinational corporations in Nigeria account for more than 90% of foreign exchange earnings, and 80% of contribution to the national budget (Christophers, 2021; Ikelegbe, 2005; National Bureau of Statistics, 2022; Okonjo-Iweala, 2012; Sanghera & Satybaldieva, 2023).

Investment in the oil sector has been monopolized by Oil Multinational Corporations (OMC-Shell, Chevron, Mobil, Agip, and Total). This provides leverage as Joint Venture Partners with the Nigerian State to own and control viable scarce oil resources as part of the energy sources that are fueling the global economy. The sector is typical for its accruing rent to the Nigerian State and the OMC. This is implicated as rentier capitalism and is notorious for corruption embedded in the failure of disclosure between the Nigerian State and the OMC on the quantum of mineral resources extracted from the ground (Christophers, 2020; Rosenberg, 2017; Standing, 2016).

The environment (air, land, and water) from which the oil resources are extracted and the people who culturally inhabit these places are dispossessed of the gains derived, the capital accumulated is discreetly shared between elites with political and economic power and the OMC. The capital accumulated and asset dispossession scheme over time create exponential wealth for the elites and OMC while dialectically reproducing increasing poverty, economic inequality, and social disruption (Harvey, 2004, 2018).

Exclusive political power is used to create extractive economic institutions that undermine the democratic decision-making process, obstruct social justice, and exacerbate economic disequilibrium (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2019, 2012). As economic opportunities become scarce through the dispossession of common assets embedded in state capture projects and increasing rentier capitalist accumulation, state and society relationship will tend to weaken to account for political instability (AichRothstein & Varrach, 2017; Aron, 2000; Asuquo, 2020; Falola & Heaton, 2008; Ikelegbe, 2013; Nelson & Prilleltensky, 2010; Oshita & Ikelegbe, 2019; Prilleltensky & Gonick, 1996; Robinson, 2023).

Rentier capitalism as a form of neoliberal reform creates a mysterious inclination that is difficult to understand in less developed economies. It generates capital for the global developed North but it is used to reproduce poverty and misery in the global South. It organically creates contradictions as a movement that is intended to create competition through expansion and innovation, but as it grows into diffused undeveloped enclaves, it becomes an instrument of alienation, targeted at asset enclosure, and a medium of extraction through coercion and corruption (Christophers, 2018; Home & Lim, 2013; Soto, 2000; Transparency International, 2020)

Corruption affects economic growth and performance in several ways. When the scale of rent drawn from the economy (returns without reproduction) exceeds the capacity of the economy to experience growth towards other sectors, uncertainty will blossom while creating risk and disincentive to invest in the economy (Harvey, 2014).

The problems of rentier capitalism and rentier states are related to exploitation and underdevelopment and have been covered by several scholars in the realm of political economy and development studies (Christophers, 2020, 2021; Ebohon, 2013; Ifaka, 2016; Micinski,

2021; Sanghera & Satybaldieva, 2023; Shawki, 2024; Standing, 2016, 2017; Van Der Ploeg, 2011), but there exist gaps in explaining the relationship, impact and causal effects of economic corruption and political instability on real aggregate output in exploited fragmented federal states like Nigeria.

The research objective of this study is to examine the relationship that exists among economic corruption, political instability, and real aggregate output in the Nigerian Economy; and investigate the effect and causal relationship between economic corruption and political instability. The hypotheses drawn from the objectives are stated in their null form; there is no significant relationship that exists among economic corruption, political instability, and real aggregate output; there is no significant effect of economic corruption and political instability on real aggregate output; and there are no significant causal effects of economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria.

The identified independent variables are economic corruption and political instability and the dependent variable is real aggregate output in the Nigerian economy.

Literature review

Economic corruption

While underscoring the neoliberal economy policies in the United Kingdom, (Christophers, 2018, 2020; Standing, 2016) epitomized that rentierism has predominated the way capital is created without recourse to production. To properly capture how the capitalist economy operates, Harvey, (2018) noted that capital is deployed into owning means of production and hiring labour, this medium is brought together in social relations of production to produce products that are distributed and exchanged for consumption, while capital is expanded to recapitalize the economy. This cycle is repeated endlessly.

Christophers, (2020) draws our attention to a new dimension of perversion in the UK economy where the focus of the capitalists is now on ownership of rentier access for extraction of rent without concern for production. The excitement is to deploy the enclosure of common assets and convert same as a means of accumulation by dispossession (Harvey, 2004).

Standing, (2019) sees the process of forcefully capturing and converting public assets in the privatization and enclosure programmes for personal gain as a new form of corruption. The accumulation of these public assets is done in phony circumstances that rip off the public, and the trend is to create rent from these assets, ignoring production that adds value to society. The displacement of production naturally displaces labour, and creates inequality, and poverty.

The expansion of capital through asset ownership from enclosure, intellectual and private properties, land and mineral resources, technology platforms, financialization as commodification, and holding of stocks and bonds not deployed to production but are accelerated to generate rent as profit maximation contribute to the crisis of capitalism, and the source of political instability (Barrett, 2023; Bracking, 2018b; J. S. Hellman et al., 2003). These anomalies are perpetuated by state elites who benefit from the rentier capitalist network (Barrett, 2023; Bracking, 2018a; Chindo et al., 2014; J. Hellman & Schankerman, 2000; Lewis, 2006; Smith, 2007; Standing, 2016).

The decision to transfer common resources in many cases are not disclosed to the public and in rentier States, the center of decision-making (capital cities) is spatially isolated or suspended

from society. The gap in distance and communication limits accountability and promotes corruption (Campante & Do, 2012).

The dysfunctional nature of corruption is typified as extractive burden place on both political and social institutions. The weight of the extract cost from corruption reduce the ability of government to provide public service, since a portion is diverted for personal gain (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Also corruption tend to erode public trust (Fukuyama, 2014, 2022) and Harvey, (2014) sees corruption as an inherent part and parcel of the capitalist structure. It is a scheme design to accumulate capital and dispossess the people from the realization of quality public service.

Corruption and political instability are deeply connected to causing distortion in preventing economic growth. Economic growth occurs when political and economic institutions are inclusive and the benefits are sharing widely (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). The distortion relates to accelerating the allocation of public resources to rent seeking behaviours that discourages robust investment through competition. Corruption is linked to cronic capitalism where oligarchy or narrow based elite interest are organized to survert public efficiency and disclosure in managing public resources and its distribution. Corruption is intensified through the use of state power to divert resources, reduce public service, priotize short term gains, upsurge uncertainty, and restrict production and economic growth (Christophers, 2014; Harvey, 2014; Standing, 2016).

Political Instability

Political order is require for government to be efficient and an enabler to allow the private sector to thrive in building a viable and sustainable economy. The primary condition for order, which predisposes stability, are a strong state institution (bureaucracy), rule of law that protect private property and assure political accountability (Fukuyama, 2014). Political decay, a condition of perversion in the misuse and abuse of public institutions can create discontent, reduce public trust and generate social tension leading to political instability (Aron, 2000; Fukuyama, 2014, 2022).

When societal resources, opportunities, positions, and status are not equally or equitable distributed, social tension is created. The fragility arisen from this exclusive institutional mechanism that violates social justice principles lend causes for group grievances, and even fractionalization of elites across race, religion, region, politics, culture, and class consciousness (Constantine, 2017; Israel & Frenkel, 2017; King, 2016; Ramzan et al., 2020).

Disadvantage groups or persons are predisposes to rebel or revolt against state institution and their functioning (Agbibo, 2013; Hedges, 2015). Corruption is often associated with the privilege use of position or assigned opportunity to seek gains at the expense of others or society at large (Ahlquist & Levi, 2013; Lewis, 2006; Noonam, 2023). Primitive accumulation deployed by capitalist and rentiers can upset public interest when politics is conjure against the interest of disadvantage groups through exploitation and dispossession (Harvey, 2018; Standing, 2019).

Political instability and economic corruption can have bidirectional effects on state capacity and economic growth. Both have negative attributes towards promoting national integration, political order and economic growth (Falola & Heaton, 2008). The quality of elite and quality of democracy (regime type) can manifest into disproportionnal outcomes, both quality of elite and quality of democracy are extractive, and predatory against the interest of the common

(Beetham et al., 2008; Burgis, 2015; Casas & Cozzi, 2022; Hoppe, 2007; Nitzan & Bichler, 2006).

Aggregate Output:

Capitalism and the neoliberal doctrine of freemarket, privatization in the ownership of capital, predisposes the lure for investment to derive profit maximation. Capital is value in motion and run in circular motion. Capital as value in the capitalist system requires production to take place before it can effectively turn out profit. Profit occurs through social relationship. This means capital is an initiator of the production process. Capital needs to be available to procure means of production (land, machine, assets, technology, raw material) and hiring of labour power (Das, 2017; Harvey, 2010).

The means of production are inanimate and requires the effect of human to create surplus value. The production process stimulate a social relation of production, the composite of means of production to generate surplus value. The output of production is commodified and valued as capital. It is at this point that labour is exploited as a commodity and bought at sustitence value, while the surplus is extracted by the capitalist as profit (Harvey, 2018, 2020; Ledeneva, 2017; Mavroudeas & Papadatos, 2018).

Real aggregate output is concern with the total output of production (goods and services) in an econmy for a giving period under investigation. It is therefore a parameter to evaluate the productive capacity of a nation. Real aggregate output reflects the present and deployment of labour (human capital), technology and physical capital to produce the total value of goods and services in an economy (Csontos, 2023; Dunford, 2021; Greiner & Finckec, 2015; Robinson, 2023; Smith, 2009).

Measuring aggregate output in the Nigerian economy will tend to focus on where the impact of the production capacity is derived from. The Nigerian economy is hugely dependent on the cruel oil and gas. The trajectory of the Nigerian economy between 1997 to 2022 is treated under three phases. The first phase of 1997 to 1999 indicated Nigeria military rule era where the country was under severe economic santions over its human rights abase and the crude oil production experied massive restrictive slaes that was dependent on global export and price determination. The GDP growth was sluggished with on 2% realization on the back of the oil sector while agriculture and manufacturing sectors were massively ignored.

Between 1999 and 2001, Nigeria entered into the democratic frenzy and sort for debt forgiveness that restrained Foreign Direct Investment in the country. This period experience recovery, flow of investment base on trust of democratic governance. From 2002 to 2007, Nigeria intensified neoliberal reforms through provitaization of various sector and the oil sector experience oil boom with a 7% GDP growth rate for the period. The country rebased its economy in 2014 and became the largest economy in Africa with a \$510 billion economy (Okonjo-Iweala, 2012, 2018).

Mismanagement of the economy, fall in the price of oil, and excessive borrowing starting from 2015 saw Nigeria entered its first recession in 2016. The GDP ran into a negative of -1.6, recovered to 0.8% in 2017, stabilizing to 2% up to 2020. However, the pandemic brought the second recession in 2020 with a decline and negative GDP of -1.8. The relative shock associated with global oil shock and proice fluatuation saw slow post pandemic recovery of under 3% of GDP up to 2022. Analyst of the country's economy has majorly captured the

driven machinery driving the Nigerian economy as rentier loaded with corruption and variance of political instability (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Fukuyama, 2014; Harvey, 2020; Okonjo-Iweala, 2018).

Theoretical framework

Corruption affects the performance of the economic in several ways. It reduces both foreign and domestic investments because it distorts and increases uncertainty, and risks of investment. Corruption equally increases cost of doing business, thus, discouraging people to invest (Wei, 2000). The reduction in foreign direct investment does not only reduce potential economic growth, but reduces transfer of technology that would have come with such investment.

The study adopted the extractive theory of imperialism as the theoretical framework for the study. The Extractive Theory of imperialism, which was propounded by Rosa Luxemburg in 1913 in her work "The Accumulation of Capital" refers to the relationship between state, its agent and the economic society. The theory relates the relationship of imperialism to corruption, exploitation, force, violence and coercion used to extract resources and labour (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). The state agent uses the resources to the benefits of their leader. Iyanda (2012) in his work on corruption definition theories and concepts he explains that the concept of extractive theory is based on the idea of authoritarianism, the use of force and exploitation of a state's resources by rulers or their agents.

Also the proponent of extractive theory of corruption is linked to Acemoglu & Robinson, (2012) in their classic book why nations fail. They established that extractive political and economic institutions embedded in corruption limit economic growth as well as propagate inequality and wide spread poverty.

Both political and economic institutions of a country can be extractive to the extent that they exclude others from participating, contributing and benefiting from both political and economic process and outcome. Political and economic exclusion naturally produce weak institutions and reproduces economic decline, intense economic inequality, legitimacy crisis and political instability (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2019; Morelli & Seaman, 2022).

The theory backs the study up by resisting autocratic regimes and the government's officials who use power and resources of the state to protect their individual and selfish interest at the detriment of the nation economic growth. In other words, where excessive power is concentrated absolutely in the hands of a few person, there is high tendency for corruption, abuse of power, wealth seeking and extraction of resources for personal gains.

Empirical Review:

The corruption of capitalism as an instrument of labour exploitation, following the neoliberal discontent, have been associated with political instability, especially in rentier States like Nigeria. There are concern of massive state capture, state failure, state fragility, and declining economic growth related to entrenched corruption and political instability (Dunn, 2017; Ifaka, 2016; Kaplan, 2000; Klein, 2007).

Political instability as political decay discourage invest in business, since investors are predispose to risk aversion. The stimulation of political instability are primary driven by the nature and character of state and society relations. The predisposition of post colonial state having features of endemic corruption, predatory, rentier, alien, comprehensively intrusive,

authoritarian regime, prebendal, hegemonical, partial and partisan state, and society that has high level of elite fractionalization, group grievance and external intervention that disruptive the productive capacity of the economy (Asuquo, 2020; Babalola, 2019; Fadakinte, 2013; LeVan, 2014; Pritchett et al., 2013; Shawki, 2024).

The challenge of corruption and political stability has been a major disruptive element in the engaging more competent human capacity in the production process in Nigeria. There is strong evidence that nepotism and corruption has prevented more qualified persons to be engage in the development of the economy. Also the exploitation of labour as driven the available human resources and capital to migrate towards more advance economy (Babalola, 2019; Burgis, 2015; Ebohon, 2013; Fukuyama, 2018; J. S. Hellman et al., 2003; Ifaka, 2022; Ifaka & Odigie, 2021; Klein, 2007; Meredith, 2005, 2019; Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, 2012; Okonjo-Iweala, 2018; Shawki, 2024).

Empirical review from the World Bank, International Monetary funds and several scholars have persistently linked the corruption perception index of Nigeria score to demonstrate the country's posture to its recurrent decline to economic growth. Mismanagement of the Nigeria's oil rent has link with corruption of elite and state capture. Similarly, a report by Okeke had established that 1% increase in corruption reduces the GDP of the country as is explained by loss of investment, reduced quality in service delivery, and inflated contract as much as severity of abandoned projects (Okeke, 2018).

Corruption is linked to fuelling political instability (Okeke, 2018) and this is implicated by associated rise in poverty, inequality, unemployment and continued discontentment with uncertainty that scare investors away and negatively impact economic growth. A study by Eze & Obinwugo (2019) found that the 2015 election instigated political instability that showed a reduction of GDP by 2.7%. Also political instability in the form of insurgency (Militant in the Niger Delta and Boko Haram in the North East) can create hostile environment for business to operate, drive down oil production which causes decline in productions and earning in oil rents (Okon & Efang, 2020).

Political instability reflected in regime change is associated with frequent change of state policies and investors are sceptical to operate in unstable policy environment. Babatunde & Akinyemi (2021) found out that between 2015 and 2020, a transition between President Jonathan and President Buhari regimes, policy reversal were rampant and the inconsistent destitely reduced Foreign Direct Invest.

Methodology

The study used secondary data and adopt the causal and effect research design. The data were source from various editions of Freedom House, Corruption Perception Index, World Development Indicators, Central Bank of Nigeria. The researched deployed qualitative method in analyzing the data.

Method of Data Analysis-

Model Estimation techniques

This study uses descriptive statistics and time series econometric techniques. First, the descriptive statistical analysis employed univariate and matrix correlation to describe each

variable in this study. Second, the time series econometric techniques employ Ordinary Least Square time series property. It also employed the Granger causality test to determine the causal direction between variables.

Model Specifications

In this study, the model specified are based on the objectives of economic corruption (ECC) and economic output as well as political instability (PLC) and economic output. The general functional relationship between aggregate output and corruption is given as:

$$GDP = f(CORR) \tag{1}$$

Where GDP is Economic output and COR is Corruption.

The model specified for economic corruption is given as:

$$GDP = f(ECC) \tag{2}$$

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ECC_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 MANC_t + \alpha_4 FDI_t + \alpha_5 TOP_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{3}$$

Where GDP is the economic aggregate output, ECC is economic corruption, INF is inflation, MCU is manufacturing capacity utilization, FDI is Foreign Direct Investment ad TOP is trade openness.

The model specified for political instability is given as:

$$GDP = f(PLC) \tag{4}$$

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PLC_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 MANC_t + \alpha_4 FDI_t + \alpha_5 TOP_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{5}$$

Where PLC is political instability and other are already defined.

The model specified granger causality test is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma GDP_t &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma ECC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma PLC_{t-i} \\ \Sigma ECC_t &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma PLC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma GDP_{t-i} \\ \Sigma PLC_t &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma ECC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma GDP_{t-i} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

β_0 is the constant coefficient

Data Analysis and Results Interpretation

Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis described the nature of the data in terms of their central tendency and dispersion. The results are presented in Table 4.1. below

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera	Probability
GDP	5.08E+13	5.26E+13	7.58E+13	2.35E+13	1.85E+13	2.561616	0.277813
ECC	20.95000	22.50000	28.00000	7.00000	6.276767	2.892057	0.235504
FDIG	1.315207	1.452078	2.900249	-0.03952	0.847627	1.227372	0.541352
MANC	48.80731	51.20000	62.04000	31.29000	9.036556	2.502902	0.286089
TOP	34.71979	36.27513	51.01630	3.030810	12.24842	5.903026	0.052261
PLC	-1.74842	-1.88293	-0.58824	-2.21112	0.424015	17.24840	0.000180

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

The results in table 1 showed that most of the data have a closed range of central tendency. That is, mean values of GDP, ECC, FDIG, MANC, TOP and PLC gap with their median values are closed. This implies that distribution of the data is not too far from the center point. The standard deviation values of all the data are below the values of the mean and media. This is due to the range of each of the data that reveal a minimal spread of the data when the minimum and the maximum values are compared. The results indicated an obvious fact that most of the data do not exhibit high degree of variabilities. Therefore, the issue of volatility is minimal and the estimation of the model does not need any auto regressive conditional heterogenous approach. The results of the Jarque-Bera showed that GDP, ECC, FDIG and MANC are normally distributed and TOP and PLC are not. However, the number of variables that are normally distributed, which are far more than the ones that are not normally distributed, strengthen the assumption of zero mean and constant variance for the joint estimation.

The maximum value of corruption perception index used to proxy economic corruption is 28, while the minimum is 7. The ranking stated that 100 is zero corruption while a low score indicates a high level of corruption. On average, the mean score recorded a approximate value of 21. Given the mean score, maximum and minimum values, corruption in Nigeria is very prominent and very far from the perfect score of 100. The political instability is proxy by the political stability in the country and score; a negative score shows that the country is politically unstable due to high degree of corruption in the political system. Both the maximum and minimum values indicated a negative value of -0.6 and -2.2 respectively and the mean score over the period is -1.75. the score is an obvious fact that the political system in Nigeria is highly unstable and corrupt.

Correlation Analysis

The estimation of correlation analysis is necessitated to test the validation of the assumption of autocorrelation in Ordinary Least Square estimator

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	GDP	ECC	FDIG	MANC	TOP	PLC
GDP	1.00					
ECC	-0.93	1.00				

	0.00	-----				
FDIG	-0.42	-0.15	1.00			
	0.03	0.47	-----			
MANC	0.65	0.85	0.16	1.00		
	0.00	0.00	0.43	-----		
TOP	-0.16	0.04	0.73	0.22	1.00	
	0.44	0.85	0.00	0.28	-----	
PLC	-0.70	-0.86	-0.13	-0.86	-0.30	1.00
	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.00	0.14	-----

Table 2. revealed that economic corruption (ECC) and political instability (PLC) has a very strong negative and significant correlation with economic output. This implies that the economic output reacts negatively to the outcomes of economic and political instability in Nigeria. Furtherance, other macroeconomic variables such as foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP (FDIG) and trade openness (TOP) also showed a negative correlation, however not too strong like the corruption indicators. The variants nature of the correlation results indicated that there is an absence of autocorrelation and the assumption that there is not correlation among the independent variables was not violated.

Model Estimation and Interpretation of Results

The study estimated two models namely: economic corruption model and political instability model. The results in the two models substantiated the objective of the study by examining the effect of economic corruption on economic output and political instability on the economic outcome as well.

Economic Corruption Model

Economic corruption is measured by the corruption perception index and it showed the level of which corruption has eaten into the fabric of economic activities in the system. The results estimation is reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Economic Corruption Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECC	-3.33E+12	3.19E+11	10.44211	0.0000
FDIG	-4.82E+12	1.74E+12	-2.764530	0.0116
MANC	-5.64E+11	2.19E+11	-2.571598	0.0178
TOP	2.62E+10	1.06E+11	0.245715	0.8083
C	1.40E+13	5.55E+12	2.515695	0.0201
R-squared	0.954502			
Adjusted R-squared	0.945836			
F-statistic	110.1400			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.539702			

Dependent Variable: GDP

The results in Table 3 discovered that economic corruption coefficient value of -3,330 billion is negative sloped and significant at 1% level of significant. This suggest that a unit increase in economic corruption index, GDP will reduce by a naira value of ₦3,330 billion per year. By implication, corruption adversely affect the economic output and all effort to develop the economy is being thwarted by the activities of corruption in the economy.

Other control variables such as foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP and manufacturing capacity utilization showed a negative and significant coefficient of -4,820 billion and -5,640 billion respectively. The negative relationship of these variables is an indication that foreign direct investment contradicts the a priori expectation and exhibit a contraction in the system. The reason behind is the level of capital flight and profit repatriation of the multinational companies and the level of manufacturing capacity utilisation is very low. The results showed that trade openness coefficient does not have any statistical significant even though it has a positive relation. The high degree of volatility of exchange rate has not been able to allow the positive effect of trade openness to reflect on the economic output in Nigeria.

The adjusted R² value of 0.95 indicate that the dependent variable is being explained by the independent variables by 95%. This shows a high degree of goodness of fit on the regression line. The changes and outcome of GDP is ascribed to be explained by a high tendency of ECC, FDIG, MANC and TOP. The value of F-statistic, 110.14 is significant at 1% level and it indicate that the overall model specified is appropriate and the joint effect of the changes of the independent variables is significant to cause an effect on economic output. The Durbin Watson also tested the serial correlation assumption of OLS showed that the value of 1.54 is higher than the value if the adjusted R² and its value is close to 2. This implies that there is no positive serial correlation of auto correction in the model estimated.

Political instability Model

In the political instability in the country and score; a negative score shows that the country is politically unstable due to high degree of corruption in the political system. The results is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Political instability Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PLC	-2.25E+13	9.41E+12	-2.391180	0.0262
FDIG	-1.21E+13	3.41E+12	-3.545075	0.0019
MANC	5.98E+11	4.29E+11	1.394915	0.1776
TOP	4.33E+10	2.44E+11	0.177366	0.8609
C	-3.38E+12	1.15E+13	-0.294263	0.7714
R-squared	0.778558			
Adjusted R-squared	0.736378			
F-statistic	18.45821			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.452308			

Source: Authors' computation, 2024. Dependent Variable: GDP

The results in Table 4 revealed that political instability (PLC) coefficient value of -2.250 billion is negative sloped and significant at 5% level of significant. This suggest that a unit increase in

political instability index, GDP will reduce by a naira value of ₦2.250 billion per year. By implication, corruption adversely affect the economic output and all effort to develop the economy is being disenchanted by the activities of corruption in the political system.

Foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP showed a negative and significant coefficient of -1,210 billion and manufacturing capacity utilization showed a non-significant positive value of 5,980 billion. The negative relationship of these variables is an indication that foreign direct investment contradicts the a priori expectation and exhibit a contraction in the system. The reason behind is the level of capital flight and profit repatriation of the multinational companies and the level of manufacturing capacity utilisation is very low. The results showed that trade openness coefficient does not have any statistically significant even though it has a positive relation. The high degree of volatility of exchange rate has not been able to allow the positive effect of trade openness to reflect on the economic output in Nigeria.

The adjusted R² value of 0.74 indicate that the dependent variable is being explained by the independent variables by 74%. This shows a high degree of goodness of fit on the regression line. The changes and outcome of GDP is ascribed to be explained by a high tendency of ECC, FDIG, MANC and TOP. The value of F-statistic, 18.45 is significant at 1% level and it indicate that the overall model specified is appropriate and the joint effect of the changes of the independent variables is significant to cause an effect on economic output. The Durbin Watson also tested the serial correlation assumption of OLS showed that the value of 1.45 is higher than the value if the adjusted R² and its value is close to 2. This implies that there is no positive serial correlation of auto correction in the model estimated.

Granger Causality test for Casual Relationship

The Granger causality test the casual relationship of the variables and reports whether there is bi-directional effect or not. Economic output (GDP), economic corruption (ECC) and political instability (PLC) are employed to estimate their casual relationship as related to the objectives. Pairwise Granger Causality test used 2 lag criteria and reported the F-statistic and the probability value showing the level of significance.

Table 5: Pairwise Granger Causality test

Variable interaction	Obs	F-statistic	Prob. Value
ECC does not Granger Cause GDP	24	2.03438	0.1583
GDP does not Granger Cause ECC		2.27128	0.1305
PLC does not Granger Cause GDP	24	2.10044	0.1499
GDP does not Granger Cause PLC		0.01491	0.9852
PLC does not Granger Cause ECC	24	1.78146	0.1954
ECC does not Granger Cause PLC		6.82131	0.0059

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

From the results in Table 5, none of the variables shows any bi-directional relationship of effect. However, economic corruption causes the changes in political instability. This is evident in the results where ECC does not Granger Cause PLC hypothesis is rejected and the alternative is accepted because the probability value of 0.0059 is below the 0.05 level of significance. By implication, we can deduce that economic corruption measure in terms of corruption perception index in Nigeria has the predictive power to influence the outcome of political instability. This implies economically, that the rot and decadence in the economic practices and activities lead

to the instability and malpractices in the political space. The bounty or national cake perceived to be in government can only be access by gaining political power. Therefore, this perception by political leaders can lead to political tussle and invariably, instabilise the political system.

4.2. Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis formulated are in line with the research question and objectives of the study. These hypotheses have been tested in the estimated model.

i. H₀ Economic corruption has no impact on economic output in Nigeria.

The estimated results found out in Table 3. revealed that economic corruption has a significant and an adverse effect on economic output in Nigeria given the level of significance and relational direction. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that Economic corruption has no impact on economic output in Nigeria and accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that economic corruption has a strong negative impact on economic output in Nigeria.

ii. H₀: Political instablity has no impact on economic output in Nigeria.

The estimated results found in Table 4 showed that political instablity has a significant and an adverse effect on economic output in Nigeria given the level of significance and relational direction. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that political instablity has no impact on economic growth in Nigeria and accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that political instablity has a strong negative impact on economic output in Nigeria.

iii. H₀: There is no significant causal relationship between economic corruption and political instablity in Nigeria.

The results in Table 5 found out that economic corruption causes the changes in political instablity and have the predictive power to influence the outcome of political instablity that leads to corruption in political practices in Nigeria system. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant causal relationship between economic corruption and political instablity in Nigeria and conclude that economic corruption causes political instablity and there is a causal relationship from economic corruption to political instablity in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion

Corruption and political instablity affect Nigerian economy in several ways. When the scale of rent drawn from the economy (returns without reproduction) exceeds the capacity of the economy to experience growth towards other sectors, uncertainty will blossom while creating risk and disincentive to invest in the economy. The study investigated the effect of economic corruption and political instablity in form of political instablity on the real economy in Nigeria. Secondary data was used from 1997 to 2022 and sourced the data form central Bank of Nigeria and World Development indicators of various editions. The study adopted Ordinary Least Square estimator and Granger causality test to analysed the data and achieved the stated objectives of the study. The results revealed that economic and political instablity exert adverse effects on the aggregate economy real output in Nigeria, while other control variables did align with their a priori expectation because of the interaction of economic and political instablitys in the system. The causality test showed that economic corruption has the predictive power to cause the changes in the political instablity. By implication, corruption is impede economic performance of Nigeria and its has a adverse spillover on virtually every sectors of the economy in Niegria.

Therefore, it is imperative to remove or reduce corruption by conscientising the patriotic mind of Nigeria to protect the fabrics of Nigeria nationhood. It is recommended that the government should consciously reduce corruption in the system by strengthen the institutions and political structure in the country. The activities of the political class should be checkmate by the various levels of government that are put in palces for chack and balances.

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Climate change and migration in Sahel region: The bane of food security in Nigeria

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Abstract

Climate changes of deforestation, desertification, degradation, among others in Sahel region has widely resulted in irregular migration of cattle herders across borders to Nigeria for greener pastures with attendant consequences or threats to food supply thereby exacerbating poverty in Nigeria. The threat to food security emanates from the decline of the environmental conditions affecting agriculture, resulting in resource scarcity often leads to violent conflict, cost increase in food prices to outright food shortages. Climate change has been observed to accelerate the displacement of people when communities are overwhelmed by flood, water dried up for crops cultivation, alarming levels of deforestation, soil degradation, water and air pollution or when there are upheavals and violent conflicts between forced cattle migrants and farmers, claiming ownership of farm lands resulting in shortage in food supplies, income earning and poverty in Nigeria and Africa in general. The paper examines the effects of climate change on farming activities in Sahel region and the impact of migrated pastoralists struggle with the aboriginal farmers over crop lands in various parts of the country on food security in Nigeria. The paper uses frustration-aggression theory as its theoretical framework. Qualitative data was utilized, sourced from textbooks, journals, the internet, among others. From the findings, it was concluded that human activities and natural occurrences have rendered Sahel environment hostile to farming particularly the pastoralists who migrate to Nigeria for better option. That their migration to Nigeria has accentuated resource conflict with the traditional farmers leading to the progressive effects on food production, food security and poverty. It was recommended that the inhabitants of Sahel environment should take to biofuel as alternative to fossil fuels to reduce climate change, the Nigeria Immigration Service should effectively guard the border movement of illegal aliens to forestall food insecurity in order to lift people above poverty in Nigeria, among others.

Keywords: Climate change, Food, Migration, Sahel region, Security.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the nine countries of the CILSS (Permanent Inter-States Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel), the countries covering the Sahel region are: Chad, Niger, Mauritania,

Senegal, Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Cape Verde, and Burkina Faso, with a population close to 60 million and a total area of 5.4 million km². There are other countries, serving as its extension such as the north of Ethiopia or Sudan. The Sahel is between the arid north and the green tropical forest in the south and borders the maritime coast in the west. Its vegetation is primarily made up of savanna-typical bushes, trees and grasses with increasing density from north to south, representing the change from semi-arid grasslands to thorny savanna (Van Keulen, Verhagen, Tekken & Battaglini, 2011). In all Sahel countries, annual rainfall quantity and distribution vary greatly, with scarcity of portable water. Apart from erratic rainfall patterns, unfavorable socio-economic conditions and poor soils are key agricultural development problems (Breman, 1990). In dry years, the livelihood of rural population is threatened, thereby contributing to a vicious circle of underdevelopment, resource depletion and poverty (Lüdeke, Petschel-Held & Schellnhuber, 2004). Changes in rainfall patterns, temperatures and severity of extreme events have direct impacts on crop yields with possibly severe consequences for the food security situation. The countries in Sahel regions, include Chad, Cameroon, Niger and Nigeria neighbouring the Central African Republic and Libya, have politically coordinated to address the decline of the Lake Chad through the Lake Chad Basin Commission and also to manage the surrounding lands, but every effort has been undermined by climate change, exacerbated by deforestation and desertification. In addition, deforestation exacerbates desertification since the removal of sun-blocking cover dries up the land and roots of trees serve to bind the soil difficult for crops to grow for better yields and livestock to graze (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change and migration in Nigeria

The continued environment degradation of parts of Northern Nigeria which has resulted in the loss of grazing fields has induced a southward movement of pastoralists and the major consequences of this migration pattern is the incessant violent clashes between farmer in the host communities and herders. The pattern of conflict has led to disruption of agricultural activities, huge losses in human lives and destruction of farm settlements and communities. The pattern of conflict has increased armed trafficking across the countries. Some herders have resorted to using their acquired armed in perpetrating crimes such as kidnapping, armed robbery and rape, hence worsening the security situation in the country. Climate change has made farming so difficult in the Sahel because of scanty and unreliable rainfall and poor soils. So for centuries, many people have raised livestock instead, moving their herds periodically to find fresh pastures and allow the land to recover (Davis, 2022). Pastoral nomads are herders who wander endlessly in search of water and grazing land for their animals. Once their herds have grazed an area, the nomads move on by given marginal grazing land a chance to recover. The Sahelian countries (CILSS), are among the poorest countries in the world with the most degraded environments. They are also among the countries that are the most vulnerable to the estimated effects of climate change. The persistent drought in the Sudan and Sahel savannah areas has forced many pastoralists out of the region towards the guinea savannah and rain forest areas. This has resulted to increased pressure on lands in these areas. Fallow grounds for crop cultivation have often been eaten up by cattle. The herders and their herds in their search for water and grazing field have often destroyed farmlands, thus bringing them in conflict with local farmers. Farmer herder conflicts have been a recurring incident in the middle belt region and parts of southern Nigeria. The studies of Adishi and Oluka

(2018) indicate that land related violence account for about 31.1% of communal conflicts in Nigeria from 1991 to 2005. This finding is similar to that of many other studies.

This makes the region an area of focus regional and attention on, in respect to the possible effects of climate change and its potential linkages to migration (United Nations Environment Programme 2011). What is causing a lot of people in the Sahel region to migrate include declining rural agricultural and coastal fishery productivity, shifting patterns of nomadic pastoralism, and migration induced by floods, landslides, and other disasters. But since the late 1960s, the Sahel has endured an extensive and severe drought. Desertification occurs when land surfaces are transformed by human activities, including overgrazing, deforestation, surface land mining, and poor irrigation techniques, during a natural time of drought. How is the climate emergency contributing to instability in the Sahel region? What are the climate challenges in Sahel? The Sahel is highly exposed to climate change, yet impacts vary across different regions. The Sahel will gradually become hotter, with some areas experiencing increased, but erratic rainfall. Extreme weather events, including droughts and floods, are expected to intensify in this context. Temperatures there are rising 1.5 times faster than the global average. As a result, droughts and floods are growing longer and more frequent, undermining food production. About 50 million people in the Sahel depend on livestock rearing for survival. But the land available to pastoralists is shrinking (United Nations Environment Programme, 2011).

Climate change and food security in Nigeria

Rainfall controls agricultural activities in Nigeria. The Sahel and Sudan savannah belts represent an extensive grazing areas with cereals and vegetable cultivation more localized around the Fadamas (Fasona and Omojola, 2005). The Guinea savannah is the major food producing areas in Nigeria. It is in the region that root crops, tuber crops, cereals and vegetables are extensively. Crops such as yam, potatoes, cassava, guinea corn, maize and millet massively in the Guinea savannah and distributed to other parts of the country. The rain forest belt also serves as major area for root and tuber crops production but is an exclusive region for cash crops such as oil palm, raffia palm, cocoa, rubber and cashew. These vegetative regions of Nigeria have been adversely affected in different ways by climates change. The persistent drought in the Sudan and Sahel savannah areas has forced many pastoralists out of the region towards the guinea savannah and rain forest areas. This has resulted to increased pressure on lands in these areas. Fallow grounds for crop cultivation have often been eaten up by cattle. The herders and their herds in their search for water and grazing field have often destroyed farmlands, thus bringing them in conflict with local farmers. Farmer herder conflicts have been a recurring incident in the middle belt region and parts of southern Nigeria. The studies of Adishi and Oluka (2018) indicate that land related violence account for about 31.1% of communal conflicts in Nigeria from 1991 to 2005.

Food security is a condition where people symmetrically have access to basic nutritious food. According to the United Nation's Committee on World Food Security. states that food security situation is where everybody has social, physical and economic access to safe, sufficient and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for a healthy and active life. World Food Summit in 1974, defined food security as the availability and adequate supplies of basic food stuffs to offset fluctuation in production, to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and prices at all times. According to FAO cited by Ani, Anyika and Mutambara (2021), when everybody both old and young do not have adequate economic, physical and social access to food, then it can be said there is food insecurity. In sub-Saharan African states Nigeria has been identified as one that is vulnerable to climatic change (Ughaelu,

2017). Some researchers such as Ayinde, Muchie and Olatunji, 2011; Ughaelu, 2017 and Ikem, (2018), Nigerian food productivity and human suffering have worsened in the past decade due to the intermittent environmental disasters. In 2012 Nigeria experienced heavy losses in human lives, livestock, crops and as well as human displacement due to severe flooding that has not been recorded in the country in the past decades (Ogbuchi, 2020). The changes in environmental conditions brought by climate change affect the six vegetative zones of Nigeria differently (Ughaelu, 2017). Studies have shown that desertification, high rainfall and flooding have adverse consequences for food production (Tirado, Clarke, Jaykusc, McQuatters-Gollop, & Frank, 2010; Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018; Uwazie, 2020).

The reason for food security crises currently facing Nigeria is the persistent fall of rainfall gradient in northern parts of Nigeria (Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018). Also, Nigeria has witnessed crop damages, loss of soil fertility, soil toxicity and disruption of soil ecosystem due to persistent flooding of coastlines and southern most part of Nigeria (Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018). The Food and Agricultural organization and World Bank have warned that serious danger is pose to sustainable food production in Nigeria due to climate change (World Bank, 2016; FAO, 2017). Climate change has adverse effect on agricultural productivity in Nigeria leading to lowered productive outputs, with short fall and disruptions in food, and hike in prices of food. The era of food insecurity is becoming intensified across Nigeria as a result of climatic factors which have limited agricultural productivity. Droughts, heavy precipitation, flooding of farmlands; rising temperature, increasing aridity and soil acidity, changes in relative humidity, increase evaporation, among others are induced by climate change with adverse effect on agricultural productivity and food systems in Nigeria (Ani, Anyika, & Mutambara, 2021). Similarly, the livelihood of some 15 million pastoralists in northern Nigeria are threatened by decreasing access to water and pasture shortages linked to climate change (Onuoha & Ezirim, 2010).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study employs adaptation and frustration-aggression theories as its theoretical orientation. According to King (2018), adaptation is a situation of adjusting to expected or actual climate and its effects to avoid harm or exploit beneficial opportunities resulting in migration. Charles Darwin and Alfred Russell Wallace whose studies in the 1830s in the Galapagos Islands established a fixed relationship between organism and its habitat. They believed that the evolution of organisms was connected in some way with adaptation of organisms to changing environmental conditions (King, 2018). Changes in weather patterns and increasing extreme events due to climate change often affect farmers, especially in areas reliant on rain for water in their subsistence agriculture (FAO, 2019; Portal, Xie, Challinor, Cochrane, Howden, Iqbal, Lobell, Travasso, 2014). Under climate change, farmers and pastoralists in Sahel region largely experience increasing variability of both rainfall and temperature which are detrimental to crop plant growth to accelerate poverty. With this conditions, therefore, a range of risk reduction strategies, is employed by households including migration (Jaeger, Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, Sunde, & Bonin, 2010). Migration is often considered as a form of climate change adaptation by which individuals, households, and communities seek to reduce the risks associated with climate change. So migration becomes an effective adaptation strategy for people in climate-vulnerable settings, who lack other options. The migration of cattle herders across Nigeria has no doubt caused frustrations among farmers and herdsmen in many rural communities leading to deadly aggressions. It is argued that the violent conflicts resulting from

climate change militate against food security and agribusiness development to generate poverty in Nigeria (Vinke, Rottmann, Gornott, Zabre, Nayna, Schwerdtle, & Sauerborn, 2021).

Frustration-Aggression Theory formulated by (Dollard, Doob, Miller, Mowrer & Sears 1939, cited in Sturmey, 2017), presupposes that the existence of frustration always leads to some form of aggression. The consequences of frustration includes among the migrated cattle herders and farmers has resulted in mass killings and destruction of property with attendant poverty in Kaduna, Kogi, Zamfara, Benue, Nasarawa, Bornu, Sokoto villages including villages in south west, south south and south east. The grazing of farmers farmlands and crops by herders' cattle with impunity elicit reactions and frustration from farmers leading to the killings of herd of cattle belonging to the herders. Reaction as reprisal from cattle herders, has always been disastrous by ventilating aggression not only to the farmers but also to individuals not responsible for the cause of their frustration, by killing, sacking people from their homes and burning down villages. Instance s of this abound in the invasions of a Catholic church in Ayar Mbalom village in Benue state by suspected herdsmen killing two priests and seventeen parishioners during morning mass on April 24, 2018. After the incident, 16 more villagers were killed in Ali Agundu and Tsav Council wards of Guma Local Government Area (Linda Ikeji, 2018). There is also a case of another massacre of over a hundred persons in Barakin-Ladi and Ri (Nnanwube, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes secondary methods of data gathering. This means using related ideas already presented by other researchers to enhance the study. The secondary sources of data used in the study were basically from textbooks, journals, news papers, the internet, among others. Finally historical analysis was employed for the analysis of the objectives of the paper

ANALYSIS

The effects of climate change on farming activities in Sahel region

The Sahel has been characterized by irregular rainfalls with strong climatic variations which increasingly posed impediment to food security and accelerates poverty in the region. Climate changes have obvious and dire consequences for food supply and poverty, and its phenomenon is a wider threat to the world's productive capacity. Climate change and poverty are deeply mutually inclusive because climate change affects poor people in low-income countries around the world. The poor is further made vulnerable or unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change including climate variability and extremes, and thereby exacerbates existing inequalities and poverty through its effects on the economy, health, and human rights (Rayner & Malone, 2001). The phenomenon of climate change is about persistent, irreversible land degradation. It is a phenomenon that is more long-term than droughts, with a progressive land degradation. The Sahel countries are affected by desertification with degraded land that can rarely be reclaimed for agriculture. Also the effect of drought and floods, are equally devastating because they result in land degradation and lose of fertility with insufficient rainfall leading to the withering of crops for lack of water to keep the crops with constant flow of water and deaths of livestock for lack of drinking water. So the food security implications are obvious, resulting in the progressive loss of fertile land, that have made the local Sahel population increasingly difficult to sustain subsistence agricultural practices. This is because of the vicious cycles of desertification, droughts, and floods, leading to crop.

Degraded land also destroys natural habitats with human food security effects. For example, desertification in the Sahel has caused loss of biodiversity, including animals around the Sahara Desert. The extinction of animals and birds both in the arid and non-arid zones, has undermined hunting and food security. The once vast freshwater Lake Chad, spanning the borders of Chad, Cameroon, Niger and Nigeria, stands as a stark illustration of desertification, having shrunk by 90% from over 25,000 square kilometres in the 1960s to just 2,500 square kilometres today (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015). The flow rates of the lake's two principal feeding rivers, the Chari and Logone, have fallen progressively over recent decades due to drought, a gradual overall decrease in rainfall and increased water demand. The region has suffered the consequences of declining fish stocks in the lake and the erosion of surrounding farmlands (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015). The ecological factors in Sahel region include, climate change and the none availability of natural resources have caused majority of the population in the four countries, to migrate in search of more favourable ecological conditions in other countries . For instance, a lot of migrants have illegally migrated as a result of climate change (such as extreme weather events); crop failure, and scarcity of food to Nigeria with abundance natural resources and minerals. These favourable climatic conditions, constitute one of the major reasons for immigration into Nigeria as many multinational companies that are interested in the abundant mineral resources in the country come to establish in the parts of the country where the mineral resources they need, are located (Ihuoma, 2021).

The impacts of climate change in the Sahel region, have negatively affected individuals' rights to life, health, housing, food, water and sanitation. The majority of people's livelihoods in the Sahel region rely on agriculture, pastoralism or fishing, and these livelihoods are deeply affected by climate change. Apart from agriculture human resource needed for the cultivation of crops is affected by climate change with significant impacts on the rights to life and health. Rising sea levels in coastal areas also results in an increase risk of mortality, injuries, physical ill-health, and mental health conditions. Flooding and heavy rainfall may heighten vulnerability to water or insect-borne diseases, while dry seasons and drought can increase the potential for people to consume unsafe water (United Nations 2021). So it is clear that Sahel region faces many challenges as climate change threatens add to land degradation, destroy vegetation, shrink water resources and food systems, loss of biodiversity and arable land losses through increased incidences of desertification, drought and floods.

Migration of cattle herders as a threat to food security

Climate change constitutes a major threat to food security and result in poverty in Nigeria. The phenomenon through its various manifestations evolve violent conflicts thereby disrupting public safety, to undermined food security and investment. As safety is elusive, there is individual and collective reduction in access to available important natural resources resulting in unprecedented poverty. The inability to access natural resources ultimately hampers the capacity of individual to act in ways that could promote food security and enhance productivity. Population displacement is often rampant due to drastic drop in agricultural output cause by flood, drought and desertification thereby accelerate poverty and want. According to Odo (2012), climate events have undoubtedly led to violent conflicts and insurgency in parts of Nigeria. For instance, Vanguard (2023), reported on 9th April 400 die in 3 weeks following intense killings by suspected herders in Benue state. This is a clear indication that there is strong nexus between climate change and farmer-herder conflicts in various parts of Nigeria. This specific example is not an isolated case in Nigeria as it applies to other African countries. With this killings human resource needed for agricultural production are depleted and those

alive are living in perpetual fear of being attacked and poverty. Crops and other agricultural activities in Sahel region are rain-watered, making the countries particularly sensitive to climate change vulnerable. For instance, according to a 2013 World Bank report on Nigeria, the impacts of climate change in Nigeria were discovered to have a declined productivity of livestock and a long-term reduction in crop yields from 20–30 percent, with unpleasant effects on livelihoods, worsening prospects for food security and generate poverty (Cervigni, Valentini, & Santini 2013). Climate change is challenging Nigeria's goal of food security and a competitive agricultural sector, particularly states in semi-arid areas like the Adamawa state and others are particularly vulnerable to climate change and further pauperizing the vulnerable farmers. The state has experienced inadequate rainfall, serious droughts, and floods have brought low agricultural yields and negatively impacted the state's agricultural productive capacity. Rigaud, Sherbinin, Jones, Abu-Ata, and Adamo (2021), opined that the impact of climate change and its effects on people's livelihoods is being experienced in the Sahelian region. Adding that the climate change has caused the scarcity of natural resources leading to migration and conflict between the nomadic and farmers resulting in poverty and mutual suspicion among them and the nation in general. See figure (1) below showing the migration of cattle as evidence of the real situation.

Figure (1) below,

Photo: Adopted from Davis,2022

Migration largely becomes an option due to the amount of land available for grazing keeps shrinking and the disruptions of livestock migration routes by farms. Also in the course of cattle grazing the land a lots of them go into farmers' farm to graze and damage crops resulting to conflict and poverty. Many pastoralists see the farms as encroaching on their traditional tribal land. This claim and counter-claim often generated violent conflicts between farmers and herders. With death toll of more than 15, 000 since 2010 in West and Central Africa, more than half of which have occurred since 2018. Olobatoke and Amusian (2017), found that both the farmers and herders lose their houses to attacks and reprisals resulting from the encroachments. Farmers constantly live in fear of being attacked by killer herdsmen making their farming environment insecure. (Nweze 2005 in Ofuoku and Isife, 2009), also observed

that there are many casualties among farmers as conflicts keep recording in many states including Benue, Plateau, Jigawa, Nasarawa, Kebbi, Imo, Borno, Oyo, and Zamfara. Nasarawa state recorded the highest number of deaths at 47 casualties in a conflict which was sustained for two days. Many farmers across Nigeria have experienced colossal loss of agricultural investments worth huge amounts to the burning of their plantations by herdsmen, harvesting of mature plants to feed cattle, and the routine grazing of cattle on foliage causing unmitigated poverty. In some instances, certain agribusiness entrepreneurs have experienced this menace for about ten years. The Cable (2017), reports the destruction and burning of 20 hectares of cassava plantations and orange worth 200 billion naira, belonging to a former top government official in Kwara state. Olobatoke and Amusian (2017), found that farmers and herders alike lose their crops and cattle to attacks and reprisals resulting from the encroachments. In their study of Kogi state, about 69.60% of farmers abandoned their farmlands partly due to low productivity. This is supported by Nweze (2005 in Ofuoku & Isife, 2009), who also observed that many herders have lost their herds which has also led to dwindling productivity in their herds. Olanipeku (2018), also reported a similar incidence on a farmland belonging to another former top government official who disclosed that herders burnt his farm as a yearly routine to enable fresh grasses spring up in days for their cattle to graze on. From these incidences crops damaged include: oil palm, yam, and cassava plantations in Ondo state. In another incidence, herdsmen set ablaze 100 acres of mangoes and pineapples in Osun state, and about 200 plants of tomato and cucumber in Ikoyi town.

The incidences can also reduce the labour availability for agribusiness owners, and also lead to high production cost in value added goods occasioned by scarcity of primary goods. Such can also rob young agribusiness entrepreneurs of their life savings and investments in one night of conflict from unregulated grazing and bush burning, to the effect of aggravating unemployment and poverty (Nnanwube, 2021). In 2011, deaths toll rose to 116 spread across Abuja, Cross River, Plateau, Benue, Imo, Nasarawa, Katsina, and Zamfara. In same year, Benue attacks which recorded 27 deaths in February and 38 deaths in June being the highest for the year, displaced people with an alleged engagement of herdsmen from Lake Chad (Nnanwube, 2021). It has been observed that the loss of products in storage and reduction in the output and income of farmers negatively affect their savings, credit repayment ability, as well as the economic welfare of urban dwellers who depend on rural farmers for food supply and consequently discouraging farming and rural economic development. This is most glaring in instances of farmers abandoning their farms for fear of insecurity (Nnanwube, 2021).

In Sahel, climate change is making life far more difficult for many pastoralists. The animals need water, but droughts and poor water management have dried up springs and streams, driving herdsmen south, into areas where farming is prevalent. Rainy seasons are becoming more variable, and there have been some devastating droughts. One of the worst, in 2010, killed more than 4.8 million head of cattle in Niger, about a quarter of the country's herd, at an economic cost of more than \$700 million (Davis, 2022). Forced migration due to climate change is directly affecting the peace and security of every Sahel country with increased clashes between nomadic herdsmen and farmers over land use and ownership, resulting in food insecurity (United Nations, 2021). From Chad to Mauritania, the amount of droughts and floods has serious effects on the populations who largely depended on agriculture and livestock for their livelihoods. Furthermore, the scarcity of water resources threatens livelihoods, droughts are more intense, temperatures rising faster than in the rest of the world, climate change causing heavy rains, land drying to absorb the rising waters, destructive river floods and numerous flooding, results in food shortages and widespread poverty (Mayans, 2020).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Focusing on the Sahel in Africa – a region covering Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Guinea, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal and the Gambia, with agriculture as the main source of livelihood of the majority of the people living in the area. Increases in temperature or modifications in rainfall quantities and distribution substantially impact on the natural resource on which agriculture depends. The vulnerability of their livelihoods based on agriculture and migration of herders exacerbate poverty, environmental degradation and violent conflict with great impact on food security. It is recommended that a comprehensive programs on water management and irrigation, desertification control, development of alternative sources of energy and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices by farmers should be the priority concerns of the various governments in the Sahel region. Individuals, families, and communities should not use migration as a strategy for adapting to changing environmental conditions to avoid violent conflict. Migration should be made a choice to the people by the government by investing adequate resources to mitigate a rapidly heating climate. Local communities, including migrants, should be at the centre of building solutions instead of fermenting trouble over ownership of resources. States, including those in the Sahel, as well as regional stakeholders and the international community, should take action on the current and future impacts of climate change causing food insecurity and poverty. It is clear that when food security is affected by climate change, states have an obligation to act and prevent food shortage. Therefore, government should deploy the policies, resources and technologies they need to mitigate and adapt to food and water crises by paying urgent attention to the provision of adequate welfare services including access to drinking water, to help the greatest number of poor populations facing scarcity of resources, to promote water for people, water for agriculture and water for livestock, to support local authorities and the community for better water management and governance in the Sahel. The use of biofuel should be encouraged to reduce the use of fossil fuels and the Nigeria Immigration Service should ensure border tight environment to discourage illegal influx of herders to Nigeria, to reduce violent conflict over resources.

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Politics And The Crisis Of Development In 21st Century Africa: A Study Of Nigeria's 4th Republic

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ABSTRACT

Much of contemporary Africa is replete with under-development. Though previous and extant attempts to address this condition have failed (perhaps because either they lack outright efficacy to achieve the desired results or due to human factors), still, the undesirable condition needs to be reversed. Civilized society desires order, evolves a structure incorporating both individual freedom and a clear set of rules for interpersonal relationships. Similarly, civilized society appreciates the need for a characteristic and effective set of principles for assigning basic rights, duties, and burdens of social cooperation amid responsibility. And the adequacy or otherwise of such principles has corresponding effect on development. With the lacunae in Nigeria's Fourth Republic in focus and adopting the Institutional and the Developing State Theories, this paper adopted some qualitative methodology and analyzed the issues about development (in its modern sense) and its lack in contemporary Africa. Accordingly, the work indicated that development would elope the continent of Africa because contemporary politicking and governance (from the experience in Nigeria's 4th Republic) is marred by corruption. The work however suggests practical routes out of the conundrum.

Keywords: Africa, development, Nigeria/4th republic, politics

INTRODUCTION

Injustice and corruption are a serious bane of development in Africa. Yet one of the most or foremost virtues of the individual, society, and institutions is justice or the idea of justice. This is because every society desires order and thus evolves a system or structure which incorporates both individual freedom and a fair distribution of goods and other interpersonal relationships. In other words, civilized society appreciates the need for (and is always prepared to affirm) a characteristic set of principles to adopt for assigning basic rights and duties, and for determining the criteria to adopt for fair and proper distribution of benefits and burdens of social cooperation. It could be indicated that the adequacy or otherwise of such principles has corresponding effect on development. Accountability is necessary for principles to be effective. Perhaps this is why public officials are required to swear to some oath of allegiance as a premise for social responsibility. Accordingly, it shall be argued that an efficacious oath system along with social, moral, legal, and individual responsibility and accountability are necessary to achieve justice, peace, and development in society—particularly the African society. We shall proceed by discussing alternative conceptions of justice, development, oath-taking and accountability, and thereafter indicate their interrelationships.

Certainly, most Third World countries are naturally endowed in both material and human resources; yet, pathetically, some of these countries are so underdeveloped despite this natural resources advantage. The plundering of the resources of these countries during colonialism has largely been responsible for this present situation. Even though some of the countries in the Third World have found their path to development, others (mainly African) have not. There abound a number of factors deduced to the present condition of Africa which might be termed as development crisis—since the continent has remained largely underdeveloped regardless of the presence of huge natural resources (gold, cocoa, bauxite, oil, diamond, timber) amid abundant human resource-presence. For instance, several decades after the end of colonialism, most parts of Africa is still fighting with problems such as high poverty rate, corruption, lack of basic infrastructural facilities in all sectors of the economy, unemployment, high mortality rate, political instability and insecurity of lives and property. The discourse on development issues is very topical. It is impossible to talk about development without referring to concepts such as poverty, production, the notion of the state, or equality. These concepts initially became prominent since early modernity/Western history; and only then have they (issues about development) been projected on the rest of the world (Sachs, 1992, 5). For example, Ghana touted as one of the best democratic and politically stable countries in Africa and Nigeria the most heavily populated African country, according to the United Nations Human Development Report in 2011, ranked 135 and 156 respectively out of 187 countries (UN, 2011). However, and against the backdrop of Africa's developmental crisis, there has been a surge in the discourse on how to initiate positive policies/programmes. This debate is, perhaps, a blistering one; and it is dominated by two main related themes, namely: the argument over the actual meaning of the concept of development and the appropriate pathway to development (Ikenna, 2009). However, despite the multi-dimensional or divergent approaches among (local and international scholars, global policy makers and institutions over these issues), they are numerous attempts have been made to understand and solve the crisis of development in Africa.

Accordingly, this paper aims to examine the nature of and issues about development/underdevelopment in general and to examine the factors responsible for the lingering underdevelopment in Africa with special focus on Nigeria. We shall therefore review the performance of politics in contemporary Nigeria (as an instance for contemporary African

states). The work shall articulate the nature, adequacy or otherwise of principles of politics on development based on the experience in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. It shall also suggest possible pathways for the realization of development in the African continent.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Politics

This relates to the (nature or acquisition of) power and those who control its distribution/exercise in the society/state concerned. Politics portends the prior existence of established political organizations and governmental institutions. Politics have to do with power relations in a social/public context. Hence in contemporary times, nations' political activities drive both all national activity and international relations. Popular description holds that politics involves citizens' activities in getting what, when, and how.

Development

By *development* is meant to include the human and material improvements in the various African states. Development is entailed in material/physical structures; it also implies economic growth, increased welfare, and human enhancement; it entails modernization, dialectical transformation and capacity building. But while Willis (2005) considers it essentially in modernity and progress, Peet and Hartwick (1999) think it in terms of improvement in standard of living by the poor. Similarly, Todaro (2011) considers development in material sense at the level of production output reflected in improved GDP. Thus the exact meaning of development has been one of controversy. Thus, the term, development is used in variety of ways. In its traditional application, the term is often equated with growth in per capita income. But development scholars and development agencies (such as the World Bank, IMF, etc.) have since the 1970s, other indicators of development have become widely used by The meeting of basic needs (or, equivalently, reduction in absolute poverty), the creation of modern employment opportunities, and the achievement of a less unequal distribution of income have all become important criteria in determining level of development (Todaro & Smith, 2003). Moreover, development "development must therefore be conceived of as a multidimensional process involving major changes in social structures, popular attitudes, and national institutions, as well as the acceleration of economic growth, the reduction of inequality and the eradication of poverty" (Todaro and Smith, 2012, 16). Their position presupposes that development is not purely an economic phenomenon but rather a multi-dimensional process involving reorganization and reorientation of entire economic and social system and is a process of improving the quality of all human lives with some equally important aspects (serving basic components or core values, serving as a conceptual basis and practical guideline for comprehending the inner meaning of development). Nevertheless the core values are sustenance, self-esteem and freedom—which represent universal goal sought after by individual and society (Todaro and Smith, 2012, 16).

On his part, Sen (1999) describes development strictly as converse to that of economic point of view. According to him, all individuals are gifted with certain set of capabilities while it is simply a matter of realizing these capabilities that will allow a person to escape from poverty and achieve freedom—illiteracy, poor health, malnutrition, amongst others, are a few indicators of its lack. Sen further expands the critical interpretations of freedom by examining five elemental forms of instrumental freedoms: political freedoms, economic facilities, social opportunities, transparency guarantee, and protective security and lays emphasis on the fact that, the five forms of freedom are complementary, interrelated and inextricable. In this way,

his presupposes that individual freedom must comprise of the five for an individual to realize his or her potentials. Further, development implies advancement and growth in any organized state, both in quantitative and qualitative terms: establishment of structures, building of attitudes, institutions—economic, social, political, religious, and legal.

Development is positive in nature. In some sense, development implies a comparative state of affairs: between past state of the same society, or between two or more societies—a matter of per capita income. Specifically, development is also a strategy of spatial reorganization crucial for the whole process of political mobilization and central state control of the planning of productive forces, not necessarily centralized at just a point. This means that development is the exploitation of nature, education, human capacity for social upliftment. Human development connotes enhancement of man's thought and rationality, purity, and being; plus the moral uprightness of individuals. A society of moral individuals is already one with a foundation for infrastructural development—involving the provision of amenities, services, and other physical and technological structures for man's use. Whether in human or infrastructural aspects, the overriding aims of development are that: one, to provide citizens with the basic necessities of life (food, shelter, clothing, security, freedom); and, two, to free man from all forms of human misery, ignorance, servitude, and dependence. Hence purposive national development plan must reflect those two ideals—human and material. However, present study shall consider development to mean qualitative and quantitative improvement in all aspects of human endeavor—whether economic, political, cultural, environmental, and/or social. Somehow, these are lacked in Africa.

Underdevelopment

Under-development is adapted to include the socio-political and economic quandary, governmental inefficiencies, failures leading to several societal malaises and injustices on the continent of Africa. Under-development is the absence of those indices of development. It could be said that imperialism/colonialism is the cause of underdevelopment in Africa. But it is common knowledge that not all African states that emerged from colonialism. Similarly, Marxists hold that every state of society is a historical phase in the history of such society. But some societies under capitalism have developed without revolution. Modernization theorists would want us to believe that development comes naturally, as a product of handwork, and that traditional social structures, such as kinship, ethnicity, extended family, superstition, hinder it. Yet there still are those who hold that development is a product of historical and political evolution. Thus none of these theories can wholly account for the continuing underdevelopment in Africa indicated in hunger, want, insecurity, and lack of social amenities/infrastructures. Corruption and injustice seem a bane to the achievement of development in Africa. And it has become a crisis.

Agreeably, every people have developed in one way or another to a greater or lesser extent; hence underdevelopment is not merely the absence of development. Underdevelopment only makes sense as a means of comparing levels of development. It is very much tied to the fact that human social development has been uneven and from a strictly economic view-point some human groups have advanced further by producing more and becoming wealthier (Rodney, 1972:21). Underdevelopment can also be explained in terms of relationship of exploitation of one country by another—implying that underdeveloped states are a product of capitalist, imperialist and colonialist exploitation. Accordingly, Rodney (1972, 22) concludes that "...if underdevelopment were related to anything other than comparing economies, then the most underdeveloped countries in the world would be the USA, which practices external oppression

on a massive scale, while internally there is a blend of exploitation, brutality and psychiatric disorder.”

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Generally, a theory is “an idea or belief about something arrived at through assumption and in some cases a set of facts, propositions, or principles analyzed in their relation to one another and used especially in science to explain a phenomena” (Obasi, 2000: 38-39). To have any value, “a theory must explain or suggest ways of explaining why a subject matter has certain characteristics; that is, it must have explanatory, predictive, and problem-solving value and not just an intellectual exercise that simply seek to provide new sets of categories of paradigm(s)” (Obadan, 2012). Therefore, the usefulness of theories in providing us with the context and foundation for our research cannot be overemphasized. Scholars have propounded quite a number of theories in explain socio-economic and political phenomena. However, for the purpose of this work, we adopt the institutional and developing state theories.

Dependency Theory

There are many perspectives on the *Dependency Theory* (DT). For instance, one view (Wikipedia, 2022) considers DT as “the notion that resources flow from a *periphery* of poor and underdeveloped states to a *core* of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former”. By and large, the central claim of dependency theorists is that rich countries accumulated their wealth through exploiting poorer countries. This implies that the substance of DT is that underdevelopment is mainly caused by the peripheral position of affected countries in the world economy. Thus the implication of DT is that the people/leadership of less-developed countries may not be blame for the failure of their societies to develop rather, Western/developed nations deliberately failed to develop their oversea less developed countries. The idea of state exploitation was initially established through the institution of colonialism and slavery. But by many states achieving independence mostly in the 20th century, state exploitative exploitation of another/other(s) became achievable through neo-colonialism (web).

Historically, however, DT was first proposed in the late 1950s by the Argentine economist and statesman, Raul Prebisch. But by the nineteen sixties and nineteen seventies, DT had started to enjoy much recognition, patronage, and prominence. In conclusion, DT holds that “the nature of our social formations is dependent on how they are integrated with the world capitalist system” (web). In today's realm, dependency thoughts are still “useful in analyzing the widening inequalities between the poor and rich countries, or in analyzing the divisions within a developed or a developing country context” (web).

In a special way, this work applies the *Institutional Theory* (IT) to underscore the pivotal role of both government and its agencies saddled with the major responsibility of governance and to galvanize grassroots development. The Institutional Theory examines the processes and mechanisms by which structures, schemas, rules, and routines become established as authoritative guidelines for social behavior. It asks how such systems come into existence, how they diffuse, and what role they play in supplying stability and meaning to social behavior. It also considers how such arrangements deteriorate and collapse, and how their remnants shape successor structures (Scott, 2005). IT assumes that organizational actions are limited by normative regulations (Donaldson, 1995; Krajnovic, 2018), and the room for manoeuver by individuals is narrowed due to the presence of institutions that impose the modus operandi (Scott, 2005). A major argument of the institutional theory is that the behavior and functioning

of the organization in the same industry is imposed by the institution, not the market itself (Meyer & Rowan, 1997). According to Sanchawa (2015), IT considers public policy as an output by government institutions as it is authoritatively determined, implemented and enforced by them. Sanchawa explained further that IT draws a very strong relationship between public policy and government institutions because there cannot be a public policy except it is opted, implemented and enforced by some governmental institution(s). In other words, the success(or lack) of public policy objective(s) could be linked to strength or weakness of governmental institutions to effect public policy legitimately—including the legal obligations to command loyalty of the citizens universally, and apply legitimate reprimand for violators.

By this theory, the failure of any government implies the failure of its institutions, agencies, and citizens—which can never assure of development. Accordingly, the theory of the *Developmental State* (DS) is deployed to support the institutional one to properly situate developmental condition of Nigeria(or Africa) vis-à-vis those among some successful states elsewhere around the developed world. Historically, the theory of the DS was first deployed especially in Japan after the devastating destructions of the Second War.

THE DEVELOPMENTAL PROBLEMS IN NIGERIA: A BRIEF HISTORICAL APPROACH

History offers the opportunity to account for a past, understand the present, and project the future. Nigeria's history is replete with myriad problems ranging from palpable economic recession, to political violence and social evils such as corruption and immorality. These have had grave consequences for social justice cum development. It is important to note that pre-colonial "Nigeria" was a number of "independent" kingdoms, empires and emirates under traditional rulers revered as "semi-divine" and who had powers of life and death on their subjects; powers of taxation, punishment and reward. During that era, justice was seen as the fiat of the ruler. Having amalgamated the North and the South of the colony into a united country in 1914 (despite their apparent and ominous cultural and political experiences), Lord Lugard became Nigeria's first leader (as Governor-General). Well, the antecedents of development had shown a fundamental difference in their respective aspirations. For instance, the south operated a system of political leadership from the grass roots and the people remained the custodian of their own rights before the intrusion of the British. Yet in the North, the Fulani Emirs emerged, as in coup imposed on the people, destroyed the political antecedent of the society with minimum resistance; maintained the interest of the ruling class, selfishly against that of the mass of the people. However, the newly introduced British system of indirect rule paid off in the North; the system permitted the Emir to rule through their family-heads as Chiefs. Thus place of native authority (in the North) marked the emergence of aristocratic political leadership in Nigeria—a condition that has continued to threaten the unity of the country till date.

The 1946 Richard's constitution divided southern Nigeria into West and East, leaving the North intact, with Ibadan, Enugu, and Kaduna as regional centers of power, and Lagos the seat of colonial authority. Each Region had a Lieutenant Governor, all under the Governor-General in Lagos. This pattern remained until independence in 1960. We must state here that the British arrangement was unjust and marked off ethnic suspicion in Nigeria's political history (Adewale 1981, 20). Political (regional) leaders thus emerged along the lines of constitutional/ethnic demarcations—the ensuing rivalries coupled with corruption culminated in military take-over in 1966. The rage in the then Western house of Assembly, the disaffections of the census and election results and the emergent kidnapping and killing culminated into the Nigeria's first Military coup on January 15, 1966; and a 30-month civil war

ensued (the secessionist Biafra surrendered on January 15th, 1970, although the discontent continued in the mind of the defeated East. This condition ignited uneven developmental opportunities in the future country.

Successive military regimes thrived on the Nigerian scene from 1966 (with civilian interregnum between 1979 and 1983) till 1999. Big revenue from oil boom emerged; and engaged in full scale financial proficiency and let go the rare golden opportunity of industrializing Nigeria. Gowon was forcibly succeeded by short-lived Murtala Muhammed and later General Obasanjo who honorably but hurriedly handed back power to civilians in 1979. Unfortunately, the civilians of the second republic were grovelingly corrupt. They killed, stole and looted Nigeria. No wonder the military, hungry for power, had reasons to bounce back on December 31st, 1983. Both Buhari and Idiagbon ruled Nigeria with iron fist and medieval inordinacy between 1983 and 1984 before General Babangida overthrew them in 1985. Although Babangida was also ruthless, he established and funded two political parties for the nations. The ensuing elections of 1993 were perceived to have been won by M.K.O. Abiola but were arbitrarily annulled by Babangida, who soon consequently “stepped aside” for a stooge Chief Shonekan in 1993, who himself was subtly overthrown by Abacha in few months. Abacha’s was maximum reign of terror until his mysterious death on June 8, 1998, and under the chaos, General Abubakar Abdusalami emerged as Head of State (Uroh, 1998, 17). However, the situation has degenerated to one of untold crises.

So, historically, the basic issues and problems with the Nigerian political project could be succinctly isolated. A few instances could suffice. The truncated Second Republic did not fare better than the First—since both Shagari and his officials were all soaked in the sea of corruption (Nzeribe, 2017). There were reports of corruption against General Gowon’s government in the early 70s (Campbell, 1981); and the so-called ‘Cement Armada scandal’ marred Gen. Murtala’s government (Afolabi, 1993). It is common belief that Generals Babangida and Abacha institutionalized official and popular corruption in Nigeria (Gboyega, 1996; Osaghae, 2002). Ever since, such attitudes sow the seed of underdevelopment. Unfortunately, that seed has thrived most robustly since the Fourth Republic.

Concerning the current conditions in Nigeria (Africa), Uroh (1998) claims it is “...a crisis of development, the problem is necessarily multidimensional...equally socio-cultural as well as moral; is a product of Africa’s chequered history.” Perhaps he holds it a crisis because development is “a rise in the standard of living of a people...a progressive elimination of poverty, unemployment, social inequalities, authoritarian political structures...” One may ask, what led to this embarrassing state of affairs? It is arguable that our immediate post-independence leaders did not have long vision for their various states and they simply channeled their energies to the attainment of political independence. This degenerated with the corrupt/immoral character of the hegemonic class and the devastating role of successive military regimes, dictatorship and wars on the continent. Today, individualism and self-enrichment is the order of the day. According to Claude Ake (2005), “...alienations, resentment, inefficiency, and corruption” are manifestations of underdevelopment. Ake further holds that “all the African countries that are supposed to be sponsoring NEPAD have been adjudged very corrupt by Corruption Perception Index (CPI) survey of 2002, hence Nigeria, Madagascar, Kenya, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Angola are all wallowing in corrupt practices” (Ake, 2005).

A general conception holds that corruption is any act undertaken either to satisfy oneself or a favored candidate, but act which deviates from social norms. It could be in form of bribery, misappropriation, misapplication or misallocation on ethnic or nepotism grounds. It could be

planned/institutional; it could be endemic—involving all and sundry; and it could be developmental (that in the guise of performing contract in which the public official indirectly amass wealth to himself). In Nigeria for example, 'blocking' or 'settlement' or '10%' is commonplace. Some of the most indices of corruption include: self-interest, laziness, economic crunch, poverty, unnecessary bottlenecks attached with service rendering, absence of effective monitoring, absence or ineffectiveness of anti-graft agencies, and capitalist ideology. The manifestation of all these is underdevelopment—loss of faith, timidity, criminality, delinquency, deviance, capital flight, inefficiency, lack of infrastructure, instability, and violence. To account for this condition, a number of theories compete.

Alternative Theories of Development and Underdevelopment

A development theory must be one of the (rival and subsidiary) theories that critique, revise, sum and offer broad explanatory frameworks on development (Pieterse, 2009). Thus, a development theory must comprise of *development concept/strategy*. Development theories are often inter-disciplinary and problem-solving oriented. There are many theories of development; let's discuss a few.

Modernization theory emerged in the 1950s as an explanation of how the industrial societies of North America and Western Europe. It developed is one of the theories that explained the pathway to development; it gained fame in the 1950s. The theory posits that societies develop in fairly predictable stages through which they become increasingly complex. Development depends primarily on the importation of technology as well as a number of other political and social changes believed to come about as a result. According to *modernization theories*, endogenous factors (such as tradition, illiteracy, population, agrarian structures, low division of labor, low scale level of communication and infrastructure) are answerable for underdevelopment in the affected countries. However, Rostow (Rostow, 1990) outlines an optimistic scenario by positing five stages of economic development which all societies in one point in time will transcend to realizing development. However its appeal, Modernization theory has been criticized in that it is Eurocentric; that it ignores the fact that development is not a linear process as it claims it to be; and that it ignores the history and culture of different groups of people and society.

Dependency Theory This seeks to explain development and underdevelopment in more rational tones. Dependency is defined as a 'situation in which a certain number of countries have their economy conditioned by the development and expansion of another' (Greig, Hulme and Turner, 2007; Dos Santos, 1978, 544). For instance, Frank (1970) postulates that the underdevelopment of undeveloped countries is an indication of the unequal and unfavourable conditions they found themselves in the world's capitalist system. The dependency theory rejects development argument that any relationship between the traditional and the modern societies would culminate into mutual benefits or gains. For them, the possibility of peripheral development is hindered by this relationship (Greig, Hulme and Turner, 2007). Frank (1970, 8) illustrates further how poorest countries and most remote part of Latin America had been historically linked to the world capitalist system and how this relationship and contact between tradition and modernity led to underdevelopment. So, in a nutshell, the main thrust of the dependency school of thought in expatiating development and underdevelopment discourse has to do with core-peripheral relationship in the world capitalist system and how the system has a negative repercussion on the periphery states. Thus Frank used the core-periphery nexus to refer to the industrialized/developed and underdeveloped/poor nations respectively.

Alternative Development Theory This perspective emerged in the 1970s and it explains how development can be engineered across space and especially in the underdeveloped part of the world of which Africa continent is an integral part. It is essential to note the fact that, dissatisfaction with mainstream development led to movement of alternative development. By mainstream development is meant the meta-narratives or grand theories to development which include the modernization and dependency schools of thought. Another Alternative view is that development should be geared to the satisfaction of needs, endogenous and self-reliant and in harmony with the environment. Whether this was meant to be an alternative practice of development apart from the main-stream or whether it is to change mainstream development is not quite settled (Pieterse, 1998). Thus the Alternative Development stride is directed to see to the extent local (traditional) and expert (modern) could deploy the bottom up approach with the objectives directed at the provision of basic needs of citizens. A critical question is whether alternative development is an alternative way of achieving development, broadly sharing the same goals as mainstream development but using different means, participatory and people-centered which is conversely to the mainstream development theories which focus on the state as their agent. It would seem this way if we consider the huge increase of development funds being directed through NGOs during the past two decades which now surpass the total annual disbursements through the IMF and World Bank. Despite the new dimension brought on board by the alternative development in the development and underdevelopment discourse with focus on NGOs and local actors as its agents, it is not devoid of censures. For instance, it lacks sufficient theoretical cohesion and there exist varying understandings of what is alternative development and what is not. However, one insight to DT is *neo-liberalism*.

Neo-liberalism This perspective in development theory is the introduction of under the principle of globalization. Neo-liberalism is in the first instance a theory of political economic practices that proposes that human well-being can best be advanced by liberating individual entrepreneurial freedoms and skills within an institutional framework characterized by strong private property rights, free markets and free trade. The role of the state is to create and preserve an institutional framework appropriate to such practices. The state has to guarantee, for example, the quality and integrity of money. It must also set up those military, defense, police and legal structures and functions required to secure private property rights and to guarantee, by force if need be, the proper functioning of markets' (Thorsen and Lie). Neo-liberalism rests on economic liberalization, free trade, open markets, privatization, deregulation and enhancing the role of private sector in society with the minimal role of the state in the economy (for instance, *Structural Adjustment Program* was packaged for the developing countries which several African countries including Nigeria, Ghana, and Zambia keyed into).

Essentially, the Structural Adjustment Program represented the policies implemented by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (the Bretton Woods Institutions) in developing countries in the 1980s and 1990s. This policy change were conditions for getting new loans from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) or World Bank, or for obtaining lower interest rates on existing loans following the oil crisis which put burden on most economies especially the developing and the underdeveloped countries. Conditionalities were attached to ensure that the money lent will be spent in accordance with the overall goals of the loan. The Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs) are created with the goal of reducing the borrowing country's fiscal imbalances. The neo-liberal prescription has been seen as a panacea for spreading growth across space since it is market led but it has been challenged and criticized by many scholars that it brought more inequality across space than ever before; that it failed to restore economic growth in short and medium term run, introduction of SAP led to worse health status of people in countries which implemented SAP and that SAP do not address the

economic constraints of Sub-Saharan Africa (low levels of technology, human resource skills, small and fragmented markets).

Eventually, the current state of under-development (which has been described by scholars as a development crisis) on the African continent cannot be explained away from one perspective alone but several perspectives of exogenous and endogenous factors which have plagued the continent for decades. One of the exogenous causes of African underdevelopment widely alluded to by many scholars in the literature has to do with colonialism. Africa's underdevelopment, from the perspective of exploitation of precious natural resources, could be linked to her colonial experience. The system did not just introduce the exploitative capitalist system; it initiated the erosion of basic/enduring African system of values and accountability.

Moreover, indigenous African countries/citizens also played a very weak role in the world capitalist system with focus on production of raw material with less or no value which affects their relationship in the world market. Apart from the exogenous factors accounting for Africa's underdevelopment, there are equally important endogenous factors causing underdevelopment in Africa. One of such endogenous factors is corruption. Today, most African nation-states have been independent for forty years. Unfortunately, at forty, many of these nation states have made either minimal progress or stagnated, in terms of socioeconomic growth and development. Despite the fact that the continent's problems are multifaceted, corruption, particularly in countries where it has become an integral part of the social fabric, is a major handicap to their development efforts. Corruption may be defined simply as the misuse of entrusted power for private gain (Ineke, 2010; Transparency International, 2006).

The financial resource involved in these corrupt deals could have been channeled into useful projects that will help to stimulate growth and development in African countries. It is also important to take note of the fact that no single regime or government in Africa after independence has been excluded from corruption saga (as was the case of Ghana and Nigeria, for instance).

One offshoot of the foregoing is the fact that post-independent African nations are replete with weak sociopolitical institutions (besides other legal formations). In some sense, this retrogression could also account for the underdevelopment on the continent; this is also an endogenous factor in explaining the divergence in developed and the less developed and underdeveloped countries. Increasingly research has shown that weak, missing or perverse institutions are the roots of underdevelopment. Other explanations for development, such as technological innovation, investment, or years of schooling are not associated with higher rates of economic growth (Shirley, 2005; Easterly, 2002). The vast majority of Africans today live in countries that have failed to create or sustain strong institutions to foster exchange and protect persons and property. Most of African countries are suffering from these problems but a point must be made that, there are some countries whose institutions are weaker than others (Sudan, Congo, Somalia, *etcetera.*). Individuals in these countries enforce most bargains using informal mechanisms—private armies; threats to reputation; ostracism—and they have little trust. The state is either too weak to prevent theft of property by private actors, or so strong that the state itself threatens property rights and personal independence. Individuals and organizations face a high risk that they will not be able to realize a return if they invest in specific knowledge, skills, or physical assets, so they refrain from investment; production, innovation, and productivity are low and the economy festers (Shirley, 2005). The Nigerian experience in the Fourth Republic is a case in point.

NIGERIA'S 4TH REPUBLIC AND THE CRISIS OF DEVELOPMENT: A CRITICAL OVERVIEW

Nigeria's 4th Republic refers to the period of governance in Nigeria since 1999 on the basis of the democratic tradition. Specifically, *The Fourth (4th) Republic* has had four (4) regimes (Olusegun Obasanjo, Umaru Yar'Adua, Goodluck Jonathan, and Muhammadu Buhari). The main presuppositions in the work are garnered from the activities/developmental efforts or otherwise under those respective regimes. With the 4th republic as a period in Nigeria's modern history, reference, therefore, would be made to certain periods in the past and precursors of this history.

1999 marks the emergence of what is now referred to as *The Fourth (4th) Republic*. From the chaotic political situation, Abubakar organized and handed power to Gen. Obasanjo, though himself a stooge of the Northern oligarchy. Since 1999 may, Obasanjo has been termed a "bridge"¹² by the Northerners. Although he did take some hearty decisions, his tenure as Nigeria's president of the Fourth Republic is threatened by two important developments: how to revive a dead economy, rehabilitate the nation and sustain the nascent democracy, on the one hand; and how to grapple with the states and minorities fight and agitation for resource control—which no previous regime had had any serious consideration for since independence.

Theoretically, the democratic tradition of governance has held sway in Nigeria since 1999 (the Fourth Republic), also in the midst of underdevelopment. Its performances rest wholly on the rare persistency of the democratic tradition (spanning 23 years now) and the fragile national unity maintained thus far. However, to the extent the nation has bestowed the basic ideals of democracy are undetermined. Thus the Nigerian Fourth Republic has been marred with issues about hunger, insecurity, corruption many other infamies.

Official and local reports of corruption in Nigeria's 4th Republic abound in every local Nigerian and (sometimes) international news medium. Amid many other un-apprehended suspects, here are a few:

- a. Former Bayelsa State Governor, Diepreye Alamiyeseigha escapes to UK after EFCC arraigns him for embezzling 55 million dollars (Premium Times, 2016);
- b. Joshua Dariye, former Governor of Plateau State has been accused of (and jailed for) laundering 1.126billion naira (ecological funds)..having to be pardoned in 2022;
- c. Retiring Army Chief, Tukur Buratai discovered to own Housing Estates in Dubai and other Asian states, and stockpiling of foreign currency in several houses in Abuja; he was rather re-appointed Nigeria's envoy to Benin Republic;
- d. EFCC accused Minister Diezani Alison-Madueke of stealing 47.2billion naira and 487.5 million dollars in cash and property (www.efcc.govt.ng).

Notably, those issues and attitudes find established catalysts in tendentious party affiliations and constitutions, sponsored banditry/kidnapping—perpetuated by 'god-fatherism' in political succession and arm-twisted judiciary. Consequently, these further sink the country deeper in the shallows of infrastructural decay, lack and social-human under-development.

Corruption appears to be at the bottom of most of Nigerian social infamies. Two explanads contend in the attempt to understand the nature of corruption in contemporary Nigeria. In the first place, there is what is called *institutional failure*—a situation where there is lack of

developmental infrastructures not separated from the overbearing influence of the ruling class. Shuaib (2015) refers to such as institutional frailties. In fact, Ake (1985, 4) observes that “in the absence of autonomizing mechanisms in the post-colonial state, the resources of the state become the tools of particular groups, especially the hegemonic factions of the ruling class.:The second explanad is the disjointed idiosyncratic (cultural or ethnic) and behavioral dimensions of Nigerian citizenry and her other segments igniting untold unimaginable immoralities, impunity, and leading to further under-development (Okolo and Akpokhide, 2014)—this point is also validated by the UNODC (2017) report. These two accounts seem to validate Ekeh’s (1975) *two publics* theory (civic and primordial). Moreover, both explanads indicate corruption in Nigeria as generic.

A general characterization/feature of contemporary Nigerian (African) politics and society suggests that while the nations of the world are embracing purposeful governance that guarantee development, the political actors of the Nigerian system are also celebrating recourse to legalized embezzlement, pabendalism, ringing; corruption, and other anti-people practices, after all, what can the people do if laws and gods “can understand”? But again, are all these acts or behaviors not against the oath of office at swearing in? Yet once one is not legally culpable, the oath is ineffectual (Asekhauno and Omamor, 2022). This is why Hobbes’s *Leviathan* is rather disabling than enabling in considering the people’s rights and the terms of the social contract; and even the gods are also disabled since the contract was not binding on them. So, occupants of positions, family heads, community leaders, administrators, teachers, lecturers, and all now operate and behave freely without fear or restraint as if we are back to the Hobbesian *state of nature*; boys and girls now uphold ‘next to nudity’, and the inordinate pursuit of money, power, and influences, as expedience. The reason is not far-fetched: to satisfy a voracious self and ego and to care for large extended familial/primordial responsibilities (Uroh, 1998).But as ASUU (Academic Staff Union of *Nigerian* Universities) succinctly put it,

It is matter of ordinary human psychology that those who have benefited immensely and who derive political power from fraud are morally, politically and otherwise too weakened and too compromised to deal ruthlessly with corruption. Unfortunately in Nigeria ...compromised leaders determine who is accused and punished and who is not, and this has created severe credibility problems and handicaps in the struggle to defeat the cancer of corruption... They have made corruption in Nigeria an inevitable feature of the political culture into an art and a political industry. There is abandonment of social welfare by a government that was sworn in to protect the people. Corruption is so systematic that superficial, occasional arrests and dismissals will not make a dent in fighting it. A major problem is that the processes/mechanisms and organs established to address corruption are, themselves, suspects. No public investigation has been established.... Public support for any anti-corruption campaign depends on the public perception of the institutions involved and the credibility of such institutions (ASUU, 2005, 2-4).

At the judicial sphere, Judges and Solicitors are no longer harbingers of justice; they have become collaborators and accomplices in crime. To worsen the situation, persons are, on oath, sworn into offices or admitted to the evidence duck, and yet, lie.

Thus in Nigeria, corruption and mal-doing is both ubiquitous and historical; the resultant underdevelopment is also evident and palpable. Regrettably, many attempts have been made to

stem the tide and re-direct the trajectory; but such have also proved futile. In fact, Asekhauno (2017) put it thus:

There is copious data/record indicative of Nigeria as one of the world's most corrupt countries; ...and she also has tried to emerge from it. Yet, underdevelopment and degradation thrive everywhere; plundering of public coffers persists; stealing and destruction of state property seem unassailable; the economy is in comatose; there is ignorance amidst increasing school-education; health services remain mere consulting centers; power and other amenities remain epileptic or non-existent, amongst other infamies. Unfortunately, public and private actors (solely or in some connivance) perpetuate the evil corrupt practices. As the tide needs to be tamed, the national government has instituted some anti-graft agencies; but they have been much of toothless bulldogs.

ESCAPING THE CRISIS OF DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: SOME PRAGMATIC OPTIONS

Africa, like all developing nations, wish to be at par with the developed countries and let us suggest some ways for propelling development on the continent of Africa—with the theory of the developmental state as our guide.

In the first place, traditional culture should be sifted to etch out the useful from the antiquated to match with modernity—education, science and development. Experts have pointed out the place of culture, that it is helpful in understanding economic development. Perhaps the broadest statement comes from the pen of David Landes: Max Weber was right. If we learn anything from the history of economic development, it is that culture makes almost all the difference. Elaborating on Landes's theme, Japanese economist Yoshihara Kunio writes, "One reason Japan developed is that it had a culture suitable for it (Harrison, 2006). It is therefore important on the part of African leaders to focus on their culture in relation to development from economic perspective, Sen's perspective on development, etc. The culture and development nexus brings to mind the Confucian ethics which is a contemporary theory linking economic development to cultures of some countries as a ramification of observation of some countries economic progress since the World War II. Example of such countries includes Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, etc. Therefore, it is essence on the part of African countries to look inward to their culture in development effort. In fact, there are certain elements of Africa's rich cultural heritage that has led to the evolution and mastery of technical knowledge with respect to the arts, textile industry, craft, music technology and food technology, in which most African societies have made some progress, and have attracted cross-geographic exchange and interaction (Ogungbure, 2011).

Secondly, national citizens/Africans should be encouraged to patronize made in African goods and reduce their taste for foreign goods which is eroding gains that should have been made by African countries should they patronize what is produced in their countries.

Third, emphasis on strong institutions in African countries can be a panacea for African development and not having strong political leaders as it pertains in Africa. This is in tandem with statement by President of USA; Barack Obama when he made a statement that, Africa needs strong institutions and not strong leaders when he met late President Mills of Ghana in 2009. Having a strong institutions can help fight against corruption since the system will be tight to address issues of corruption of whatever form- political corruption which is paramount in Africa as well as corruption in the civil service, etc. In addition, to combat the pernicious problem will require putting in place appropriate anti-corruption and legal machinery; and

prosecute without fear and favour. The low incidence of corruption by the governing elites in countries like Denmark, New Zealand, Sweden, Singapore, Finland, Iceland and the Netherlands is present, thanks to rational legal bureaucratic practice, is evidence that corruption can be contained (Uneke, 2010). And this cannot be achieved if there exists no strong institutions and therefore, having strong institutions in Africa will be in the right direction toward development.

Fourth, transfer of technology is another pathway which can aid in Africa's development. Technology is basically defined as an application of scientific knowledge to practical problems whilst transfer of technology on the other hand has to do with the processes by which technological knowledge moves within or between organizations and countries; it can be international technology transfer. Technology transfer is an important means by which developing countries can gain access to technologies that are new to them. For example, the acquisition of foreign technologies by East Asian newly industrialized countries, coupled with endogenous technological learning efforts to accumulate the capability to change technologies have been key factors in their rapid technological and economic development. African countries can do the same but definitely there are challenges of acquisition and mastery of technology, both costly and time-consuming, acquired technologies often need to be adapted to local conditions- hence the issue of appropriate technology. All in all, transfer of technology can help African countries in all aspects of their economies toward development.

A fifth suggestion is that the government should ensure institutional autonomy and enhanced efficiency of the anti-graft agencies such as ICPC, EFCC, the judiciary, and policing.

The sixth prospect for Nigerian (and indeed, African) development has to do with the government strategically positioning itself in the world capitalist system being perpetuated by globalization and its compelling forces. In order for globalization to have positive impacts on Africa's development, national governments must have the choice to choose among apt monetary, fiscal, trade, macroeconomic and other economic and social policies without heavy-handed intrusion by the developed countries and the multilateral institutions these countries control. In short, a more democratic international economic and political environment is a *sine qua non* for sustained and broad based economic development to take place in Africa.

CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, the development gap between the developed (core) and the underdeveloped (periphery) countries has remained an issue among development experts, academics, politicians and students of development studies. Various development theories of different nature- meta and micro narratives on development have been advanced but the gap between the developed and the underdeveloped countries is widening by days. Various factors have been advanced for African underdevelopment comprising both endogenous and exogenous factors of colonialism and the scramble for African continent, world capitalist, corruption, geographical location and weak institutions. Despite the above causes, there is still hope for Africa's development. Consequently, for Africa (Nigeria) to develop, there is the need:

- a. To be an emphasis on strong institutions in African countries,
- b. there should be adequate transfer of technology to the continent,
- c. Africans should ensure that they strategically position themselves in the world capitalist system.

- d. In addition, African States should evolve policies that are development oriented. These should aim at reducing poverty and inequality. This is particularly in Africa, where there is no linkage between policy formation and policy implementation.

Finally, and with the dawn of President Tinubu's Administration (May, 2023) as I conclude this paper, there is renewed hope for new/more effective strides in the areas of security, the economy/job creation, agricultural/infrastructural development, amid practical steps to relieve the pains and pangs of poverty and reverse the underdeveloped trajectory in Nigeria.

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